

**Influence of Ethical Leadership on Employees' Job Strain and
Outcomes, Moderating Role of Organizational Compassion**

BY

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Declaration by Student

I, the undersigned, declare that this is an original work of mine not submitted to any other institution, college, or University other than the University of the West of Scotland for academic credit.

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List of Abbreviations

EL	Ethical Leadership
OC	Organizational Compassion
EJS	Employee Job strain
EOC	Employee outcomes
M	Mean
SD	Standard Deviation
%	Percentage
β	Beta
ELQ	Ethical leadership Questionnaire
POS	Positive Organizational Scholarships

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ABSTRACT

In recent years' ethics has emerged as a leading subject of discussion in contemporary organisations. The topic of ethical leadership is still making headlines all around the world. Countries like Pakistan are not exempt from ethical lapses resulting in intense job strain and ineffective outcomes for the organisation. Based on existing literature such as (Brown, Trevino and Harrison, 2005; Mayer et al., 2009), this study investigated the influence of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan with specific emphasis on the exploration of the moderating role of organisational compassion. The study employed descriptive and correlation research designs to determine the nature of the relationships. To maintain methodological rigour, the researcher used the most established quantitative survey technique and collected data through structured questionnaires from 200 employees working in Islamic banks of Pakistan. The researcher used correlational statistics to determine the relationship between the variables listed above. Data analysis has been performed using appropriate statistical tools such as simple, multiple, and regression analyses. This served as the foundation for the in-depth analysis, findings, and suggestions.

The key findings of the study showed a substantial negative relationship between ethical leadership and employee job strain, a direct relationship with employee outcomes, and a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between organisational compassion, employee job strain and outcomes. The contribute to the body of knowledge theoretically by conducting SLR and providing entire understanding of ethical leadership influences. The research expands the literature on ethical leadership by investigating the EL influences with organizational compassion practices. The research also contributes practically to HRM and HRD departments to enhance employee outcomes. The research provides empirical evidence to address employee job strain problem by incorporating ethical leadership and organizational compassion practices.

Based on the findings, the study made the following conclusions. Islamic Banking sector and overall banking organisations in Pakistan should provide ethical leadership to their employees along with the acts of organisational compassion practices; this will improve outcomes for employees by reducing their job strain level. This study was valuable since it was the first of its kind in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector, in which the workforce was provided with the opportunity to generate empirical data relating to the ethical behaviour of their leaders, as well as to recognise the value of compassionate practices. The results bare significant implications for management in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan, as they have a responsibility to ensure ethics remain an ongoing discourse, and the essence of compassion must be at the heart of overall management responsibilities. This research has opened new horizons for future research. The findings identify significant implications for the Islamic banking sector and the overall banking industry in Pakistan. Finally, Islamic banking organisations in Pakistan should not only consider a financial resource, but they should also consider the fact that other variables can impact their employment outcomes.

Keywords: Ethical Leadership, Organizational Compassion, Employee Job strain, Employee outcomes.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The first chapter presents an overview of the thesis, outlining its rationale, the gaps in known literature, and how the research addresses these gaps. As a prelude to the study's goals and objectives, it enumerates the research context and setting of Pakistan's Islamic banking sector. Moreover, it provides a brief overview of the structure of the thesis so that navigation throughout the document will be simplified.

1.1 Problem Statement and Research Gap

The critical issue of employee job strain and its effects on performance has been a never-ending debate in organisations worldwide. Over time, the severity of the situation increases. Researchers have been investigating different factors that can contribute to the solution of this problem, and ethical leadership has become the researcher's focus of investigation in the past decade. Job strain is a global phenomenon that adversely affects employees' health, outcomes, and overall organisational efficiency. The researcher found, in literature, that a major segment of research related to job strain and ethical leadership has been carried out in the western world; however, a considerably low amount of this research is related to the Eastern world, and this initiated the research gap to conduct research in eastern countries. Although researchers have tested different mediators and moderators to investigate the relationship between employee job strain, employee outcome and ethical leadership, the quest for effective mediators and moderators continues. Research confirmed that the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan is one of the top sectors suffering from job strain, and no research has been conducted to address this problem in the past ten years (Abid et al., 2013). Even though ethical leadership practices are a key component of Islamic banking, current trends indicate that these practices are insufficient to address the main issue of employee strain and performance (Ahmed and Ramzan, 2013). Consequently, there is a tremendous potential to find additional factors that enhance ethical leadership practices to make them more effective.

In this scenario, it was imperative to conduct research in the eastern culture, especially the Islamic Banking Sector of Pakistan, to confirm the results conducted in the western world, where

culture, environment, work conditions and atmosphere are different. In addition, there is a high need to test a unique moderator (which the researcher identified as organisational compassion) that could contribute effectively to the body of research related to job strain, ethical leadership and employee outcome. The researcher recognised that there was a desperate need to hear from the workforce of the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan to learn from them about their viewpoints on ethical leadership and its influence on their job strain and outcomes. Furthermore, the author recognised the importance of organisational compassion and the potential impact it could have on workers' outcomes in the Islamic banking sector, considering the absence of empirical investigations on the subject. For this reason, the researcher chose to conduct a quantitative research study to address the problem and cater for the research gap in the East, specifically in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan.

Therefore, the researcher proposed the following questions to address the problem of high job strain and its adverse impact on employee outcomes and thus addressing the research gap in the East related to job strain and ethical leadership (none in the Islamic Banking Sector of Pakistan) and testing of effective variable organisational compassion.

1. What is the influence of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan?
2. Does organisational compassion moderate the effect of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes?

1.2 Background

In recent times, practitioners, academics and scholars have progressively appreciated the significance of employee outcomes for the organisation's overall performance (Buldan et al., 2021). Outcomes of employees determine organisational achievement (Ermita, Syamsudin and Sugeng, 2021). A large body of knowledge has now established these conclusions (Faez et al., 2021; Effendy, 2021; Wanasida et al., 2021; Sciarelli, Gheith and Tani, 2020). Organisations need to keep their employees performing well to retain effectiveness. However, they also must find solutions to problems that hinder their efficiency (Al-dalahmeh, Khalaf and Obeidat, 2018).

Outcomes of employees have been drastically affected by job strain experienced by employees due to increased convoluted and accelerating demands at the workplace (Rasool et al., 2020). Research conducted in several countries has recognised job strain as one of the crucial problems (Siu, 2003). Dwindling individual health and sickness have been reported as the consequences of work-related strain (Rusbult and Van Lange, 2003; Kram and Hall, 1989). This scenario has resulted in a considerable decline in employee outcomes, managerial efficiency and organisational health-related expenses (Kim et al., 2020; Ahsan et al., 2009). At workplaces worldwide, strain is a common experience among employees. Predominantly, an elevated job strain risk is found in human service professions (Greenglass and Burke, 2003; Santos et al., 2003; Cox, 2021; Shane, 2010). Business organisations are the most human profession influenced by job strain (Havlovic and Keenan, 2020). In this scenario, it became extremely important for organisations to focus on this issue and make effective strategies to reduce strain as it directly affects the outcomes of employees and, ultimately, the organisation's overall success (Strydom, 2021).

From the literature, it is evident that researchers continuously explore the role of ethical leadership in managing job strain (Cox, Griffiths and Rial-Gonzalez, 2000; Lallukka et al., 2008; Simpson, Farr-Wharton and Reddy, 2020; Bormann, 2017). Ethical leadership is expected to be among the most valuable style for escalating employee outcomes at work, particularly in modern business organisations (Theriou, Chatzoudes and Moya, 2020). Within organisations, ethical leaders are key to ensuring employees' required set of outcomes and behaviours (Sarwar et al., 2020). Required outcomes may include reduction of job strain and enhancing efficiency (Nassif, Hackett and Wang, 2020). Ethical leaders are honest and supportive to their employees at times when employees' morals and their well-being are low (Mahsud, Yukl and Prussia, 2010). Employees receive help and care from their ethical leaders, who serve as a powerful resource for them as emotional support (Qin et al., 2018). This factor can have a great tendency to positively affect employees' overall well-being in the workplace. Brown (2005) suggested that an ethical leader might have a huge tendency to significantly affect employee attitude and behaviour at work. Piccolo et al. (2010) suggested that ethical leaders enhance task significance and might also affect employee outcomes. Researchers have studied negative behaviour in combination with ethical leadership (Hsieh et al., 2020; Islam, Ahmed and Ali, 2019; Ali et al., 2021). However, now

researchers are more interested in positive outcomes associated with ethical leadership, particularly in the context of employee outcomes, well-being, and overall performance. The relationship between ethical leadership and employee outcomes needs significant investigation, as well as how ethical leaders can ensure the success of an organisation by utilising human resources effectively.

It is noticeable that most research exploring the connection of ethical leadership with other variables took place in the Western world (Schwepker and Dimitriou, 2021; Jeon and Kwon, 2020). Eastern countries are not exempted from the global phenomena of job strain. It is equally important to conduct research in eastern countries as they are understudied areas, offering great potential to investigate concepts and theories tested in the Western world regarding differences in environmental, cultural values, and norms.

Researchers are testing new moderators and mediators that can effectively improve employee performance through ethical leadership (Zaim, Demir and Budur, 2021; Wadei et al., 2021; Shafique, Kalyar and Rani, 2020). In the quest for an effective moderator in the above relationship, organisational compassion bears a significant influence on employee job strain (Guinot et al., 2020). Compassion within an organization has been observed to have long-standing applications and practices in clinical, behavioral, and religious fields (Kitson, 2020; Alacovska, 2020; de Souza et al., 2020). However, the application of organisational compassion in business has been very recent (Dey et al., 2020; Frost, 2006). An emerging area of research focusing on compassionate practices in the workplace has a logical context and relevance to the well-being of both individuals and organizations (Dutton, Lilius and Kanov, 2007; Lilius et al., 2011). Despite ongoing research, employers and employees remain unaware of the outcomes and impacts of organizational compassion in the workplace (Miller, 2007; Vogus and McClelland, 2020; Ko, Kim and Choi, 2021). In terms of organizational compassion, the workforce was overwhelmingly convinced of its importance. They explained that they felt connected and valued when they received compassionate acts from others within the organization (Frost et al., 2000; Dutton, Workman and Hardin, 2014). Organisational compassion is at the heart of the concept of being ethical, as it contributes to the personal and social welfare of individuals and the organization (Sznajder, 2001; Höijer, 2003).

To briefly summarise, from the above context, three facts highlighted by studies were noteworthy, eliciting the researcher to choose this area for investigation. First, the researcher realised the pain of employees' job strain in the workplace and wanted to propose an effective solution. Second, the researcher wanted to cover the research gap by conducting a study in eastern countries. Thirdly, the researcher wanted to test a new moderator proposed, organisational compassion and its impact on chosen variables. Therefore, this research intended to determine how ethical leadership influences the overall employee outcomes and the job strain level in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector. It further attempted to study the moderating role of organisational compassion in the correlation of ethical leadership and employees' job strain and outcomes. These were the research aim, objectives, questions, and hypothesis.

1.2 Research Aim

This research examines the correlation among ethical leadership practices and employee job strain and outcomes in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector and considers the moderating effects of organisational compassion.

1.3 Research Objectives

1. To explore the relationship between ethical leadership and employee job strain and outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan with the assistance of a literature review and survey.
2. To investigate the influence of organisational compassion on ethical leadership, employee job strain and outcomes
3. To examine the significance of organisational compassion as a moderating factor.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What is the influence of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan?
2. Does organisational compassion moderate the effect of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes?

1.5 Research Hypothesis

H-1. Ethical leadership has a positive impact on employee outcomes

H-2 Ethical leadership has an indirect and opposite influence on employees' level of job strain experienced.

H-3 Organisational compassion moderates the influence of ethical leadership on employees' outcomes.

H-4 Organisational compassion moderates the impact of ethical leadership on employees' level of job strain experienced

1.6. Research rationale

The reason for deciding to investigate the impact of ethical leadership on employees' job strain and outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan was predominantly due to a current surge in the global phenomena of job strain in the workplace. The discussion on an ethical leader's impact continues to be an understudied area, and still, a huge amount of investigations are required to completely explore its implications on individuals and organisations in various contexts (Den Hartog and Belschak, 2012). The justification of the current study was to investigate the ethical leadership concepts in Pakistan, specifically in the Islamic banking sector, where the workforce suffers from a high level of job strain, according to research (Badar, 2011). Pakistan is an understudied region for research. There is great potential for conducting research in this region. As a developing state, Pakistan has many limitations in building a research culture. The major and exhaustible challenge is to deal with the inadequate and insufficient financial support to the universities for research. Comprehensive research is desperately needed in every area of Pakistan. The urgent need of the hour is for research to be greatly boosted in all areas of life, especially in the banking sector.

The Islamic banking sector of Pakistan is one of the leading organisations contributing 8% of the total banking industry (Ansari, 2013). According to the State Bank of Pakistan, assets under the management of Islamic banks in Pakistan have increased to PRs. 641 billion, depicting a 13 per cent quarterly increase. The advancement of Islamic banking services is critical to the country's economy (Furqani and Mulyany, 2009).

During the past few years, financial institutions in Pakistan have been faced with a vibrant, competitive, and fast-paced environment on both a national and international scale. The Islamic banking industry has now spread to all corners of the globe and appeared as a practical and viable alternative to the conventional banking system, which has numerous advantages. At present, Pakistan's Islamic banking has attained massive acceptance, despite its origins to satisfy the needs of Muslims. There is no doubt that Islamic banking sector of Pakistan is one of the most rapidly expanding areas of finance and banking. While most Islamic banks are in promising and/or Middle East states, many banks in developed countries are beginning to appreciate the enormous demand for Islamic banking products (Sufian, 2007). Islamic banking assets and deposits continued row throughout the quarter, increasing from Rs. 411 billion at the beginning of the quarter to Rs. 424 billion by the end of the quarter. Additionally, the year-over-year (YoY) growth was 31%.

Furthermore, at the end of the quarter, deposits and financing & investments increased by 38.2% and 17.7%, respectively, to Rs. 338 billion and Rs. 233 billion. As a result of the unique nature of Islamic business models, job stress is equally relevant to Islamic banks, which share many characteristics with their conventional peers, but are also exposed to additional risks (Chattha, 2020). The scarcity of short-term liquid assets and the deep money markets of Islamic banks make them particularly susceptible to liquidity and commodity price shocks. Additionally, Islamic banks require comprehensive collateralization of all borrowing and lending activities, mostly via precious metals or certain agricultural products. Moreover, most Islamic banks operate in emerging markets and developing economies (EMDEs), where the multifaceted nature of the shock presents complex (and in many cases unprecedented) macro-financial challenges. Due to a deterioration in investor sentiment, many EMDEs face acute strains from a sharp reversal of capital flows. This, in turn places pressure on exchange rates and credit spreads, increasing the likelihood of credit defaults, financial distress, and macroeconomic instability.

According to Gani (2012), the Islamic banking sector has grown significantly over the past decade. It has been subject to swift and remarkable changes in accordance with the demands of globalization and liberalization. In the Islamic banking industry of Pakistan, competition has increased as a result of the entry of private, international, microfinance, and other corporate banks into the market. Therefore, downsizing or right-sizing, efficient operations management, bringing synergy, new innovative ideas, and technologies are becoming increasingly critical in this sector.

In the banking sector and among its employees, such levels of competition and evolving concepts create pressure and stress. Globalization, accompanied by technological advancements, has drastically altered conventional patterns in all sectors due to privatization policies. There is an increasing trend of occupational stress in Islamic banking affecting all categories of workers, as well as families and society. Since no considerable amount of research has been conducted in this sector in terms of ethical leadership and job strain, it was deemed relevant for the researcher to investigate this neglected area.

This study aimed to investigate further the influence of ethical leadership on job strain and employees' outcomes and brought empirical evidence related by testing organisational compassion as a moderator within this relationship. The current scenario was important to the researcher because, as a research scholar and Pakistani, it was a great opportunity for the researcher to contribute to the literature by exploring a highly important but neglected sector of Pakistan in terms of research and proposing solutions to the problems by providing empirical evidence.

1.6.1 Research Significance

This study intended to make a conceptual and realistic contribution by emphasising problems associated with the job strain employees face due to immense global situations. As a result, twenty-first-century business organisations cannot provide a supportive work environment to their employees to meet the challenges and show required production and outcomes. To respond to the requirements of the modern challenges of the business world, employees require a sense of association, compassion, and sharing in the workplace, which is impossible to attain without peace of mind. Individual suffering at work must be considered to a significant extent by taking the well-being of the individuals as an essential factor. It is, therefore, imperative to find the solution to these problems so that the well-being of employees can be ensured (Marques, 2006).

Theoretical significance

This investigation contributes to the research literature by addressing the correlation between ethical leadership and employee job strain in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan with the moderating role of individual compassion. The research provides empirical support that generates and presents evidence relating to the employee sufferings at the workplace, the experiences of ethical leadership and the organisational compassion influences. Previous research

has mainly examined the link between ethical leadership and job strain, the reasons for job strain, and the coping strategies, but the influence of ethical leadership and organisational compassion in this context have been little explored.

Further, this study contributes explicitly to the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan. This study adds grist to the little but growing body of empirical research involving ethical leadership, work strain and organisational compassion, especially regarding Pakistan's Islamic banking sector. Therefore, the researcher has endeavoured to elucidate for the first time the nature of the relationships that these experiences of employees at work hold with crucial occupational health outcomes: job strain. Integration of the study of the ethical leadership domain with occupational outcomes as measures of well-being represents a significant theoretical advancement in management literature.

Practical Significance

This study was significant to the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan and focused on the workplace issue and a practical way to address the problem. The research was significant as ethical leadership is a continuous subject of attention in business organisations (Resick et al., 2011). This research presented opportunities for future studies. This research has paved the way for the researcher and others in the years ahead regarding ethical leadership, job strain, and employee outcomes in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector. Additionally, it was appropriate to study as little or no work has been done related to this subject, and little or no empirical evidence was on record reflecting the variables studied to make decisions. There has been no thorough study of the influences of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes within Pakistan's Islamic banking industry.

Furthermore, there was no evidence to suggest that organisational compassion within the organisation impacts these outcomes. The study outcomes are original because they show significance in the area researched. The goal of the research was to discover answers. Consequently, this study attempted to conceptualise its findings within a larger body of research. The study is of high quality in terms of information creation that is practical and relevant outside of the research environment.

Research findings encouraged more connections and collaboration between researchers, which might improve related field investigations. The research findings opened the door to further study by other researchers to support the knowledge base and skilled enterprises in the field. Most previous research has contributed to investigating the correlation of ethical leadership and job strain and the reasons related to job strain and coping strategies. However, an insufficient investigation has been done to examine the effects of ethical leadership and organisational compassion in this context. Further, this study contributes explicitly to the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan. This research enhances grist to the little but growing empirical body of knowledge involving ethical leadership, job strain and organisational compassion, especially regarding the Islamic banking sector.

Therefore, the objective of this study was to use quantitative methods in order to obtain empirical evidence in support of the argument that ethical leadership is vital to employee job strain and outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan. This knowledge is generalisable as it represents the global phenomena, and the situation within the Islamic banking sector is no different from the conventional banking sector or overall business organisations. The researcher has posited an evidence-based answer to a problem in the workplace that can assist organisations in enhancing ethical leadership by raising awareness of the effects of ethical leadership and the implications for organisational compassion. While several researchers, including Brown, Treviño and Harrison (2005), Resick et al. (2006), and Walumbwa et al. (2011), have acknowledged leadership, this study specifically aimed Islamic banking sector and so differed in its application in the means of delivering contextual and generalisable information.

1.7 Purpose

According to research (Pedler and Abbott, 2008), addressing workplace issues necessitates first recognising the concern and then acting in light of new information obtained through discussion and involvement of people in the organisation. This research aimed to dive deeper into the influences of EL practices on job strain and employee outcomes. In addition, gathering empirical evidence using organisational compassion as a moderator sheds light on the subject. The goal was to employ a quantitative approach to explore the relationship between variables to produce realistic results. To generate and interpret data within a contextual setting, the study took

a quantitative approach. Using the survey method, empirical data was collected, and regression analysis was used to produce meaningful conclusions. The study was completed by conducting a survey which gathered the responses of 200 employees. Data analysis led to the interpretation of the survey results as helpful information.

Originality

Originality refers to the aspect of a work that is distinct from reproductions, copies, derivations, or falsifications (Guetzkow et al. 2004). Original work is not published by others nor copied or based on the work of others. Since it is a study document written by the researcher who conducted the research, this thesis is considered original. The researcher identified the research question, hypothesis and purpose of the study. The researcher chose the analysis methods and unique variables were employed in the study. Essentially, it is a work which has never been published elsewhere.

Under-studied region

As in other developing countries, Pakistan faces psychosocial, and environmental problems that cannot be resolved by research conducted in the developed world (Sabzwari, Kauser, & Khuwaja, 2009). This often results in research topics that do not address the issues facing Pakistan's society (Haider & Mahmood, 2007; Hoodbhoy, 2009). Compared to research conducted in more advanced countries, this situation is quite different. It is a common objective of research in Europe to produce answers that will not only have global relevance but will also improve the economic competitiveness of the region by transferring knowledge to private businesses (Hoodbhoy, 2009; Tarar, 2006). It is the responsibility of educational institutions in general, and universities, to encourage students to ask questions and engage in research (Khalid & Khan, 2006). Unfortunately, in Pakistan, the money released by HEC for research is not consumed by quality research that in one way or another can contribute to the stock of knowledge and positively impact Pakistani society; rather, it has resulted in distorted priorities and considerable waste of resources (Hoodbhoy, 2009).

A research culture considers both disciplinary and interdisciplinary ideas and values. It also provides as a conducive environment for researchers to flourish as individuals with their own research abilities. In addition, it includes the enthusiasm of academics to participate in research projects (Evans, 2007). In higher education institutions, research culture refers to the type of environment that encourages academics to perform research. Research culture may be described as the way we do research in an institution (Rao, 2003). A university or higher education institution's research culture is defined by Bako (2005) as a framework within which students and supervisors work collaboratively to build capacity and intellectual capital in collaboration with stakeholders and/or funding bodies. It has been reported by The News (2010) that faculty members of higher education institutions do not bother to update their knowledge and professional competencies through research activities along with a lack of interest and creativity on the part of their students.

Pakistan is an understudied region in terms of research. This region has enormous potential for conducting research. Being a developing and impoverished country, Pakistan has many limitations regarding the development of a culture of research. Providing adequate financial support to universities for research is a significant and exhausting challenge. Comprehensive research is urgently needed in Pakistan across all fields. There is a crucial need for research to be accelerated in all areas of life, including the banking sector. In this case, a study has been conducted that attempts to pursue research in this understudied region. Research in Pakistan has provided researchers with opportunities to further explore this understudied region.

Understudied Area

This category pertains to explanations of original research, as it has been performed on an area under evaluation or a known period. This study falls within this category since it has been conducted in Pakistan and specifically in the Islamic banking sector, one of the country's most understudied areas. The research topic, the emphasis on job strain, and the organisational compassion concept are all novel developments in Pakistan, particularly in the Islamic banking sector. This study examines the Islamic banking sector in Pakistan to meet the urgent need for research in this area. It has been noted by numerous commentators over the years that there is a lack of research in Pakistan. It is also a topic of discussion in academic institutions. Almost all

discussions relating to such topics emphasize the lack of adequate funding and facilities as the primary reasons why research has not been conducted in the country on a large enough scale.

New Topic

This study is unique in its combination of leadership and organisational compassion, a concept that has not previously been explored in studies on leadership and job strain. The concept of organisational compassion has always been present in the field of medicine and nursing and has not been researched in the context of business organisations. Therefore, the topic is novel and original and opens new vistas for the body of knowledge in business administration. It is a subject that was studied once in the western world; though it has fallen out of fashion in many parts of the world, it is still relevant in some parts of the world, such as Pakistan. Compared with previous studies done in the subject area, the current study provides a fresh perspective and a deeper understanding of the topic.

Original Data

This group focuses on the original nature of data descriptions as opposed to the originality of their use of the data. It includes evidence, documents, records, materials, or data. The current study meets this criterion since the data is original and gathered from various branches of Islamic Banks throughout the region. This data enabled the researcher to visualise relationships between variables, understand their connection, and generate reasonable outcomes from their analysis. Primary data was obtained to fulfil the research objectives and produce fair and original results.

Original Results

Research findings are original as they contribute new insights, interpretations, and understandings to the field. Researchers, business organisations, and academia will find the results original in generating new perspectives. The results present novel interpretations of the data gathered. The study is original as it presents the issue from varied perspectives, contributing to its originality.

New Findings

A research finding is considered original when it has the potential to significantly impact the field in which it was conducted. The purpose of the research was to provide actionable insights. The present study tries to contextualise its findings in the context of broader research practice. The

research is of high quality in terms of creating useful and applicable information outside the research environment. Research findings may lead to more connections and collaboration between researchers, improving related field investigations. Other academics can continue to study the research findings to develop the knowledge base and skilled enterprises in the field.

In summary, with the purpose of the study, the researcher discussed the significance of conducting research in ethical leadership, its need and uniqueness in the context of an understudied area, its theoretical and practical importance, and its goals and objectives. Consequently, the results of this study have significance not only for the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan but also for its stakeholders, the wider business arena, and their communities.

1.9 Structure of Thesis

The thesis is organised into seven sections. Subsequent to the introduction, which includes the research gap, background, objectives, questions, hypothesis, and research significance, the second chapter, includes the literature review and discussion on the four key works of literature: job strain, employee outcomes, ethical leadership, and organisational compassion. It incorporated the previous research concepts concerning these key variables in this study. The literature laid the foundation for the development of a conceptual model and the generation of hypotheses, which guided the study further. The third chapter provides an explanation of the theoretical foundations underlying the relationships examined in this research and a summary of the proposed hypotheses. The fourth chapter discussed the methodological insights of the study. Following the study objectives, this study took a posit stance, employing survey data gathered from employees in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector. The data generated and the results of the study are presented in chapter five. In the sixth chapter, the findings of the study are discussed, in addition to the contribution of the study to knowledge and practice. Finally, chapter seven brought this thesis to a close by highlighting limitations and recommendations for future research.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

A review of the theoretical constructs that formed the foundation for the conceptual framework is presented in this chapter. In this way, it hoped to gain insight into the relationships explored within the conceptual model. This analysis is incorporated in several bodies of literature. This chapter reviewed previous and current studies to examine the relationships between all four research variables. Despite including other perspectives, the primary focus remained on ethical leadership as initiated by Trevino and Brown (2005).

Several theoretical backgrounds have been analysed to understand the relationship between leadership and other variables in the body of knowledge. Ethical leadership influences social learning (Bouckenooghe, Zafar and Raja, 2015; Brown et al., 2005; Khuong, Linh and Duc, 2015). The social exchange process theory is the other theoretical foundation that anchors this research. Like the social learning theory, it proposes that individuals make choices by knowingly or unknowingly weighing the risks and consequences of a connection or response, eventually seeking to increase their benefit (Homans, 1960). According to Expectancy theory Oliver (1974), people behave in a particular manner because they are encouraged to prefer a particular activity over a different activity by having a knowledge of outcomes. Moreover, Weiss and Cropanzano's (1996), Effective events theory discusses the connections between employees' internal influences (such as thought patterns, feelings, and states of mind) and their responses to situations in the workplace that affect their performance, commitment to the organisation, and work satisfaction.

The second primary body of literature covers employee job strain and outcomes. The literature on individual job strain and outcome is then embedded with the literature on ethical leadership, empirical linkages between these three variables are addressed, and general direct and indirect relationships between variables are recommended. Lastly, the concepts of organisational compassion as a moderator are examined to determine its significance in determining in which way ethical leadership understandings are correlated with employee workplace strain and employee outcomes.

Figure [2.1] depicts the framework of this literature review to guide the reader through the chapter. Each section concludes with a summary highlighting the main points.

Figure 2. 1: literature review Structure

Moderator	Organisational Compassion <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Concept• Compassion at work• Organisational compassion in different contexts and measures
	Model <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Summary• Hypothesis
Summary	

2.1.1 Leadership

Leadership is one of the most thoroughly investigated areas in the behavioural sciences dating back to the 18th century (Cyert, 1990). The fundamental reason is that the overall success of organisations in terms of political, social and economic context depends on the leader's directions and excellence (Brown and Treviño, 2006). An excellent way of observing organisational success is through its leader (Denscombe et al., 1993). Previously, leadership was defined as a process (Barrow, 1977). Leaders and followers interact continuously to accomplish company goals as part of the leadership process. Essentially, leadership is the ability of a leader to influence others to reach a common goal. The process by which leaders and followers work together may differ from organisation to organisation. Eventually, consistency and accomplishment were incorporated into the definition of leadership (Kotter, 2001). Modern scholars define leadership in terms of relationships, influence, achievement, behaviour, persuasion and differentiation (Dinh et al., 2014). Leadership is expertise in motivating followers to achieve organisational targets (Plsek and Wilson, 2001). Effective leaders create a vision not only for followers but also for the organisation (Banutu-Gomez and Banutu-Gomez, 2007). Building a legacy of success in organisations is through its leaders and followers (Bennis, 2007). Leadership theories attempt to explain the nature

and influence of leadership and its outcomes (Giltinane, 2013). These concepts have been discussed in the past and are continuously catching the attention of modern scholars.

The discussion continued from the 1960s right up to the present day. They carry a variety of perspectives from traits to relationships and then move on to situational aspects, and the best way to define leadership is still being researched (Harrison, 2018). These perspectives blended various views about leadership; however, the best definition of leadership is not identifiable. According to Hughes (2014), leadership is a process of involving leaders and followers together to make a decision that satisfies both parties. Denscombe et al. (1993) argued that leadership motivates followers to behave in an acceptable way to the organisation. Northouse (2010), on the other hand, defined leadership as a process of influencing subordinates to achieve required objectives. Workman and Cleveland-Innes (2012) contributed to defining leadership as a process of influencing people to attain shared goals in the organisation. Drucker (2001) view on leadership is that it is a process of motivating individuals to increase their productivity. Hence leadership involves shared adjectives, influences, motivation, and people.

A breakthrough shift has swept the knowledge of leadership research in the 21st century. Leadership scholars have paid attention to an exclusive link between leadership and ethics and ethical leadership; hence this became one of the attractive areas of research by scholars not only from the organisational context but also from a social perspective (Lanctot and Irving, 2010; Parolini, Patterson and Winston, 2009; Russell and Zuckerman, 2001; Whetstone, 2002). In the past, leadership scholars argued that moral and ethical concerns should be separated from leadership (Barker, 2001; Cardona, 2000). Researchers have contributed to the literature regarding leadership by exclusively insisting on moral and ethical values in leadership (Northouse, 2010; Groves and LaRocca, 2011). A modern concept of leadership sees a leader as a moral person, and his moral character is essential for societal good and organisational success and achievement. As a result, the ethical focus in leadership appeared as ethical leadership theory. The applications and effectiveness of ethical leadership in organisations have emerged as an enormous opportunity for scholars to investigate and contribute to the body of knowledge. Ethics and leadership seem complementary to each other, and leaders should act morally correct in their actions (Sendjaya, 2005). More than 200 articles in peer-reviewed journals show relevance to ethical leadership (Brown, Treviño and Harrison, 2005).

2.1.2 Ethical leadership concept

Ethical leadership is an endorsement of right behaviour through decision-making and building a productive, trustworthy bond with followers and the public through integrity and honesty. Researchers insisted that ethical leadership is a character demonstration that promotes the right behaviour and will protect organizationally and followers' values (Anser et al., 2021; Ferrell et al., 2014). Since several decades have passed, a number of scandals involving public and corporate officials have heightened interest in investigating practices and implications related to ethical leadership (Brown and Trevino, 2006; Ghahroodi, Mohd and Seyedghorban, 2013). Ethical leadership principles and philosophy exhibited by an ethical leader's behaviour are significantly characteristic of numerous contemporary well-known conceptualisations such as Social Exchange and Social learning in leadership writing (Avolio and Gardner, 2005; Smith, Montagno and Kuzmenko, 2004). The investigation of ethical leadership's influence, outcomes, processes, and experiences has increased steadily over the past decade (Wilmore and Thomas, 2001). Trevino (2000) first introduced the perspective of ethical leadership as a distinctive concept. These preliminary findings informed further research into the ethical leadership framework and the development of instruments to measure ethical leadership.

The work of Trevino et al. (2000) assumes a two-dimensional idea, which includes the ethical man and the ethical supervisor. The moral man aspect relates to the leader's attitudes and practices (Kanungo and Mendonca, 2001). A moral person is fair and reliable. He is sociable and involved with other people and society and is also thought to be consistent both professionally and personally (Trevino, Hartman and Brown, 2000; Khuntia and Suar, 2004; Brown & Mitchell, 2010). The moral manager aspect concerns staff development, in which ethical leaders convey their standards of behaviour to followers and praise ethical conduct while penalising unethical behaviour in the workplace (Yukl, O'Donnell and Taber, 2009; Freeman and Stewart, 2006). Ethical leadership constitutes a process that includes participation, educating and creating awareness about what is right and wrong and setting an example of ethical behaviour for followers (Choi, Ullah and Kwak, 2015).

Trevino et al. (2000)'s conception of ethical leadership considers the leader's beliefs and how ethical actions are implemented among their employees. These dimensions are addressed by scholars in their scholarly contributions to ethical leadership literature. Ethical leadership can be

described as encouraging and motivating with the power of sense as regards achievement, healing with an element of love and compassion and supporting moral conduct (Kaiser and Hogan, 2010). Ethical leadership exhibits leaders as role models for followers because their behaviour is accepted as appropriate (Ciulla, 2005). Leadership insists on effective communication and participation and justifies leaders' actions to their followers (Harrison, 2017). Zheng, Wang and Li (2011) suggested a third aspect of ethical leadership in addition to the Trevino concept, including developing ethical standards. The third added aspect overlaps with Trevino's core concept of ethical leadership because the individual aspect reflects the good leader or manager, and ethical standards reflect in the ethical decision-making of a leader (Kannair, 2007; Bormann, 2017). As a matter of fact, in both eastern and western cultures, the understanding of ethical leadership dimensions seems to be almost comparable. Although the importance of ethical leadership appears to be highly regarded by scholars, a number of contemporary studies intend to advance ethical leadership by shifting the emphasis from the leader-follower connection to CSR (Voegtlin, 2016). Studies have investigated the relationship involving ethical leadership and corporate social responsibility; however, most have concluded that CSR is an outcome of EL and not a separate element (Saha et al., 2020; Zhu, Sun and Leung, 2014).

2.1.3 Ethical Leadership Definitions

Despite the similarities in conceptual understandings, different perspectives on EL are found in scholarly publications. One of the most widely used definitions is that provided by (Brown et al. 2005). EL is an exhibition of normatively proper behaviour employing actions, relationships, communication, and reinforcement (Brown, Trevino, and Harris, 2005). This definition is widely accepted but has a flaw that it does not specify what normatively proper behaviour is or is not (Frisch and Huppenbauer, 2014). This definition is further criticised by Harrison and Price (2017) because it concentrates on normativity, which he claims does not always relate to ethical behaviour. Eisenbeiß and Giessner (2012) fill this void by identifying standards that ethical leaders can use as guidelines. Eisenbeiss (2012) proposes four dispositions for normatively acceptable behaviour: humane, responsible, justice-oriented and moderate. Other definitions encompass moral beliefs or favourable personal characteristics that ethical leaders should possess to describe normatively correct norms and attitudes. They contend that by following ethical principles and making ethical choices, leaders must sincerely retain moral beliefs and favourable individual traits,

for instance, openness, reliability, integrity and truthfulness (Resick et al., 2006), consideration for others (Ruiz-Palomino, Sáez-Martínez and Martínez-Cañas, 2013), compassionate, empowering, and motivating individuals (Sabir et al., 2012). Regardless of variations in the definition of EL, most researchers suggest that ethical leadership primarily affects the norms and behaviours in the associations. Merely Tang et al. (2015) consider investors, indicating the potential effects ethical leaders may have. Over the years, scholars have defined ethical leadership in several ways, as shown in table [2.1] below.

Table 2. 1: Ethical Leadership Definitions

Author	Year	Definition
“Trevino et al.”	2000, p. 128	A leader who is committed to ethics and values must also be able to determine ways to bring this focus to the organisation, as well as formulate policies that will affect the behaviour of all employees.
“Brown et al.”	2005, p.120	Normatively suitable behaviour is modelled through the conduct of individuals and interactions with others, as well as encouraged by the exchange of information and feedback.
“Khuntia and Suar,”	2004, p. 14	Choosing the right ethical leader is not only about your charisma, but also about self-motivation, critical thought, consideration for others, willingness to serve, and asking how your followers are doing.
“Brown & Trevino”	2006	A distinguishing characteristic of ethical leadership is its concentration on ethical management, as opposed to other forms of leadership. In order to influence followers' ethical behaviours, leaders articulate moral guidelines and utilise positive and negative reinforcement in order to hold them accountable for their goals.
“Keith et al.”	2003, p.254	Show an excellent ethical conduct.
“Ruiz et al.”	2011, p. 590	An ethical leader is one who promotes ethical behaviour in employees through the use of their thoughts, ideas, attitudes, and moral behaviour.
“Zheng et al.”	2011, p. 181	Essentially, leadership is ethical in and of itself. It implies that leaders influence followers in an ethical manner. In addition to leading ethically, leadership is

		characterised by ethical behaviour. A leader, for example, lives ethically. Another way, they will enforce ethical behaviour and attitudes by establishing ethical values and creating an ethical environment for employees.
"Hartog and Belschak"	2012, p. 36	Leadership that is ethical has a significant impact on the consciousness and attitudes of followers.
"Arel et al.,"	2012, p. 352	Executive activities that promote or oppose an ethical workplace.
"Kacmar et al."	2013a, p. 33	Ethical leadership is characterised by behaviour that is consistent with accepted norms, as evident from the actions and connections of the leader.
"Beeri et al."	2013, p. 61	Ethical leadership is first and foremost about demonstrating ethical behaviour by the organisation's top management.
"Ruiz-Palomino et al."	2013, p. 33	It is highly desirable for ethical leaders to possess qualities such as honesty, reliability, empathy, consideration, and concern for others.
"Steinbauer et al., "	2014, p. 382	The role of ethical leaders is to demonstrate, express, and enforce right behaviour within an organisation. A leader should engage their followers appropriately, set a good example, manage ethics actively, and have an internalised moral viewpoint that gives them the ability to exercise idealistic influence on others.
"Lu & Guy"	2014, p. 5	An ethical leader is someone who offers direction and role modelling to the employee.
"Eisenbeiß et al."	2015, p. 637	As a higher-level construct, CEO ethical leadership encompasses five subcomponents: people orientation, integrity, fairness, responsibility, and balance.
"Tang et al."	2015, p. 398	An ethical leader should focus on acting ethically internally and on corporate social responsibility externally.

2.1.4 Ethical leadership Principles

Ethical leadership is based on some principles that exhibit its most important and prominent properties. These factors include, firstly, respect for others with honour. In organisations, ethical leaders respect and show extreme care for others with honour. In their treatment and dealings with others, they value people as ends in themselves instead of giving value as means to their ends (Mihelic, Lipicnik and Tekavcic, 2010b). In this way, they show and demonstrate that the followers have goals and objectives that the organisation acknowledges and have worth and significance. The caring acts include active listening to others, tolerance for conflicts and empathic feelings for others in the organisation (Thompson et al., 2008).

After that is the second factor, service for others. Ethical leaders give preference to others. Their important prime concern is to care for and support their subordinates. They serve and care for others in the organisation. They behave in a human fashion instead of behaving in dominance and authoritativeness (Theron, Van Aswegen and Engelbrecht, 2005). Their dealings include team building, giving power to others, mentoring and guiding (Elçi et al., 2012). Another vital factor is justice. While making any decision, ethical leaders ensure that altogether fairness, clarity, equal opportunity and justice must be the prominent and central parts of their decisions (Ruiz, Ruiz and Martínez, 2011). They take care of all subordinates in very equivalent conduct, excluding only if there is a very apparent requirement for discrepancy management and there is exactness about why it is necessary. In addition to being clear, the reason for discrepancy dealing should be ethically logical (Sims and Brinkmann, 2003).

A very crucial factor that contributes to ethical leadership is honesty towards others. Honesty is the main requirement of ethical leadership. Untruthfulness destroys belief. In contrast, truthfulness enhances trust and strengthens the leader's follower relationship (Berghofer and Schwartz, 2011). Honesty indicates openness by showing our way of thinking to others (Hansen et al., 2013). This led to establishing a level of openness with others, and disagreements are only generated in rare scenarios. Truthfulness and sincerity are the values the ethical leader must project (Hamoudah et al., 2021). Another essential factor is building community with others. Ethical leaders build community with others. This is a serious and critical chore because a leader has to influence subordinates to accomplish the required task and achieve a common objective (Smith, Montagno and Kuzmenko, 2004). So, leaders have to establish goals that prove appropriate for the

organisation and its commitments (Walumbwa, Morrison and Christensen, 2012). In the same way, research recognises an ethical leader as an individual with accurate morals and a concrete personality that positions illustrations for others and endures enticements (Kalshoven and Boon, 2012). It is to be noted that an ethical leader is an individual that exhibits a personality having prominent qualities and fair decision making, considerable care and empathy for the people at large, and a developed ethical behaviour in their professional lives (Brown and Treviño, 2006).

2.1.5 Ethical Leadership Research Measures

Most studies on EL and its implications for personal or organisational outcomes utilise a quantitative approach to assess ethical leadership. Although numerous measurements have been published, the scale developed by Brown et al. (2005) has been shown to be extensively applied (Ng and Feldman, 2015). Approximately 125 researchers have employed Brown's scale in measuring ethical leadership, which shows the dominance of the scale. More than 80% of research employed the ethical leadership scale to assess ethical leadership. This measurement integrates Trevino et al. (2000)'s ethical leadership pillars: the ethical individual and the ethical supervisor. Still, these aspects are often merged, and EL is viewed as single-dimensional (Chao and Wang, 2015; Zhu et al., 2015).

Similarly, Yukl et al. (2013) developed the measurement of ethical leadership (ELQ) that evaluates EL from a single-dimensional perspective, but it is far less recognised than the Brown scale. A number of scales have been developed to assess ethical leadership as multiple-dimensional including Kottke and Pelletier, (2013); Resick et al., (2006); Khuntia and Suar, (2004) are a selection of other multidimensional measurements of ethical leadership that have been utilised but seldom used in the publications. The ethical leadership scale developed by Pelletier and Bligh (2006) is unique in that it distinguishes between hierarchies of leadership within an organisation. Therefore, it is possible to study ethical leadership disparities within an organisation at various levels (Kottke and Pelletier, 2013; Beeri et al., 2013). Many studies measure the relationship of ethical leadership but how each ethical component is related independently to ethical leadership is also very important (Walumbwa et al., 2011; Zheng, Wang and Li, 2011). Since these measurements were developed specifically to assess ethical leadership, many studies use a wider variety of scale items taken from interwoven concepts such as immoral practices, moral integrity,

cross-culture leader conduct (Hanges and Dickson, 2004), equality, responsibility (Maak and Pless, 2006) or authoritarian (Farh and Cheng, 2000). Even after the availability of different measurements to evaluate EL for multiple settings and objectives, the published literature exhibits a great consensus around Brown et al. (2005). EL measure which views EL as a single-dimensional construct and is implemented in a variety of contexts.

2.1.6 Ethical Leadership Antecedents

Most of the investigation on the origins of EL concentrates on leader behavioural characteristics. According to Jones (1995), it is generally the character of an individual that determines whether they adopt or reject ethical criteria in real-world actions. Literature is evident from the last decade detailing the mounting importance of ethical leadership characteristics (Adnan, Bhatti and Farooq, 2020; Masood and Zia-ur-Rehman, 2017; Ofori and Toor, 2009; Mihelic, Lipicnik and Tekavcic, 2010). Appropriate characteristics of an ethical leader are openness (Ruiz, Ruiz and Martínez, 2011; Brown and Trevino, 2006; Kalshoven and Boon, 2012), moral responsibility (Resick et al., 2013; Mayer et al., 2012), moral character formation (Bonner, Greenbaum and Mayer, 2016), capacity to influence (Qabool et al., 2021; Banks et al., 2021; Banerjea, 2010), communication skill (Harvey et al., 2014) and honesty (King, 2008). Other research recognises organisational environment aspects that affect the rise of ethical leadership. Providing role models for leaders at lower levels of hierarchy appears to be an essential aspect of the organisational context. Numerous research findings directly relate to ethical leaders who prefer the focal leader (Frisch and Huppenbauer, 2014; Ruiz, Ruiz and Martínez, 2011; Mayer et al., 2009). Given that EL is primarily evaluated by a member of staff based on their perceptions about the leader, Frisch and Huppenbauer (2014) propose that employees' ethical attributes and how much they intermingle with the leader's attributes may alter conceptions of ethical leadership. Presuming that the morals of employees and leaders interrelate, conceptions of ethical leadership will be powerful (Jordan et al., 2013). A summary of the major characteristics of ethical leaders identified by scholars in a literature review can be found in the table [2.2].

Table 2. 2: Factors of ethical leaders emphasised by authors in a literature review.

Factors	Authors
Leader Attributes	(Adnan, Bhatti and Farooq, 2020; Masood and Zia-ur-Rehman, 2017; Ofori and Toor, 2009; Mihelic, Lipicnik and Tekavcic, 2010).
Sincerity	(Ruiz, Ruiz and Martínez, 2011; Brown and Trevino, 2006. Kalshoven and Boon, 2012)
Responsibility	(Resick et al., 2013; Mayer, 2012),
Ability to influence	(Qabool et al., 2021; Banks et al., 2021; Banerjea, 2010)
Honesty	(King, 2008; De Vries, 2012)
Team leader	(Mayer et al, 2012 ; Ruiz, Ruiz and Martinez, 2011; Greenbaum, 2009)
Communication skills	(Harvey et al., 2014)

2.1.7 Ethical Leadership Outcomes

The concept that being ethical is the proper thing to do is typically explained as why organisations should adopt ethical leadership (Poff, 2010). However, there is substantial support

that EL has a favourable impact on company performance. The investigation of the effects of ethical leadership looks at a broad range of aspects of personal and professional performance at various dimensions, including person, department, and institution. Hiller et al. (2011) categorise these outcomes as perceptions, behaviours, beliefs, and efficiency. Though table [2.3] is not comprehensive, it shows how ethical leadership has initially been associated with various perceptions, attitudes, and cognitions, individual and organisational efficiency. In terms of outcomes related to attitudes, the majority of the research results focused on confidence (Chughtai, Byrne and Flood, 2015), dedication (Harvey et al., 2014), welfare (Beeri et al., 2013), fulfilment (Brown et al., 2005), and inspiration as outcomes of ethical leadership (Frisch and Huppenbauer, 2014).

Similarly, studies also contributed to individual behaviours and attitudes in this respect (Bonner and Mayer, 2014) and ethical and unethical attitudes (Arel, Beaudoin and Cianci, 2012). Perspectives of the ethical environment, ethical norms and values, and equality are of particular interest (Demirtas and Akdogan, 2015). Literature also shows the link between ethical leadership and cognitive factors related to work, such as the perception of politics (Harris, 2013) and job demands (Kacmar et al., 2013) or job relevancy (Piccolo et al., 2010; Stouten et al., 2010). Regarding employee efficiency, EL is connected with overall and particular employee outcomes, such as creative and effective attitudes at the workplace (Tu and Lu, 2016). However, the study of individual performance has received less attention than research on attitudes and cognitions.

Despite studies showing a relatively favourable connection between ethical leadership and an organisation's performance, insufficient emphasis is placed on organisational efficiency (Ma, Cheng and Zhou, 2013). Literature shows an extensive exploration of the consequences of ethical leadership research focused on the personal level, leaving the group level entirely unexamined. Moreover, while there is a substantial information ground for the association between EL, behaviour and perceptions, the connection between EL and organisational efficiency has received little attention. This gap is huge in terms of specific factors related to employee and organisational outcomes compared to general performance measures.

Brown and Trevino et al. (2000) heavily influenced the current understanding of EL in their work exploring ethical leadership perspectives. There are numerous explanations and instruments, but Brown et al. (2005)'s explanation and EL scale are widely recognised in the literature as being one of the most effective. A major critique of Brown et al. (2005) definition of EL revolves around its ambiguity regarding what constitutes normatively acceptable behaviour and whether it can contribute to ethical practices. Many contemporary studies on ethical leadership address three key issues: the challenges that organisations face in putting ethics into practice, the ethics of the leader, and the impact that ethical leaders have on followers. The field of ethical leadership has many unexplored topics that require further investigation, and fresh research must be conducted (Monahan, 2012). Research linking ethical leadership and employee job strain and outcomes in the Eastern world has not been sufficiently studied. In research on the backgrounds of EL, the emphasis has primarily been on the personal characteristics of a leader and how these characteristics contribute to EL (Jones, 1995)

Additionally, it appears that ethical leadership in the workplace may be influenced by the organisation's environment and mentors, both inside and outside the organisation, which may influence the leader's behaviour (Kalshoven, Den Hartog and De Hoogh, 2011). By demonstrating ethical behaviour, fairness, social connection, and role modelling to employees, leaders can build stronger relationships that can influence their behaviour towards their work (De Cremer et al., 2011; Den Hartog and Belschak, 2012). There is evidence that ethical leadership can be essential in achieving improved employee outcomes, including superior job performance, involvement, and job demands (Avey, Palanski and Walumbwa, 2011; Lu, Kuo and Chiu, 2013; Walumbwa et al., 2011). Although the literature indicates a connection between EL and employee behaviour, insufficient findings evaluate the association between EL and employee work strain and performance, particularly in Eastern cultures.

2.2 Job Strain

Strain is an ancient concept that was limited to the Latin Word *Stringer*, which means to draw tight. However, in a modern definition, it is an individual's reaction to stressors present in the environment (Yang et al., 2021). It can also be taken as a normal response in an unusual condition when an individual wants to escape from this situation. Strain is explained in a way that it is a state of affairs in which one person demands his physical or mental energy atmosphere (Brooks et al., 2017; Banyu et al., 2021). The strain has also been defined as an event or condition that seemed intimidating, harsh or difficult (Hardie, Kashima and Pridmore, 2005). For the past years, many studies, articles and seminars have focused on the topic of stress differently (Coffey, 2004). The phrase strain was used for the first time by an American Physiologist who focused on the theory of fight and flight to explain the response of animals when they feel any threat from any outside event (Cummins, 1990). While explaining the influence of strain on humans, he also states that there must be a balance in the organic system of any human body because this balance collapse acts directly on the rude functioning of a body. A description given by Edwards et al. (2009) has linked the strain with the person's environment in the workplace. It explains that any stressful workplace causes different strain problems, and it is a misfit among a person's skills and abilities or demands of a person's job. It says that the reaction of a human depends upon the conditions, happiness and calmness of the workplace (Kokkinos, 2007; Alhurani et al., 2018). If this coordination is absent, then it will cause strain.

Strain is generally known as the pattern of physiological and psychological troublemaking reactions to events that mostly threaten the ability to adapt. Put another way, strain is the body's reaction to changes that create complicated requirements (Ramlawati et al., 2021). Strain can be either positive or negative, either. The positive strain is short-term and includes the motivation characteristics, feeling ecstatic and improving the outcomes. Negative strain, on the other hand, is called distress too. It can be short or long-term and may include depression, discomfort, lowering outcomes and psychological problems (Spielberger and Reheiser, 2020). The strain has been described as a condition that should cause a person to back from starting ordinary work due to changes in their emotional and physical conditions (Banyu et al., 2021). The long-lasting workplace strain triggers the industry's routine and repetitive course, which disturbs the worker's daily working schedule (Aguinis and Henle, 2002).

Job strain is an unpleasant and uncomfortable feeling that the individual feels on the job, resulting from requirements and constraints relating to job demands (Manning, Avramchuk and Carpino; Siu, 2003). Adverse attitudinal outcomes such as job strain have been linked with stressful work life and suffering (Kunz-Ebrecht, Kirschbaum and Steptoe, 2004; Spangenberg and Theron, 2005; Burke, 2002; Edwards and Rothbard, 2005). It has the worst effects on employees' and workers' health (Jamal, 2007). The National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health defines stress as damage to a person's physical and cerebral conditions, which occurs when there is any mismatch between the skills and environment of the workplace and when resources are not provided according to the needs or demands of the employees. The Executive of Health and Safety explains this job strain as a person's reaction when he feels burdened by the responsibilities and scope of the job. Recently, the strain was explained as a mood of a physical or mental burden linked with worry and pain; in response, a person wants a change (Amin, 2021).

Employee job strain has got an extensive range of concentration for numerous organizations. According to Selye (1985), strain is an inevitable outcome of life, and as a result, it can adversely affect the outcome of organizations. The American Institute of Stress reported that up to 80% of all injuries related to job strain and 40% of turnover related to the workplace are taken place where strain is identified as a significant factor (Atkins, 2007). In the U.K., strain is considered the second foremost cause of non-attendance among workers, as the Confederation of British Industry reported. It has been stated by European Foundation for Working Conditions that significant numbers of European working people are affected due to strain factors (Giga, Cooper and Faragher, 2003). A growing number of personnel reimbursement claims to ensue from work-related strain in the Australian State (Caulfield et al., 2004; Bytyqi, Reshani and Hasani, 2010). It can be understood from these explanations that work-related factors are caused by strain. The table [2.4] below records the categories of stressors related to workplace strain.

Table 2. 3: Classification of job stressors.

Indicators	Stressors
Job Description	Workload Complicated Job Excessive accountability Inconsistent/uncertain challenges."
Operating Environments	Inadequate environment Physically exhausting job
Job Terms	Less Salary Lack of Career Opportunities
Social Interaction	Weak Management Weak social assistance Centralization Bias

2.2.1 Job strain and Employee Outcomes

Employee outcomes have been declining, and the increase in job strain is coming from work delaying, globalization and lack of involvement (Naseer et al., 2020). Impassiveness from work is escalating due to downsizing, fierce competition, re-engineering and consolidation (Makawatsakul and Kleiner, 2003; Burke and Mikkelsen, 2005; Sparrow, 2003). Numerous studies have revealed the stressors and conditions that are sources of stress at work, and the problems that are physically and mentally associated with this phenomenon include low outcomes, low morale,

and a high rate of absenteeism (Ching, Seok and Ismail, 2021; Jackson and Frame, 2018; Abbas and Raja, 2019; Pandey, 2019; Ma et al., 2020; Kinjerski and Skrypnek, 2004). Strain is a fundamental reason for deliberately causing harm to the worker's outcomes in organizations (Lee, 2020). It is an individual's complex state when confronted with incentives, demands and resources to satisfy their needs where the result is uncertain (Judge et al., 2010). Job strain may occur because of different aspects: levels of motivation (Jain, Giga and Cooper, 2013), leadership type (Al-Hosam et al., 2016) and moral support (Wani, 2013). An elevated amount of strain can be noticed across every organization and at all levels of management, which primarily affects employee job outcomes (Giorgi et al., 2017; Crouse et al., 2021; Bouckenooghe et al., 2021). According to Rose (2003), workers experience a great deal of strain when working extra hours, which decreases employees' desire to perform higher. Studies have discovered a link between job stressors and the outcomes of an organization's employees. It can further affect employees psychologically. The person's outcomes may be emotional, physiological, or a combination (Houle and Nash, 2008; Khoozani and Hadzic, 2010; Harmsen et al., 2019). Additionally, evidence relating job strain and employee outcomes concluded that the average strain improves employee outcomes at various managerial and organizational levels (AbuAlRub, 2004; Frank, Lambert and Qureshi, 2017; O'Connor, Thayer and Vedhara, 2021). In the existing literature, there is a significant relationship between employee job strain, such as work overload and overworking (Jamal, 1984), exhaustive work intensity, managerial functions and low morale (Beehr et al., 2000). For example, a study of blue-collar and middle management in Canadian firms reported a negative relationship between job strain and employee outcomes. Furthermore, the study found that employees under much strain are less dedicated, feel less protected, are frustrated, and perform poorly (Jamal, 1984). Other studies have discovered a negative relationship between job strain factors and employee job outcomes (Bokti and Talib, 2009).

According to these research findings, when organizational strain exceeds a certain level, it reduces employee outcomes. It can be established that strain is a continuous source of concern for employees, affecting their outcomes at work and leading to job disenchantment. By creating a positive organizational environment and reducing workplace stressors, the job outcomes of employees can be improved (Ahmadi and Alireza, 2007). It was determined through studies

conducted by Ahsan et al. (2009) and Yahaya et al. (2010) that the strain factors of high workloads, performance expectations, and job satisfaction are inversely related.

Research performed among 134 staff working in Pakistan found a negative relationship between job stressors such as work overload and employee outcomes (Al Halbusi et al., 2020). Studies have found that job stress is strongly associated with a variety of negative job outcomes (Arshadi and Damiri, 2013; Mosadeghrad, Ferlie and Rosenberg, 2011; Glazer and Beehr, 2005; Liu, Spector and Shi, 2008). The major effects recognized by studies include anxiety as a reason for job dissatisfaction (Fox and Spector, 2006), reduced employee affiliation (Ziauddin et al., 2010) and inadequate work execution (Rehman and Mubashar, 2017). Several aspects of the work environment are antecedents of job stress, including injustice, weak interpersonal skills, minimal contribution to a decision, absence of opportunities, and lack of organization in job contents (Murphy, 2003; Greenberg, 2004). Table [2.5] summarises the antecedents of job strain in literature.

Table 2. 4: Antecedents of Job strain:

Factors	Authors
Excessive work	Caplan and Jones, (1975)
Job Uncertainty	Kahn et al., (1964)
Role Inconsistency	Gilmore, Beehr and Richter, (1979)
Job protection	Pincherle, (1972)
Work Involvement	Kasl, (1973) ; Margolis and Quinn, (1974)

Lack of Advice about Job results	Cassel, (1974)
Technical transformation	Ginzburg, (1967)
Innovativeness	(Kahn et al., 1964)
Career Advancement	Erikson and Gunderson (1972)
Life trials	Adams (1980)

2.2.2 Scenario in Islamic Banking Sector

The Islamic banking sector in Pakistan has been one of the fastest growing segments, with new growth and efficient and unique products being launched frequently. With heightened competition, it is becoming more difficult for employers in the banking sector to provide their employees with a satisfying work environment. As a result, employees appear to be overloaded and dissatisfied with the workplace in which they are positioned. Furthermore, due to the rigours of the job and the rigidity of hours worked, the number of stressed-out employees in the Islamic banking industry is increasing significantly. This high-strain level leads to low self-esteem and less commitment among employees, destabilizing their outcome statistics and reducing employee job satisfaction.

The impact of strain on employee performance has been examined in a number of studies (Clarke, 1990; Cetinguc and Calisir, 2017; Stamper and Johlke, 2003; Bayraktar et al., 2017), but there is still a recognizable gap in developing countries such as Pakistan. Employers or managers in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector are unaware that their organizational practices, particularly those dealing with strain management, have a negative impact on their workers (Ahmed and Ramzan, 2013). Increased strain at the workplace with no management interest in a way to solve results in the loss of qualified workers, a shaky organizational public image, and decreased work efficiency (Vakola and Nikolaou, 2005). Such circumstances necessitate using a

timely and effective strain management strategy to boost employee quality of work life (Imtiaz and Ahmad, 2009). Research indicates that job strain is evident in various business sectors of Pakistan.

According to Shahid et al. (2011), the elements of strain are significantly negatively associated, specifically extreme high job demands, fewer organizational considerations, job consistency, and job outcomes among Pakistani bank employees. A further study conducted in the banking sector in Bahawalpur, Pakistan, revealed that, among other factors, job strain negatively impacts employee job motivation. Researchers found that job strain is related to employee satisfaction (Saleem et al., 2019). Moreover, a study conducted in the Azad Kashmir Health Sector found that job strain negatively affected employee productivity. When stress factors have a significant influence, it has a negative effect on employee outcomes (Naqvi et al., 2013). In a study, the occupational strain has been demonstrated to negatively influence employees' job results, resulting in a decrease in workers' participation in their overall tasks, leading to a greater degree of work disappointment (Gilboa et al., 2008).

2.2.3 Job Strain in Different Contexts

Across a range of professions, the unfavourable effect of strain on wellbeing has been accepted widely (Asif et al., 2020; Keech et al., 2020). Evidence can be found in various fields of psychoanalysis related to individuals in organizations (Grebner, Semmer and Elfering, 2005), nurses (Vallone, Smith and Zurlo, 2020), and dentists (Molina-Hernández et al., 2021) and general working population (Nanda et al., 2020). Research also mentions the adverse effects of job strain on university students (Platania et al., 2020), managers (Malini, 2021) and teachers (Wu, 2020). In addition to adversely affecting physical or emotional wellbeing, job strain negatively affects the overall wellbeing of individuals (Taouk, 2021). Strain may also lead to harmful effects on the individual, such as reduced self-confidence and diminished fulfilment in life (Fadli et al., 2020). In literature, a broad exposure has been given to job strain and collective outcomes (Wang and Seifert, 2021; Sørensen et al., 2020; Finney et al., 2013; Setar, Buitendach and Kanengoni, 2015). Stress-related disorders are predicted to be the second highest prominent cause of disease and disabilities, according to The World Health Organization (Kalia, 2002). European Working

conditions proved strain as the second imperative factor which gave rise to employees' health problems at work.

Employees' working experience in organizations has also related to job strain. Studies revealed that there is a strong association between the number of years spent working with an organization and job strain. Those employees with a long experience working with an organization experience more job strain when compared to the employees who are less experience with the organization (Ratnawat and Jha, 2014; Badawy and Schieman, 2021). On the other hand, some researchers have revealed opposite results. They found that the employees their organization has employed for more than ten years were less stressed at work compared to those who have been working with their organization for less than ten years (Pace et al., 2019). This scenario might be because employees work for a longer time in organizations, become well-adjusted to the work routines, and better cope with the pressures of the work (Hong et al., 2002). Other than outside factors such as professional and managerial in strongly predicting the level of job strain, individual personalities also play an important role (Swider and Zimmerman, 2010). They focused on the Five-Factor Model personality traits such as honesty, sensitivity, agreeableness, extraversion, and dependability, recognized to be powerful predictors of job strain. According to the results, people with less conscientiousness, lower openness, and high neuroticism have more tendencies to show negative attitudes in the workplace. Non-participatory style of management in decision-making, which represents a lack of family-friendly policies and inadequate communication, is another important factor (Yoho, 2021). Furthermore, when contributing to the same investigation, it is asserted that the level of stress is depended upon the style of management (Yetunde, Igbinoba and Adejumo, 2021), organizational policies, poor communication, and lack of participation in decision-making (Palmer, Cooper and Thomas, 2003).

Job strain has a connection with individual demographics as well. Literature suggests that demographic variables are associated with job stress, including gender, age, job experience, and education (Lau, Yuen and Chan, 2005). Female employees experience more strain than their male counterparts (Bouckenooghe et al., 2005). Age may also affect the strain experience. It is reported that more aged employees experience more strain at work than less aged employees. Circumstances may vary from situation to situation, but all these variables provide ground for an investigation of the job strain from various dimensions. More strain is reported in experiences of

female employees facing strain at work compared to male employees (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2006). They also reported that female employees experienced and responded more to the stressor than male employees. So, in this way, gender may influence the working strain experience in organizations. Experienced employees respond better to stressors because they have a good position in the organization than their colleagues. As employees' work experience and expectations rise, they are expected to experience job strain (LaMontagne et al., 2010). Education can also have an association with the experience of job strain, and it can affect how an individual experiences job strain in the organization (Masoom, 2021). It is recognized that the more educated employees tend to express reactions to stress full environment and stressors in psychological terms. They are more likely to show feelings of self-doubt, anxiety and mental breakdown (Cope, 2003). Approximately 45 percent of the employees surveyed in a study on stress in the United States reported that their workload was overwhelming.

An analysis of upper middle-level managers has revealed that work overload is the most commonly perceived cause of stress in the workplace (Knezevic et al., 2011). Pressure is forced on the entire organization as workers experience job strain, and it usually carries social, emotional, and physical costs such as a higher likelihood of employee health problems and they may have a greater disdain for their jobs and feel less motivated to stay with the company (Jannoo, Yap and Haron, 2015).

In 2017, the American Psychological Association, Center for Organizational Excellence recorded that 37 per cent of working Americans surveyed "typically feel anxious or stressed out" during their working day (p. 22), while a study by Statista (2017) found that 70 per cent of workers surveyed with management roles frequently encountered strain at work. A survey conducted by Mental Health America (2017) found that 81 per cent of surveyed U.S. workers believed that strain at work negatively influenced their relationships with friends and family, with 63 per cent reporting that strain from their careers caused them to engage in unhealthy behaviours on a regular basis. Job strain, environmental or otherwise causes, or factors, are considered job strainers. Instead of having these strong results, explaining the relationships is still difficult, with very little or no presumptions (Burnett, Sheard, and Thompson, 2020). Salient features of the work-related environment are pointed out by Kirkcaldy and Martin (2000) to identify stressors for employees dealing with loads of work on a daily bases in their organizations.

Halkos and Bousinakis (2010) investigated the impacts of strain on an organization. The study results found that increased strain leads to lower productivity, and enhanced satisfaction leads to higher productivity. Zarei, Razavi and Emamgholizadeh, (2014). The study showed a strong and important link between strain management and efficiency in the workplace. Naqvi et al. (2013) examined the effect of job strain and showed that lack of financial and monetary rewards, work hour inflexibility, emotional problems, low work environment control and bureaucratic management system are negatively correlated with the productivity of employees. Donald et al., 2005 investigated the effects of strain on work productivity by using a shortened strain assessment tool which involves individual job strainers, strain outcomes (physical and psychological wellbeing) and commitment. The study revealed a marginal association between job strain and work productivity. Hoboubi et al. (2017) study showed related results.

Strain and job pressure can negatively affect employee productivity and have a significant impact on the overall performance of an organization. This can adversely affect the organization's ability to accomplish its planned goals and achieve a competitive advantage (Garton and Mankins, 2015). The factors causing strain are the need to do more and the complexity of work and responsibility (Farooq and Farooq, 2019). The issues surrounding hindering stressors are position uncertainty, organizational structure, and job insecurity (Sonnetag and Fritz, 2015). Bowling and Eschleman (2010) showed that job strainers were more closely related to counterproductive work behaviours. In 2007, M Jamal conducted a study that supported the negative linear relationship between job strain and employee outcomes. In the research conducted by Jamal (1984), the negative linear relationship between strain and output results was generally more favourable than positive linear or curvilinear relationships. Bashir and Ismail Ramay's (2010) study indicated job strain significantly reduces an employee's outcomes. Liu et al. (2013) observed that employees who confirmed stressors of challenge had more job outcomes and were more dedicated than employees who reported stressors of the obstacles.

2.2.4 Job strain and leadership

Leaders' actions, also known as their leadership style, did contribute to subordinate strain (Shkoler and Tziner, 2020). Organizations especially considered the improved associations

between supervisors and subordinates less important to lower strain levels, whereas, in the lead role, their behaviour or leadership style could reduce strain on employees. Leaders play an important role in fostering a positive working environment where subordinates can work to their full potential (Lee, Idris and Tuckey, 2019).

Leadership style, actions and attitudes that have the potential to inhibit or dominate style could end up putting subordinates under strain. Managers' subjective perception of ethical leadership is inversely correlated with subordinates' perception of job strain (Zhou, Jin and Ma, 2015). Harms et al. (2017) observed meta-analytic reports from countries worldwide and presented 25 observations from different countries. The outcome confirms two research findings: Leadership is inversely associated with both employee strain and employee exhaustion in general. Coercive management found that positive relationships with subordinate strain levels were registered higher. According to Lornudd et al. (2016), Leaders experienced significantly more occupational strain and strain than the others. In Ghana, Saleem et al. (2019) found the inverse connection between strain transformation leadership and the positive relationship between strain and transaction leadership. Parvaiz et al. (2015) revealed the direct relationship between the factors like the leader's encouragement and the employees' strain level.

In a complex business climate, organizations worldwide face tough competition. They need to improvise and reinvent in order to survive. Companies need to compete with their most powerful resources, which are human capital. Increasing demand for work will lead to strain and dissatisfied workers, eventually hampering their outcomes (Mc Loughlin and Priyadarshini, 2021). Companies need to focus on their leadership to keep up with the rising demands for jobs. The purpose of leadership is to influence employee behaviour at work. Business requires leaders and managers that care, empathize, and continue to support their subordinates. With this strategy, workers can be encouraged to work harder to achieve the company's goals. So it is vital to appreciate the link between leadership and occupational stress (Liu et al., 2021). Globalization has made it imperative for companies to enhance their competitiveness. This context has increased pressure on workers for better outcomes, raising their strain levels. Ethical leadership is expected to increase employee morale and trust (Wang et al., 2020). Therefore, to manage tension and improve job satisfaction, leaders and workers get involved in positive and productive experiences together (Freire and Bettencourt, 2020).

The ethical leadership style encourages positive interaction with subordinates through inspiration, support, and emphasis on the positive impact of achieving organizational goals on individual achievement. Increased morale (Graves, Sarkis and Zhu, 2013), corporate citizenship behaviour (Kim, 2012) and decreased employee turnover (Demirtas and Akdogan, 2015) are among the positive effects of ethical leadership. Ethical leadership will also change the organizational perception of the employee and encourage them to do more tasks than is normally expected of them (Mujkić et al., 2014). Past studies have investigated the connection between good leadership and strain at work and reported varying results. However, most studies have reported a negative correlation to date. Many scientific publications endorse the negative relationship to decreasing employee strain levels when good leadership is incorporated (Syrek, Apostel and Antoni, 2013; Yao et al., 2014; Baysak and Yener, 2015; George, Chiba and Scheepers, 2017).

On the one hand, ethical leadership practices are expected to prove effective for individuals in organizations. On the other hand, the employees are experiencing high strain in the workplace (Gamarra and Giroto, 2021; Okpozo et al., 2017; Morkevičiūtė and Endriulaitienė, 2016). This situation may prevail because of a lack of association and feeling a connection for company employees (Dewa et al., 2007). Recent research has revealed that employees desire to be identified, valued and embraced enriching fulfilment at work, which is referred to as compassion activities of the organization facilitated at the workplace (Zulfiana et al., 2021; Lund Dean and Safranski, 2008). Work is considered a source of individual wellbeing (Judge et al., 2010). It has a sound contribution to mental and physical health. As employees spend considerable time at work, the workplace must provide meaningful, supportive strength and a sense of association (Ellis et al., 2021; Mulaney et al., 2021).

2.3 Employee Outcomes

2.3.1 Perspectives and Definitions

Escalating organizational objectives due to the fast-changing economy, intense competition, and globalization compels high management to acknowledge employee outcomes on a large scale (Cera and Kusaku, 2020). Over the past decade or so, numerous studies have demonstrated the enormous success obtained by organizations through the effective management of performance-oriented employees (Evans and Davis, 2005). Additionally, much of the research validates earlier writing on the significant contribution of employee outcomes to organizational achievement (Delery and Doty, 1996; Wright, Dunford and Snell, 2001).

Employee outcomes are one of the crucial factors of organizational long-term and short-term success. It is empirically tested and proven that most of the organization's success depends on its employee's outcomes; however, it is also true that the outcomes of a few employees cannot change the organization's destiny (Asbari, Hidayat and Purwanto, 2021). It is, in fact, a combined effort from all levels and contributions of all employees at large. Employee outcomes are vital to attaining organizational objectives backed by planned strategies to motivate and boost employees' behaviour towards it (Puspitasari and Darwin, 2021). Employee outcomes have been defined from various perspectives in different contexts, and every aspect differs. One of the precise descriptions of employee outcomes is that employee outcomes are the system of behaviours to achieve the objectives of the organization, in which multiple tasks are assigned to employees, and they have to fulfil these tasks to ultimately contribute to overall organizational objectives (Ferris et al., 2010). On the other hand, another description of employee outcomes is that it is not the behaviour but particularly the outcome of behaviour (Aguinis, 2009). According to Shinagare et al. (2014), employee outcomes can be described as the economic or non-financial outcome of the employee that has a solid connection to the organization's outcomes and accomplishments.

Employee outcomes are also defined in a way that is highly related to the actions and activities of employees and what they do. It is not always about the outcome of their work (Holley, Wu and Avey, 2019). Another perspective of employee outcome is the rate of accomplishment employees have while performing on the job. To add to this viewpoint, employee outcomes are defined as the result of an employee's work-related activities throughout a given time. (Shahzad et

al., 2011). While explaining employee outcomes, Borman et al. (1993) distinguish them into two aspects. One aspect is task outcomes related to employees' skills that they must accomplish formally, which is the central kernel of every organization. Task outcomes include behaviours directly engaged in providing support to perform the job (Pahos et al., 2021). The other aspect is contextual outcomes that include all the activities of the individual that are not directly related to duties but provide support in fulfilling the job (Ramli, 2019). It includes the social and psychological context.

Motowidlo (2003) defined employee outcomes as a value that an organization expects from an employee by performing discrete behaviours at a particular time. This definition has different assumptions, with the idea that job outcomes are behavioural, episodic, evaluative, and multi-dimensional. Behaviour and outcomes are different in meaning; therefore, amplification is necessary for these two terms. Outcomes are what employees do, and it is estimated by an organization about the people's behaviour (Buil, Martínez and Matute, 2019). Employee outcomes represent a general exhibition of employee behaviours that promote the success and accomplishment of organizational objectives (Farzaneh and Boyer, 2019; Riyadi, 2019). Generally, from three perspectives, employee outcomes can be presented: individual knowledge, knowledge of the process, and motivation. Based on these perspectives, employees may perform better than others (Cooper et al., 2019). The dependence of employee outcomes on how workers distinguish their jobs has long been acknowledged by researchers (Shuck et al., 2019; Audenaert et al., 2019). Researchers argued that by developing awareness of job implications — a perception that one's job has a constructive influence on other people- the employee's outcomes could be increased (Morgeson and Humphrey, 2006). For managing individual outcomes, organizations have focused on evaluating outcomes, and the rewards allocated to effective outcomes are the consequence of the dealings between a person's capability and inspiration (Atmojo, 2015). Organizations' measures are representative of employee outcomes, which are considered an outcome of organizational processes and have often been considered potential predictors of organizational outcomes (Buil, Martínez and Matute, 2019). Research on organizational issues has focused on employee outcomes (Fahmi, Musnadi and Nadirsyah, 2019; Aziz and Moyer, 2018).

Managing dedicated and motivated employees for the last two decades has been a great challenge for organizations to foster employee outcomes (Bryson and White, 2019). Managing

employee outcomes is arduous because people respond in different ways and outcomes sometimes become voluntary choices exhibited by employees (Rounok and Parvin, 2011). Leadership cultivates motivation in employees, who then direct their efforts toward the desired goals. Management must pursue the variables that motivate individuals to a greater level of performance (Kauppila, 2018).

If employees are neglected by management, this results in a lack of interest in the job, which may cause suffering, strikes, absenteeism, or sickness (Bandura and Walters, 1977). Satisfied employees will generate more outstanding commitment, acceptance and understanding to implement the organization's objectives and prove vital to organizational outcomes (Byron et al., 2018).

Employee outcomes are usually considered in terms of goal achievement, job design, and task setting, yet empirical research in this area is uncertain about the constituents of this variable. Employee outcomes, by and large, maintain their position of prime importance in the organizations and two main reasons can contribute to it. Firstly, the overall growth margins in productivity have fallen worldwide. Productivity is the main factor responsible for improving wages, living standards, and quality consumption of products (Goodwin, Groth and Frenkel, 2011). So, generally, employee outcomes are crucial to social improvement at large (Walumbwa et al., 2011). Secondly, for management in organizations, improvement in employee outcomes is a matter of consideration as it is associated with the outcomes of the overall organization. Management is all the time interested in developing strategies to improve the outcomes of employees in the organization (Paracha et al., 2012).

Previous studies show a positive relationship between employee commitment and outcomes concerning a satisfied employee performing more than an unsatisfied employee in the organization (Ostroff, 1992). Researchers have studied employees' outcomes with different variables to investigate the relationships and impact of various factors associated with employee outcomes. Karatepe and Kilic (2009) show that workplace incivility and work-family facilitation impact employee outcomes, and work-family facilitation improves job outcomes. According to Biswas (2009), an efficient organizational structure helps the workforce grow faster by transferring

social norms from the workplace to an individual's way of life there. It also continues to support leadership style, which has a remarkable impact on raising employee outcomes.

2.3.2 Employee outcomes and Ethical leadership

Management practices contribute immensely to enhancing the efficiency and usefulness of the behaviours of employees and also in strengthening a strong positive association (Carlson, Upton and Seaman, 2006); Ogbonnaya and Messersmith, 2019). Tessema, Soeters and Abraham's (2005) research shows the strong relationship between management actions and organizational employee outcomes. This connection draws considerable attention from researchers and top management in the organization (Vigoda-Gadot and Dryzin-Amit, 2006). Zhu, Avolio and Walumbwa (2009) insisted that leadership may affect the employee's behaviour and ultimately can promote the efficiency of the organization. Brown and Trevino's (2005) research is an excellent contribution in this regard which concluded that a leader's ethical behaviour has a meaningful influence on his followers that affect his outcomes. Nearly all recent studies have reached the same conclusion: individual behaviours that effectively support organizational goals are seen as employee outcomes (Palm, Seubert and Glaser, 2019; Ogbonna and Harris, 2000).

In support, previous investigations have focused mainly on ethical leadership and negative behaviours (e.g. Avey, Nimnicht and Pigeon, 2010; Sharkie, 2009). Few researchers only in the west have investigated the reasons and mechanisms why and how ethical leadership is associated with employee outcomes (Hosmer, 1994). A notable exception in this regard is the research by Piccolo et al. (2010) that investigated the importance of autonomy and task significance in the connection between E.L. and employee outcomes. The study concluded that ethical leadership increased task significance, ultimately affecting employee outcomes. Researchers associate the leadership style as a significant factor in enhancing employee fulfilment and employee acts that can be associated with the employee's outcomes (Howell and Hall-Merenda, 1999). Leadership and outcomes link has always been the researcher's interest, and suggestions have been made that there are chances that ethical leadership significantly affects employee outcomes (Grant, Gino and Hofmann, 2011). Employee outcomes are enhanced under extraverted leadership when employees are neutral (Obicci, 2015). Literature shows E.L. is related to employees' fulfilment and convinces

employees are more likely to perform well and less likely to leave the company (Jones, Latreille and Sloane, 2004; Asbari, Hidayat and Purwanto, 2021). Since the last decade, researchers have advocated that organizations launch leadership strategies to boost employee productivity and outcomes. (Ozaralli, 2002; Biswas, 2009).

Ethical leadership is related to the readiness of employees to communicate problems (Brown, Treviño and Harrison, 2005), motivation (Piccolo et al., 2010) and effective response to the job (Ruiz, Ruiz and Martínez, 2011). Piccolo et al. (2010) suggested that an ethical leader can influence the employee's willingness toward task achievement and outcomes. The Ethical leader has the authority to make decisions directly related to employee aptitudes to fulfil their objectives (Burke et al., 2007; Ofori and Toor, 2009; Resick et al., 2011). Researchers have focused on two factors in investigating the influences of ethical leaders on employee outcomes. These factors are trust and employee commitment (Berrone, Surroca and Tribó, 2007). Ethical leaders develop and promote the relationship of trust among followers, as a result of which followers keep their promises and behave consistently, resulting in their outcomes (Yang and Mossholder, 2010). Ethical leaders influence the employee's behaviour because the employees trust their leader and believe that the ethical leader has positive intentions towards them. An ethical leader informs employees about their expectations and guides them in how they can directly contribute to the organization's objectives. Alternatively, an ethical leader's treatment of employees strengthens their confidence (Kalshoven, Den Hartog and De Hoogh, 2011). Brown, Treviño and Harrison (2005) conducted research with 87 MBA students and concluded that ethical leadership is directly linked with employee trust. By developing an emotional relationship of trust with employees, ethical leaders develop a foundation of commitment to achieve shared goals with employees (Collins, 2010). By building a relationship of trust between leader and employee, both parties grow a faith that no one shall act opportunistically (Judge, Piccolo and Kosalka, 2009).

Theorists have categorized trust into three types. The first type is deterrence-based trust. This trust is because of fear of punishment if trust is violated (Jones and George, 1998). In this situation, individuals act according to directions given to him/her because they fear consequences. The second is knowledge-based trust. That trust comes from past knowledge and history, and individuals predict other person's actions in a particular situation based on their knowledge. The third is identification-based trust. This type is based on mutual understanding between both parties

about their goals and objectives (Zhao et al., 2020; Avolio et al., 2004). Trust is a significant issue in organizations regarding employee outcomes, and if it is broken may affect the employment outcomes and lead to adverse consequences (Madjar and Ortiz-Walters, 2009). Trust is the medium through which employees comply with organizational values, rules and culture and contribute to achieving organizational goals through their outcomes and participation (Ponnu and Tennakoon, 2009). Employee outcomes connection with the ethical leader is substantially based on trust, and studies support that the level of trust is enhanced when employees perceive the organization as ethical and influence their outcomes as well (Fulmer, 2004).

Employee commitment is the second factor that has been the centre of attention for researchers in exploring the relationship between employment outcomes and ethical leadership. It is defined as an individual's loyalty to the leader or organization. In this state, the employee feels that he/she belongs to a leader or organization and finds satisfaction from working for that leader or organization.

Researchers have also investigated commitment to suggest worker behaviour in outcomes and achievement (Neubert et al., 2009). Theoretically, commitment can be seen from three aspects (Meyer and Allen, 1991). The first type is an emotional affiliation which is an affecting commitment to the person or company. The second type is continuance commitment, which is related to the perception of an individual's economic benefit while connected with the organization or person and the comparison he/she made between connection and disconnection based on economic benefit. Moreover, the third type is a normative commitment, defined as staying in an organization or with a person for a moral or ethical reason. Relationships between ethical leaders and employees energize employees' commitment level, which influences employee outcomes in result (Ponnu and Tennakoon, 2009; Upadhyay and Singh, 2010).

Similarly, investigations reveal a direct link between the ethical leader and employee willingness toward required outcomes through solid employee commitment to the organization (Mize, Stanforth and Johnson, 2000; May and Avolio, 2004). On one side, several studies support the connection between employee outcomes and ethical leadership. On the other side, some studies conclude this connection's inconsistency (Detert and Burris, 2007; Kia, Halvorsen and Bartram, 2019; Sugianingrat, 2017; Mayer et al., 2012).

Research also declares that ethical leadership's effect on employee outcomes depends on context, which may change if the context changes (Martin et al., 2021; Yukl and Mahsud, 2010)). Therefore, it is imperative to test the influences of E.L. on employee outcomes in different contexts and situations (Avey, Palanski and Walumbwa, 2011). According to Bello (2012), employee outcomes can be improved if directed by ethical leaders. Detert and Burris (2007) conducted research and revealed that efficient leadership significantly influence discovering and polishing employee contribution in terms of their outcomes to organizational achievements. Luthans (2000) further added that effective leadership means that employee outcomes are vital in attaining organizational objectives. Researchers suggest a favourable connection between E.L. and EOC. However, empirical studies in this area are scanty (Zaim, Demir and Budur, 2021).

2.4 Organisational Compassion

This section provides an overview of the intellectual history of creating a working concept of organisational compassion. This part adds to the investigation by providing an overview of the literature on organisational compassion and then developing a connection to the phenomena related to this study. It also presented organisational compassion as an enveloping aspect of the organisation. Firstly, the conceptualisation of compassion was introduced, its impact and facilitating conditions in the organisation's workplace, and then the efforts that could be contributed to institutionalising compassion were addressed.

2.4.1 Introduction

Since the dawn of civilisation, the definition of compassion has been a subject of discussion across various disciplines, including medicine, religion, sociology, psychology, and philosophy (Frost et al., 2004). According to Mannion (2014: 115), compassion is a "complex, controversial, and value-laden concept entangled in conflicting meanings and elusive in its definition". According to Smith (2009: 19), compassion implies more than dignity or empathy. There remains a significant challenge in reaching a consensus about what compassion means (Schantz, 2007; Strauss et al., 2016). Compassion has been described as an individual characteristic (Goetz et al., 2010), an emotion (Vastfjall, 2014; Condon and Barrett, 2013; Rashedi et al., 2015; Palgi et al., 2015), and a behaviour (Sprecher and Fehr, 2005). Although compassion in the organisational literature is still in its infancy (Cameron, 2017; Eldor, 2017), it has been precisely conceived as an

interactive process (Lilius et al., 2012; Kanov et al., 2004, 2016). Kanov et al. (2004), in writing for organisational literature, first expressed compassion as a process between people in the organisation that consists of three sub-processes: 1) "noticing," 2) "feeling," and 3) "responding" to others' suffering. This conceptualisation differs from perceiving compassion as a characteristic or an expression (Lilius et al., 2012) and has been referred to as 'compassion at work in the literature (Lilius et al., 2008, Dutton et al., 2007; Chu, 2016; Moon et al., 2014; Rhee et al., 2017). In fact, 'compassion at work' relates to workplace attitudes and acts of kindness toward others (Eldor and Shoshani, 2016).

Kanov et al. (2004) added the concept of 'organisational compassion,' which occurs when people in the organisation exchange the sub-processes of noticing, feeling, and responding to the anxiety or distress of other members of that system. To be shared and thus collaborative, these subprocesses must be legitimised and spread with coordinated responses. This scenario is aided by various organisational factors, including norms, procedures, systems, and leadership (Kanov et al., 2016). As a result, the concept of 'organisational compassion' encompasses more than just compassion in an organisational context or 'compassion at work.' This understanding is like 'organisational virtuousness,' which has been revealed as a five-dimensional framework (optimism, trust, compassion, forgiveness, and integrity) demonstrated by collectives (Cameron et al., 2004; Dutton et al., 2014; Worline and Dutton, 2017).

The term "virtuousness in organisations" refers to the actions of the organisation's members, whereas "virtuousness through organisations" pertains to the attributes that facilitate virtuousness (Bright et al., 2006). As a result, Cameron et al. (2004) described "organisational virtuousness" as "persons' behaviour, collective activities, qualities, or methods that facilitate the spread and continuation of virtuousness in an organisation." Surprisingly, Cameron et al. (2004)'s operationalisation of 'organisational compassion,' which is a component of 'organisational virtuousness,' did not adhere to the same conceptualisation. Organisational compassion, as part of organisational virtuousness, has been classified as people caring about one another, and that kindness and concern are prevalent within the organisation (Rego et al., 2010; Cameron et al., 2004). This viewpoint ignores organisational factors and implementers and disagrees with Kanov et al. (2004 's; 816) claim that organisational compassion is not a "mere aggregation of compassion

among people." On the other side, Kanov et al. (2004) describe 'organisational compassion' as a collective process that is empowered by elements, which falls short of the understanding of the concept of 'organisational virtuousness,' which contains specific processes and aspects as constituent components and not merely as enablers.

This omission of considerations has also been acknowledged by Simpson et al. (2015), who argue that the current theorising of organisational compassion restricts it to individuals acting and further suggests that organisational compassion includes socio-material procedures. "The socio-material approach challenges the widely held belief that new technology, work, and organisations should be conceived independently and progress the vision that there is an implicit close interaction between the technical and the social (Orlikowski and Scott, 2008). According to Banker and Bhal (2018: 5), "because we are talking about organisational compassion, personal actions and organisational factors must go together to exhibit compassion." Even though authors acknowledge the significance of organisational factors in the existing conceptualisation of organisational compassion (Kanov et al., 2004; Dutton et al., 2014), their conceptualisation does not perceive organisational factors as enormously important (Simpson et al., 2015). Furthermore, while Kanov et al. (2004) affirm the existence of individual compassion at work, their proposed definition implies otherwise and appears to reflect Frost et al., 2004's concept of 'compassion organising,' which considers compassion as a shared activity. According to Stiehl et al. (2017), understanding the interactional process of care is obligatory before studying 'care' at an organisational level. In light of the preceding argument and the conceptualisation of 'organisational virtuousness,' 'organisational compassion' will be viewed holistically in this thesis to include both 1) individual and collective interpersonal processes and 2) organisational factors. In this study, the term compassion at work is being used to explain the interpersonal process between organisational members, whether individual or collective, whereas 'compassionate factors' are being used to describe aspects and enablers in the organisation that facilitate compassion, as shown in figure [2.2].

Figure 2. 2: Organisational Compassion constituents

Compassion at work

Over a decade, compassion at work being a source of development, its benefits and influence at organisational and individual levels have emerged as one of the most discussed areas among researchers and scholars (Halifax, 2011). Organisational compassion has taken its interest and place in a considerable number of practitioner seminars, publications, and events being held in research centres (Lilius et al., 2012; Keane, 2014; Rynes et al., 2012; Simpson, Clegg and Pitsis, 2014; Worline and Dutton, 2017). Recently, the foremost requirement is to identify the positive implications of compassion in the workplace and investigate the conditions these can generate (Dutton et al., 2014). At first, the impact of compassion was exposed by those employees who described the value and connection of their thoughts after getting compassionate organisational responses (Frost et al., 2000). It is comprehended by following Davis (1983) that compassion is a process having various dimensions in which the most significant activities are noticing the other's sufferings, responding in a manner that relieves the pain of the other and possessing feelings for the others (Dutton et al., 2014). For a better understanding of compassion, all of these essentials are compulsory.

Particularly, emotional or material social support results from a compassionate response and organisational citizenship behaviour (Smith, Organ and Near, 1983) or prosaically conduct (Borman, Motowidlo and Hanser, 1983). However, compassion is not restricted to only these actions they may also include a range of activities like listening, sharing, expressing and talking as well (Zellars et al., 2001; Dutton et al., 2002). Another distinctive trait is that compassion is preceded by suffering and is driven by felt compassionate apprehension (Frost and Dutton, 2002).

In conclusion, it can be conceived that compassion is one of the crucial types of care given to employees. It is argued that compassion is ever-present in several organisations since it responds to the unavoidable pain of human existence (Frost, 2003; Frost, 2006). Organisational compassion focuses and directs attention toward investigating compassionate activities in practice. In this perspective, organisations must examine their context, culture, practices that exhibit compassion, and how that context can be designed and shaped. The first and foremost action in this regard is that organisations have to boost people's capability and readiness to contribute to, observe, feel

and report the sufferings and dissatisfaction of people in the organisation (Kulkarni et al., 2013). The basic assumption of compassion is human first, so routine activities, burdens of work and production, and daily realities of life often obscure people at work (Kanov, Powley and Walshe, 2017).

There can be many potential barriers to organisational compassion. This also has to be understood by the management and generate the circumstances that foster organisational compassion. Researchers suggest that broadly speaking, there are two ways that organisational compassion can be facilitated in institutions (1) by creating situations that foster organisational compassion in the workplace and (2) by explicit attempts to practice regular activities related to organisational compassion through the institutionalisation of compassion procedures. Compassion is not only regarded as independent thoughts and feelings at the organisational level; it is a group strategy implemented in a socio-political frame of reference inspired by interpersonal networks, social traditions, frameworks, procedures, job functions, and management behaviours (Simpson and Berti, 2020). Here organisational compassion has been discussed in the context of an individual act and collective perspectives.

Compassion has been recognised in the organisational context as an interactive process distinct from perceiving compassion as an attribute or a sentiment (Lilius et al., 2012). Raman and McClelland (2019) define it as more concentrated and concise and could be viewed as a significant portion of the wider perspective of compassion proclaimed in literary works. Compassion at work can form the basis of moral support like kindness and assistance, flexible schedules like covering up for co-workers and giving things of value like cash and flowers (Lilius et al., 2008). It can also be an interactional act instead of a collective and organised act (Lilius et al., 2012; Poorkavoos, 2017). Both aspects will be covered in this section.

Compassion as an Individual Process

Based on Clark's (1997) research on sympathy behaviour, Kanov et al. (2004) defined compassion as an interaction process including recognising, feeling, and responding to suffering among organisational members. This concept was tested in a study by Miller (2007) and Way and Tracy (2012). Noticing, Relating, and Reacting (Miller, 2007) and Realising, Connecting, and responding were developed as study findings (Way and Tracy, 2012).

Figure 2. 3: Response to strain. 'Compassion at work' by Dutton et al., (2014).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Dutton, J. E., Workman, K. M. and Hardin, A. E. (2014) 'Compassion at work', *Annu. Rev. Organ. Psychol. Organ. Behav.*, 1(1), pp. 277-304.

Dutton et al. (2014) later expanded Kanov's concept of compassion at work by including a fourth dimension of "sensemaking" figure [2.3]. According to Kanov et al. (2004), compassion at work occurs when strain is recognised and articulated. Similarly, Dutton et al. (2006, 2014) believe articulating strain is necessary to elicit compassion at work. Hence, compassion at work has indeed been generally associated with actual and projected strain (Kanov et al., 2004; Dutton et al., 2014). Miller examined Kanov et al. (2004)'s concept of compassion at work in 2007 by interviewing organisational employees to investigate the three-part procedure of noticing, feeling, and responding. According to the study, compassion at work entails recognising a need for assistance and sources of strain. A second study by Way and Tracy (2012), which tested the concept among hospice personnel and discovered that compassion at work might respond to unspoken pain, came up with similar results.

Consequently, Way and Tracy (2012) renamed the noticing subprocess to recognising. They further imply that noticing implies consciousness, consideration, and assessment, whereas recognising goes even further. Recognising entails "awareness and implementing meaning to others' verbal and nonverbal communicative gestures, the timing and circumstances of these cues, as well as cracks between or absences of communications" (Way and Tracy, 2012). It could be

argued that this is acceptable in an organisational setting where workers may be completely unresponsive or show no signs of distress. However, this may also be true in work settings, where expressing distress is complex and frequently covered up by constant delays and mistakes that prompt criticism rather than compassion (Worline and Dutton, 2017). In addition, modern businesses show that suffering from strain has no place in the workplace (Kanov et al., 2004). As a result, it has recently been determined that it is vital to understand work-related strain more compassionately by learning to be interested and discover concealed distress (Worline and Dutton, 2017).

The preceding discussion was about whether compassion at work entails perceiving outward signs of strain or recognising internal signs of suffering. All the concepts described so far share the premise that compassion at work is a reaction to current distress, whether apparent or concealed. However, The Dalai Lama (2001) emphasises compassion's purposeful role in preventing strain. According to Boyatzis, Smith and Beveridge (2013), the concept of compassion at work is frequently related to those other positive phrases in the academic literature, such as loving, collaborating, and assisting (Kanov et al., 2004; Goetz et al., 2010), that are not solely caused by suffering. Furthermore, data reveals that compassion at work has a trait of concern, warmth, tenderness, and sympathy (Campos et al., 2009; Goetz et al., 2010; Lilius et al., 2008). Another investigation which included emotional experiences found that compassion at work, despite sorrow and empathy, was able to accommodate the positive emotion category (Shaver et al., 1987). Boyatzis, Boyatzis and McKee (2005) offered a new concept of compassion at work based on Confucian philosophy that combines the determination to achieve and serve others whether or not their circumstance is based on suffering and sorrow.

Based on this, Boyatzis, Smith and Beveridge (2013) presented an enlarged definition of compassion at work as an interactive process that entails perceiving another individual in need, empathising with them, and trying to improve their welfare in reaction to that need. They claim that this conceptualisation can be utilised beyond the coaching environment, although it was suggested that coaching. Cosley et al. (2010) endorse this enlarged view by defining compassion at work as care for the wellbeing of others. According to Boyatzis et al. (2013), their broadened understanding of compassion at work focuses on boosting both hedonic and eudemonic welfare, which is concerned with self-satisfaction. They go on to say that in the traditional understanding

of compassion at work as a response to pain, the emphasis is solely on improving hedonic wellbeing, whereas, in the broadened theory, compassion at work can improve both hedonic and eudemonic health. However, the research literature on the strain suggests that this is not the case. The research of Avramchuk and Manning (2014) confirms the existence of compassion at work in both the absence and presence of distress. According to Simpson, Clegg and Freeder's (2013) research, compassion at work should be incorporated into organisational practices and procedures. It should be viewed as a continuous process best developed during times of stability rather than during moments of emergency. The current study has taken a comprehensive view of compassion at work and, as a result, added to the existing literature by examining compassion at work in the framework of normalcy in the empirical environment of Islamic banks of Pakistan.

Compassion as a collaborative process

Compassion has previously been studied on an individual or interpersonal level. However, data from the previous study showed that compassion in the workplace is more likely to be a collaborative effort, including numerous employees (Lilius et al., 2008). Next, the researcher examines compassion through the prism of the organisation, looking at it as a collaborative process (Frost et al., 2004). Compassion as a collaborative process arises when the earlier indicated compassion practices are pooled among a community of individuals. Collaborative compassion, in other words, would comprise collective Noticing, caring, and responding. These sub-processes would need to be legitimised and propagated to be exchanged (Frost et al., 2004; Kanov et al., 2004). Legitimacy ensures that inside an organisation, acceptable and desired behaviours prevail. Compassion organising is more likely to appear when it is accepted that perceiving, experiencing, and acting in response to suffering is legitimate (Frost et al., 2004). According to Frost et al. (2004), legitimisation and dissemination have a bi-directional link.

When feelings and information are transmitted, it not only legitimises pain but also increases the possibility that members of an organisation will share it. Coordination is the way of introducing related activities together in a manner that allows goals to be met. Coordination is essential for communal organisational compassion since it allows the transition of similar sub-processes of perceiving and experiencing into a collective reaction (Frost et al., 2004). Individuals

with a mutual understanding of strain in a social system initiate collective compassion by collaboratively recognising and acknowledging their suffering. Guidelines and a shared culture that increase members' awareness of strain, physical structures that enable users to contact one another, and technology and ensure efficient communication are all used by organisations exhibiting a potential for collective Noticing (Kanov et al., 2004). When people of an organisation are allowed to communicate their thoughts and emotions and share emotional narratives about professional and home life, collective feelings emerge. Practices, rituals, culture, and leadership training that actively encourage the proliferation and legitimisation of emotions foster these activities. When members of an organisation coordinate their responses to distress, this is known as collective reacting (Kanov et al., 2004). Coordination can be accomplished by a centralised procedure in which a single individual coordinates a response, or it can occur spontaneously when people band together to respond collectively (Dutton, 2003). Therefore, organisational variables are critical in spreading, legitimising, and coordinating effective collective reactions.

Cameron and Payne (2012) researched virtuous organisations and concluded that organisational compassion is positively associated with profitability, productivity and customer retention. Lilius et al. (2003) conducted empirical research measuring organisational compassion and revealed noticeable compassionate experience and its productive influences in the workplace. According to Atkins and Parker (2012), the giving and receiving process of organisational compassion is influenced by rational and political appraisals in an organisation. Researchers reveal considerable benefits of organisational compassion: connectivity, positive affectivity, better organisational citizenship behaviour and enhanced wellbeing (Reizer, 2019; Worline and Dutton, 2017; Simpson, 2015). Few researchers have assessed compassion influences from the context of organisational shared values and mission (Kanov et al., 2004; Dutton, Workman and Hardin, 2014).

2.4.2 Organisational Compassion Factors

Despite compassion being primarily an interpersonal phenomenon, organisations play a significant role by incorporating their structures, cultures, and practices into what their members notice and respond to (Sutcliffe, 2001; Dutton et al., 2006; Kanov et al., 2016; 2014; Worline and Dutton, 2017; Banker and Bhal, 2018). According to a study (Henshall et al., 2017), organisational

factors like leadership increase compassion for others. It has been noted that workplace 'factors', such as values and routines, facilitate collective compassion (Kanov et al., 2004). However, Lilius et al. (2012) argue that organisational factors influence how compassion manifests in individuals and coordinated communities. As they discuss, organisations can either indirectly foster compassion by cultivating 'conditions' that facilitate compassion; or by establishing processes that enable compassion. Conditions encompass relationship quality, culture, and leadership, whereas processes involve formal defined roles and programs that identify and respond to suffering, such as employee support programs.

According to the review of empirical and theoretical accounts of organisational compassion by Dutton et al. (2014), organisational compassion can be understood at three context levels: personal, relational, and organisational. An analysis of organisational compassion by the authors found six factors affecting it: shared values, shared beliefs, norms, practices, relationships, and the behaviours of leaders. According to Banker and Bhal's (2018) research, five factors enable compassion in business organisations: values, culture, leadership, policies and practices, and work structure. However, only 10 middle and senior managers participated in the study. A recent article by Worline and Dutton (2017) offered a framework for understanding organisational factors that contributed to compassion and called it 'social architecture' encompassing social networks, organisation cultures, roles, routines, leadership, and stories.

Worline and Dutton (2017) proposed a framework for understanding organisational elements that lead to organisational compassion, termed "social architecture," which included social networks, organisational cultures, roles, routines, leadership, and stories. Their framework is considered to grasp all elements mentioned in the previous frameworks, including those in Dutton et al. (2014)'s model, which was described as the most comprehensive based on an analysis of empirical and theoretical acts of compassion (Kanov et al., 2016). Worline and Dutton's framework also includes two additional elements, roles, and stories, while keeping the overall number of elements at six. This was accomplished by combining relevant elements such as values, norms, and beliefs into the culture, which reflects how culture has been characterised (Schein, 1991). The organisational factors presented by (Worline and Dutton, 2017) are discussed next.

Networks

Two aspects of these factors are social network ties and the quality of relationships among members. In terms of network ties, they are the clusters of people who are well acquainted with one another (Dutton et al., 2014; Worline and Dutton, 2017) and that provide a means of conveying information, advice, and feelings between the individuals (Worline and Dutton, 2017). It has been observed that the stronger the network is, the easier and faster it will be for information to flow (Dutton et al., 2014). According to Simpson et al. (2019), co-workers within a strong social network are more likely to recognise changes in a person's mood when distressed. Consequently, information about suffering would be shared more rapidly, and a coordinated response would be more likely to be effective (Worline and Dutton, 2017). Relationship quality is depicted by network members' cooperation, vitality, and respect. A higher-quality group will be more likely to have emotionally attached members, which facilitates the development of compassion (Lilius et al., 2011; Dutton et al., 2014). The existence of relationships of higher quality facilitates the expression of both distress and compassion (Lilius et al., 2011).

In a recent study, empirical evidence suggests that individuals are more likely to provide compassion to co-workers if their work relationships are of higher quality (Chu, 2017). Furthermore, individuals can rely on the respect and trust they have developed in their connections, leading to a greater likelihood that notifications about distress will be taken seriously (Dutton et al., 2014; Lilius et al., 2008). The organisation's size seems to affect the quality of networks, as reported by managers in a study who noted that the smaller the organisation, the more its members can interact with others, enabling compassion (Banker and Bhal, 2018). In a recent study, empirical evidence suggests that individuals are more likely to provide compassion to co-workers if their work relationships are of higher quality (Chu, 2017). Furthermore, individuals can rely on the respect and trust they have developed in their connections, leading to a greater likelihood that notifications about distress will be taken seriously (Worline and Dutton, 2017). It has been observed that the size of an organisation seems to affect the quality of its networks, as shown by managers in a study who reported that the smaller an organisation is, the more its employees can interact with each other, which in turn allows organisational compassion to flourish (Banker and Bhal, 2018).

Culture

In an organisation, culture is defined as the basic assumptions concerning human nature and the values adopted by the members (Worline and Dutton, 2017). Furthermore, the authors refer to the common assumption of human equality, which holds that the members of an organisation are part of one human family and that human beings, by nature, are good, capable, and worthy of compassion. It can therefore be said that organisational culture is a set of shared values, beliefs, and norms among the members of an organisation (Simpson et al., 2019). Members of organisations share values, beliefs, and norms, which refer to the expectations of acceptable behaviour within the organisation (Dutton et al., 2014).

Banker and Bhal (2018: 11) argue that compassion cannot be practised in isolation and must be rooted in a value system (individual or organisational). Organisational values are the principles, aspirations, and goals the organisation adopts. In the recruitment and performance management process, values such as moral standards play an important role (Banker and Bhal, 2018). However, values that promote humanity, such as empathy, dignity, respect, teamwork, and equity, are conducive to compassion (Worline and Dutton, 2017). Furthermore, they created an environment where people could respond to suffering and coordinate resources (Dutton et al., 2006). A vital component of organisational norms is the emotion norm, which specifies how to express feelings appropriately. Typically, they provide guidelines regarding how and what people should feel at work and how those feelings should be expressed. Kanov et al. (2004) found that when an organisation's culture values the expression of suffering, members are more likely to express compassion. Dutton et al. (2014) found that these rules influenced how members felt and expressed strain but also how members felt and expressed compassion at work.

An empirical study indicates that the shared belief in the legitimacy of displaying humanity has facilitated communication and improved the ability to respond to organisational compassion (Dutton et al., 2006). Accordingly, organisations with a culture of shared humanity can interpret distress more generously and legitimise compassionate organisational action (Worline and Dutton, 2017). Similarly, to perceptions of the quality of networks, perceptions of the organisational culture appear to depend on the organisation's size. The participant in the study commented that a smaller organisation is more likely to feel compassionate and have a warm and friendly culture,

while "when a larger organisation becomes larger, these things become diluted." (Banker and Bhal, 2018: 12).

Roles

Roles are defined as patterns of behaviour that are expected to accompany a particular position. Making roles and taking roles play an important role in fostering compassion in an organisation. The process of role-taking involves the description, formal design, and communication of roles to new employees. A role that embodies care and compassion can awaken organisational compassion if employees view compassion as their responsibility and an integral part of their work duties (Simpson et al., 2019). Additionally, managers trained in caring responsibility and concern for the wellbeing of their employees are better able to demonstrate compassion towards them. In contrast to role taking, role making involves creating and changing expectations based on social needs (Worline and Dutton, 2017), thus allowing for the creation of and innovation within existing roles (Simpson et al., 2019). Thus, in organisations where employees are empowered to innovate and where roles are flexible, they are more likely to recognise and act beyond their formally designated roles, giving rise to new paths of organisational compassion (Worline and Dutton, 2017; Simpson et al., 2019).

Routines

According to Feldman and Rafaeli (2002), routines are ways of accomplishing recurring tasks such as recruitment, decision-making, and planning that are thought to strengthen relationships between individuals and facilitate the development of collective capabilities. Worline and Dutton (2017) describe routines that are similar to those described by Dutton et al. (2014). A routine involves formal organisational practices such as hiring individuals with good interpersonal skills, providing financial assistance to employees, providing pastoral care to employees and providing orientation programs for new employees (Lilius et al., 2011). Moreover, it encompasses informal practices such as conflict resolution and celebrating important life events such as birthdays and marriages (Lilius et al., 2011). An organisational practice such as employee support has been found to enable organisational compassion in three ways: (1) facilitating the integration

of new employees into the organisation, (2) sustaining compassion by enhancing employee wellbeing, and (3) enhancing compassion resources by strengthening employee wellbeing (McClelland and Vogus, 2019).

In a second study, participants indicated that policies and practices such as leave policies and employee benefits foster a caring atmosphere at work that acts as a source of motivation, enhances self-worth, and inspires employees to reciprocate compassionate behaviour (Banker and Bhal, 2018). Both standard and flexible routines can enhance organisational compassion. A routine of communication among staff members, for example, enables staff members to recognise when individuals are experiencing difficulties (Lilius et al., 2011). Employees are empowered to express their feelings collectively when they participate in regular team meetings with an agenda encouraging them to discuss work and personal issues (Kanov et al., 2004). It is also important to note that standard practices that allow the use of communication channels and resources in response to suffering legitimise the patterns of compassion and promptly facilitate the response to suffering (Kanov et al., 2004). By improvising on this standard routine, organisations can tailor compassionate responses in response to strain (Worline and Dutton, 2017). According to research, these improvisations increased the speed, scope, and scope of the resources provided to suffering individuals and increased the legitimacy of the process (Dutton et al., 2006).

Leadership

Leadership plays a vital role in facilitating organisational compassion by facilitating an environment of empathy and norms surrounding compassion (Lilius et al., 2012). In a recent study, respondents indicated that when leaders show concern for the members of an organisation, a compassionate culture will be built, and ethical values will be reinforced. This type of leadership has been termed empathetic leadership (Banker and Bhal, 2018). As a result of leaders expressing their feelings and concern openly, distress and compassion are legitimated, and organisational compassion is flourished (Kanov et al., 2004). Based on symbolic leadership theory, Dutton et al. (2006) assert that leaders can influence others cognitively and emotionally. Using a symbolic act of pausing the speech, telling the incident, and providing a donation, the Dean of the University propagated attention to the suffering students, induced emotion, and legitimated compassionate

actions (Dutton et al., 2006). A leader's compassionate actions can inspire many others, propagating and legitimising collective responses (Worline and Dutton, 2017). Additionally, leaders can influence all the other compassionate factors and direct resources towards alleviating suffering by using their position and formal power (Dutton et al., 2014). It is also possible that leadership can inhibit compassion at work. It was suggested in a study that employees may refrain from helping if their leader is not empathetic, even if they are motivated to do so (Banker and Bhal, 2018).

Stories

Stories contribute to the spread of information regarding suffering, thus generating ideas and sources to manage it (Dutton et al., 2006). In the case of one-time suffering events, this may be beneficial. Nevertheless, it is most important that stories about an organisation contribute to the understanding of its members of three prominent issues: what kind of organisation one works in, what kind of people one works with, and what kind of person one can become while working there (Worline and Dutton, 2017). Stories are a powerful tool for capturing an organisation's shared beliefs and values. By sharing stories of compassion within an organisation, Frost et al. (2004) hope to contribute to a shared understanding of the organisation's values regarding recognition of suffering and employee wellbeing. The study by Dutton et al. (2006) showed that when people were exposed to stories of compassion at work, they understood that the whole organisation was more compassionate, saw their colleagues as more compassionate, and realised that it was possible to show compassion at work. By incorporating these symbolic patterns into the structure, members of an organisation are more likely to respond to suffering generously in the event of suffering (Dutton et al., 2006). Stories enhance the members' identities and the collective identity of their organisation and may help them redefine their understanding of their organisation in new ways (Frost et al., 2004).

2.4.3 Organisational compassion outcomes

Compassion manifests itself in organisational members as the conduct of replying to the mental and physical distress of co-workers, supervisors, and managers or to the pain caused by social interactions between workmates and between leaders and subordinates (Simpson, Farr-Wharton and Reddy, 2020). Suffering is typically described as distress that results in ontological resentment (Reich, 1989). Such anguish could also be triggered by disease or disability, the death of a loved one, or worksite emotional damage (de Vries and Schene, 2015). This responsiveness serves as the foundation of care and recovery for other participants of the organisation who are struggling (Wieck, Kunzmann and Scheibe, 2021; Jenkins, 2021).

Following the terrorist attacks on September 11, 2001, Dutton and his fellows have vigorously conducted studies on organisational compassion, encouraging feeling, constructive employment individuality, job designing, and other topics. Their compassion research has primarily depended on methodological techniques, specific case studies, and established compassion scales used in their investigation. In research on organisational compassion, Moon et al. (2014) discovered a direct association between CSR and compassion, and Hur, Moon and Rhee (2016) discovered a good association between organisational compassion and employee creativity. The number of qualitative research on organisational compassion has steadily increased since Lilius et al. (2008) conducted empirical research linking organisational compassion to positive feelings and affective engagement in the organisation.

The concept of organisational compassion refers not only to a high-quality link with others but also to the nurturing response to the pain and misery of others in terms of behavioural, sentimental, and attitude factors. It differs from other emotional responses in that it involves actions of response to distress (Frost, 2014; Dutton et al., 2002). Representatives of a corporation's compassion manifest itself as actions of replying to not just the physical and mental distress of staff, supervisors, and managers but also the distress originating from social interactions among members of the organisation (Jazaieri and Rock, 2021). Caring, reflection, and recognition are concepts that sound similar to compassion. Caring is transmitting other people's feelings to oneself; reflecting is transmitting one's feelings to another; and recognising is feeling one with the institution (Counter, 2021).

Organisational compassion is also an interactional procedure that includes good actions that assist in acknowledging the distress of others, feeling for their psychological anguish, and reducing their suffering (Grundy and Landers, 2018). Compassion, as a gesture of simply reacting to the pain and misery of others, is perceived as genuine behaviour by organisational members (Vincett, 2018). Members of the organisation who encounter compassion with others perceive truthfulness about their compassionate behaviour. Having a persona of compassion involves acknowledging and believing others' suffering and responding to it in a sincere and interpersonal manner (Petchsawang and Duchon, 2012). Moreover, people in the organisation who have developed positive emotions see activities of sharing and exchanging compassion as a celebration. According to the Affective Events theory by Weiss and Cropanzano (1996), encouraging feelings would increase organisational members' emotional attachment to executing their organisational roles.

Likewise, organisational compassion can also have salutary consequences in work organisations for employees. Compassionate actions in an organisation improve sensemaking among colleagues (Senreich, Straussner and Steen, 2020). Employees who experience compassion at the workplace are more committed and dedicated to the organisation. In addition, employees experiencing organisational compassion are more likely to perform appropriately and report positively at the workplace than others (Eldor, 2018). People in the organisation who see their subordinates and colleagues in a phase of distress may help them by coaching with compassion (Boyatzis, Smith and Blaize, 2006). It will allow employees to get through that painful state and perform better.

Modern research revealed that compassion in organisations through attention, love and kindness establishes resources that generate and lead to lifelong satisfaction, commitment and reduction of strain at a minimum level (Fredrickson et al., 2008). Organisational and individual outcomes are improved in the organisation to the extent that caregiving behaviours are shown among employees (Ahmet, 2008); not only does compassion exhibit positively influence, but it also helps to reload the resources they need for their colleagues (O'Donohoe and Turley, 2006). According to research on organisational compassion, employees who feel valued and connected to their organisation are more likely to support and demonstrate positive behaviour towards their subordinates (Shanock and Eisenberger, 2006).

Current research mentions the influencing impact of organisational compassion, while it has long been a supposition that acquaintance of organisational compassion is a very tiring attempt (O'Driscoll et al., 2018; Taylor et al., 2017; Neff et al., 2020; Tierney et al., 2016). Another research suggested that providing organisational compassion may produce satisfaction related to and derived from helping others (Stamm, 2002). Also, studies showed that those who indulge themselves in compassionate actions are more responsive to social support, which helps to reduce their physiological pressure (Cosley et al., 2010). Over the past decade, Frost has urged researchers and organisational scholars to reorganise their practices and theories to investigate and describe organisations' sufferings and present organisational compassion as an identified, valued and essential element against those sufferings.

This study demonstrates that it is correlated with substantial outcomes related to the employees and organisation. When organisations and employees receive compassionate actions, it has proved beneficial for both parties - the organisation and the employees (Aboul-Ela, 2017; Frost, 1999).

2.4.4 Organisational Compassion and Job Strain

Job strain is one of the inescapable factors in the organisation, and organisational compassion against this aspect is a fundamental remedy (Raman and McClelland, 2019). Job strain is a comprehensive term that includes a broad array of unlikeable and painful experiences that may include distress, emotional fatigue, trauma, psychological distress and feeling of high strain extrication (Kanov, 2021; Vander Weele, 2019) as a result of which certain considerable events can occur that may trigger serious consequences (Schulz, 2020). Apart from family and personal reasons, these unpleasant situations can occur due to rudeness and incivility of colleagues (Cortina et al., 2001), or work itself can be the reason for suffering (Jacobson, 2006; Frost and Harris, 2003). These sufferings create strain in the workplace. Strain at the workplace has no limitations (Allard-Poesi and Hollet-Haudebert, 2017; Hui and Aye, 2018). For organisations, it is not only a moral but a financial concern. For example, job strain has been anticipated to cost businesses billions of dollars per annum (Brough, Raper and Spedding, 2021). Organisations are neglecting the cure of these sufferings, resulting in an increase in these costs over time. These sensitively hurting

experiences have a meaningful impact on employees and organisations (Harvey, 2001). Clearly, this situation illustrates the importance and need for organisational compassion activities (Hall, Shucksmith, and Russell, 2013; Molinsky and Margolis, 2005).

One effective event for triggering a positive attitude towards work and reducing job strain is experiencing organisational compassion at work (Chu, 2016). Organisational compassion is a helping strategy for employees who experience strain at the workplace, generating positive feelings (Fredrickson, 2003). Employees also have recognised the need for felt connection, belongingness, and compassion for the attainment of efficiency at work in an effective manner because the bigger challenge is not only the financial stability but the compassioned life at the workplace (Maitlis and Ozcelik, 2004; Ko, Kim and Choi, 2021). As a result, employees consciously and unconsciously seek belongingness, compassion, relaxation and ways to fulfil work (Gull and Doh, 2004). Employees long to feel the association in the workplace (Gockel, 2004; Ashmos and Duchon, 2000), and demand for this has increased more than ever as the missing association has become alienated (Collins and Kakabadse, 2006). The need for organisational compassion has surged by the immense strain level at work (Trougakos et al., 2008). In this scenario, compassion shown by people in the organisation can establish a connection and relief and strengthen people's emotional attachment to become productive employees (Dutton et al., 2006).

Organisational compassion consists of a felt relation with others. It includes the notice of strain, and most importantly, it comprises actions that reduce that strain (Stellar et al., 2015). This conceptualisation differentiates organisational compassion from empathy (Davis, 1996) and organisational compassion as an attribute (Cosley et al., 2010). It also escalates the view of organisational compassion as emotion (Sprecher and Fehr, 2005). Studies indicate that organisational compassion may include negotiations (Galinsky and Moskowitz, 2000) and knowledge sharing (Parker and Axtell, 2001). A compassionate response is an integral part of organisational compassion that comprises actions that lessen, alleviate, or make the job strain bearable. Research also indicates that the organisation indulging in compassionate responses at the workplace can initiate it by facilitating, supporting emotionally and morally and grating time and flexibility (Sukhera and Poleksic, 2021; Richardson, 2004). This way, organisational compassion transmits helping behaviour and deliberate actions that help others (Dovidio and Penner, 2004).

It is theorised by Kanov et al. (2004) that organisational compassion contributes to the capability of the organisation to establish and generate relationship resources, educate critical relationship skills and escalate organisational values. Compassion in organisational life is more fully appreciated; however, it is very important to be considerate and shift the concern to identify it on an organisational level. The main consideration is to take it as a progression led by several organisations at large by all individuals in the organisation and at all levels. Indeed, several service organisations are more required to be compassionate to achieve the success they seek and enhance their capabilities in that concern. It is not proposed that organisational compassion is a straightforward accumulation of compassion along with individual people; rather, it is suggested that organisational compassion is a literal indication, belief, and reaction appropriately to pain.

To a certain extent, organisational compassion comprises procedures and activities in which feelings for others, responding to pain, sharing among organisational members and noticing are included (Benzo, Kirsch and Nelson, 2017). As a result, people in the organisation associate with a shared group and context, all of these procedures must be encouraged and organised in a coordinated approach (Moon et al., 2016). These procedures are followed by feeling, responding to pain, sharing, collectively noticing the problems, and influencing the whole organisation constructively (Nussbaum, 2001).

2.4.5 Organisational compassion measures

Compassion contains diversity in its nature, so it raises measurement issues for the researchers. There are different approaches to measuring organisational compassion. One approach considers qualitative data as evidence of taking measurements regarding sufferings, feelings, noticing and responding (Miller, 2007). Some approaches involve direct asking questions about the sufferings and experiences of the respondent in the workplace (Lilius et al., 2008). Studies have used several measurements using the trait-based view of compassion and emotional measures (Shiota, Keltner and John, 2006).

Similarly, compassion can be measured through observing and measuring personality traits. Compassion is a personality trait in this approach (Kanov et al., 2004). It is also possible to evaluate organisational compassion by determining whether its activities are conducive to

compassioned values such as sharing, listening, feeling, and responding (McLelland, 2010). Some researchers have taken the organisation's generosity level as a reflection of organisational compassion (Muller and Whiteman, 2010). Organisational effectiveness is another important way to measure organisational compassion, and compassionate responses vary along with expression of interest and efforts related to work-related help (Elices et al., 2017).

2.4.6 Previous Research on Organisational Compassion

Compassion is crucial to any organisation's emotional health (Cherkowski and Walker, 2013), but it is extremely important in educational institutions because the best learning occurs in healthy, loving, and mentally secure environments. As career-oriented organisations, academic institutions can provide a favourable environment for nurturing compassion toward the workforce (Eldor and Shoshani, 2016; Gibbs, 2017).

According to Gibbs (2017), the more universities are concerned about their employees, the more they will feel about their students, who will depart their academic institutions as compassionate people. However, many studies and literature has focused on improving students' capabilities to demonstrate compassion or how compassion might be cultivated through education (Lipponen, Rajala and Hilppö, 2018). Furthermore, research on organisational compassion in educational contexts has typically concentrated on pupils, ignoring compassion for teachers (Eldor and Shoshani, 2016). Delbecq (2010) observes that there appears to be a disconnect in recognising how to behave compassionately to instructors vs pupils. Research on compassion in the workplace has used qualitative studies to investigate the characteristics of compassionate individuals (Poorkavoos, 2017).

Other research looked at what constitutes compassionate organisations and organisational characteristics that generate compassion from the perspectives of healthcare managers (Avramchuk and Manning, 2014) and business executives (Banker and Bhal, 2018). Another research examined how compassionate behaviours in hospitals help to foster and maintain compassion (Raman and McClelland, 2019). In addition to the concept of compassion potential, types of distress that prompt compassion and forms of compassion were investigated at a hospital (Lilius et al., 2008). Other qualitative investigations of the processes of 'organisational compassion'

(Dutton et al., 2006; Peticca-Harris, 2019) focused on one of the particular incidents of suffering. By describing how compassionate elements create the conditions for collaborative compassion, Dutton et al. (2006) extend the work on compassion organising and contribute vital insights into compassion competency.

Peticca-Harris (2018) investigated the effects of grief following the loss of a co-worker in a restaurant, shedding light on the processes of compassion in a new organisational context. Three managers were questioned, and the results revealed that they were suffering central actors dichotomous role of delivering compassion and suffering simultaneously, which contradicted earlier models (Dutton et al., 2014). Despite this, the study only covered three managers' accounts and provided no employee perspectives. Other research looked at specific types of suffering, such as employees with neurological disorders (Vickers, 2010) or the end of a loving relationship (Little, 2011). Another study looked into compassionate assistance in the aftermath of major disasters, and 25 people from 18 organisations touched by the Brisbane floods were questioned (Simpson, Cunha and Clegg, 2015).

As can be seen, most qualitative research has focused on compassion in connection to distress. However, according to Avramchuk et al. (2014), limiting compassion research to the existence of distress may not explain the currently robust and forward-looking conceptual frameworks of compassion in contemporary organisational behaviour. Quantitative research on compassion has mostly focused on examining the link between compassion in the workplace and other effects (Kanov et al., 2016). Research results suggest an association between workplace compassion and positive feeling (Lilius et al., 2008; Chu, 2016; Subba and Rao, 2016), with those mentioned earlier linked to organisational citizenship behaviour and improved efficiency (Chu, 2016), employee engagement (Lilius et al., 2008; Ko, Kim and Choi, 2021) and organisational commitment (Lilius et al., 2008; Ko, Kim and Choi, 2021). Organisational compassion has also been revealed to be strongly associated with productive work-related belonging (Moon et al., 2016; Hur, Moon and Rhee, 2016), employee engagement (Lilius et al., 2008; Moon et al., 2014), job involvement (Eldor, 2017), effectiveness (Chu, 2016, 2017; Hur, Moon and Rhee, 2016; Eldor, 2017; Aboul-Ela, 2017), mental wellbeing (Chu, 2017).

Organisational compassion was explored to be positively associated with sleeping health and adversely connected to strain and workplace violence (Byron et al., 2018). Research in five Israeli high schools found that demonstrating compassion toward teachers is favourably linked to better affect, emotional liveliness, work satisfaction, and commitment to the organisation while adversely correlated with emotional exhaustion (Eldor and Shoshani, 2016). The second research by Egyptian professors discovered a link between compassion and job effectiveness (Aboul-Ela, 2017). Organisational virtuousness was studied among teachers in schools, and a link was discovered between it and psychological empowerment (Williams, Kern and Waters, 2015), work engagement (Williams et al., 2015; Abedi Kooshki et al., 2016) and job satisfaction (Williams et al., 2015). Nevertheless, because the results of the organisational compassion component were not reported in the above investigations, it is unclear whether the conclusions apply.

The scarcity of organisational compassion research was highlighted in the last review. It also demonstrates that throughout the last decade, quantitative research has focused on compassion as a phenomenon that occurs in an organisational environment, ignoring compassionate variables. Researchers have found that the experience of organisational compassion can increase compassion for others (Henshall et al., 2018).

In addition, Lilius et al. (2008) called for more research into the elements that lead to organisational compassion. Yet, research that looks at compassion as a general trait of organisations is few (Worline and Dutton, 2017), and empirical evidence on organisational determinants is scarce (Vogus and McClelland, 2020). Despite qualitative research findings on the influence and relevance of organisational characteristics on workplace compassion, this has yet to be quantitatively proven. Authors (Huppert, 2017; Eldor, 2017) have emphasised this, highlighting the qualitative nature of extant literature and research on organisational compassion. Simpson et al. (2019) claimed that studying organisational compassion quantitatively using established metrics is an important subsequent step in research. As a result, by experimentally investigating the organisational compassion impact as a moderator, this research will try to address this gap and react to the authors' calls.

Organisational compassion studies are more orientated to be qualitative and accepted as a vital thread in emergent knowledge of organisational compassion. On the other hand, it is

considered to ascertain the findings of quantitative studies and methodologies for generating a legitimate and consistent degree of OC (Lilius et al., 2012). An attempt has been made to address the gap identified in this study of insufficient quantitative studies in organisational compassion and has contributed to the exploration of its substantial impact as a moderator in organisational behaviour studies.

For this study, an SLR is conducted to find answers to the main questions and gather information about emerging trends related to ethical leadership to address the global phenomena of employee job strain and outcomes.

2.5 Systematic Literature review

Systematic reviews attempt to address the issues by characterising, rationally assessing, and incorporating the findings of all relevant, individualised, high-quality research that addresses specific research questions. An excellent systematic review might accomplish most, if not all, of the following (Baumeister and Horton, 2013). Develop a generalised conclusion (do not just summarise everyone else's points). Examine and identify relationships, contradictions, discrepancies and inconsistencies within the literature (for example, by proposing new conceptualisations or explanations for discrepancies).

- Defines the degree to which current work has advanced towards clarifying a particular problem.
- Commenting, analysing, expanding, or evolving theory.
- Give practical and policy implications
- Describe paths for future studies.

Systematic analysis is a work that, by its very definition, can answer far broader issues than any single empirical study ever could. The systematic literature review includes a systematic search method for studies addressing a specific study topic and a systematic presentation and formulation of the features and findings of the search queries (Fiona and Kathy, 2011). The review's inclusion and exclusion criteria are unbiased, stated clearly, and adequately enforced in such a manner that the choice to include or exclude various studies is completely obvious to

readers, and another researcher would most likely reach the same conclusion using the same standards (Grant and Booth, 2009).

This precise approach aims at mitigating bias and encourages review readers to examine the author's findings, methods, facts and conclusions rather than concluding the text. This approach also helps other researchers to update the analysis later so that new results are incorporated. Baumeister and Horton (2013) suggest following the mentality of a judge and jury rather than a prosecutor to serve the aims of systemic analysis better. A judge and jury analyse the evidence with scepticism to make the decision as rational as possible. In comparison, a prosecutor's approach to the facts includes attempting to produce the ultimate specific instance on one side of this issue.

2.5.1 Stage 1: Planning the Review

A group of specialists with expertise in ethical leadership were requested to advise on establishing a comprehensive evaluation procedure before initiating the review process. The panel helped explain the cross-disciplinary complexity of leadership and the diverse viewpoints that can emerge within this evolving framework. A more in-depth examination and analysis were made. In addition, a narrative literature review was conducted in order to identify and explore the growing patterns in ethical leadership-related literature.

The researcher clearly understood what she wanted to know within the research area. What type of research findings can contribute to the topic, and what kind of articles can address the research questions? An expert panel observed developing specific, clear, answerable questions and inclusion and exclusion criteria. Supervisory support was provided in developing unbiased objectives, quality assurance of included studies, and the definition of appropriate review boundaries.

Questions guided the review

Q1: What is the connection between ethical leadership and employee job strain and outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan?

Q2: Does organisational compassion moderate the relationship between ethical leadership and employee job strain and outcomes?

Qualifications for inclusion

- English version of the paper.
- The paper must emphasise ethical leadership.
- One or more review questions are addressed directly in the paper.
- Papers that were published between the years 2000-2020
- The paper's title must include the words addressing the questions of the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- The papers do not address the main questions of the study.

2.5.2 Stage II: Conducting the Review

The research approach was set up by identifying and scanning keywords from the review panel. Table 2.6 detail the keywords and search words.

SLR Search Terms

Table 2. 5: SLR search Terms

Search Word Number	Keywords
word 1	Ethic*
word 1A	Ethical lead*
word 1B	Ethical leadership imp*
word 1C	Leadership and outcomes
word 2	Job strain
word 2A	Leadership and strain*
word 2B	Ethical leader and strain
word 2C	Ethical leadership and job strain
word 3	Leadership and employee*

word 3A	Ethical leadership and employee
word 4	Compassion
word 4A	Organizational Compassion

Ethic* means ethics, ethical, Lead* means leader, leadership etc. Imp* means importance, impact etc., employee means organisational employees, workers, followers etc.

Data management systems are essential because they manage data efficiently and enable users to perform multiple tasks easily. An information management system consists of a single software application that accumulates, organises, and maintains a large amount of information. The search words were used in nine repositories described as the most appropriate for management research. See tables [2.6-2.7].

Table 2. 6: Data Base for Systematic Literature Review

Science Direct	Taylor & Francis	Web of Knowledge
Google Scholar	Sage Journals	Springer link
Wiley Online	Emerald	Elsevier

Databases for SLR

At this research stage, the main aim was to find and gather all available published work that addresses the research questions. The best way to gather the required material is to use comprehensive and relevant databases.

The literature is chosen based on search words; to acquire the appropriate ones. According to the standard of inclusion and exclusion, title and abstract screening were performed. Citations and references of these publications are reviewed for their inclusion or exclusion. There were 151 articles in total found at the first stage. The review process further refined these papers, and duplicate papers were rejected. For exporting research results, Endnote was used. The article's title and abstract were thoroughly read, and further selection was made based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. A list of all accepted articles was made. These articles' citations and references were thoroughly reviewed. Finally, 69 papers were chosen for analysis and further evaluation based on the inclusion criteria. It was made sure that all selected articles were properly referenced. It was determined that all potentially eligible studies were suitable and vital for acceptance.

Research Quality Evaluation

Each paper observed through the SLR procedure was evaluated based on content standards.

- Is the paper presenting specific facts and arguments?
- Is the article cited appropriately?

2.5.3 Stage III: Reporting and Dissemination

This section summarises the literature reviewed on ethical leadership. The table [2.8] below gives the focus of reviewed articles.

Focus of the articles reviewed

Table 2. 7: Articles Reviewed summary

Article	Names of Authors	Focus
1. "Ethical leadership: A review and future directions."	(Brown and Trevino, 2006)	The purpose of this paper is to present theories about the causes and effects of ethical leadership. This study examines the concept of ethical leadership and compares it with related notions similar to spiritual, authentic, and transformational leadership.
2. "Does EL Motivate Followers to Participate in Delivering compassion"?	(Lara and Armas, 2019)	In this study, compassionate feelings are hypothesised to operate as a moderator between ethical leadership and interpersonal citizenship behaviour. It was discovered that compassionate leadership and peer-focused citizenship were highly and directly connected with ethical leadership.
3. "The impact of EL and leadership effectiveness on employees' turnover intention: The mediating role of work-related stress."	(Elçi et al., 2012)	In this study, ethical leadership and leadership efficiency were examined for their impact on employee turnover intentions. According to the study, while employee turnover intentions are negatively affected by EL and leadership effectiveness, work-related strain is beneficial.
4. "Leaders matter morally: The role of EL in shaping employee moral cognition and misconduct".	(Moore et al., 2019),	This research looks into how ethical leaders influence how employees understand morally reprehensible decisions and thus how they act. It was discovered that EL diminishes employees' moral detachment,

		with long-term implications for incorrect conduct and aberrant behaviour.
5. "A three-level examination of the cascading effects of EL on-employee outcomes: A moderated mediation analysis."	(Byun et al., 2018)	By using a moderated-mediation framework, this study examines high-level leaders' job performance and low-level leaders' job performance. According to the findings, EL from upper-level executives flows down to lower-level executives, lowering incivility and improving job outcomes."
6. "Leader mindfulness and employee Outcomes: A sequential mediation model of LMX quality, interpersonal justice, and employee."	(Reb et al., 2019),	This research analyses the relationship between leader attentiveness and work outcomes through the lenses of organisational justice and leader-member relations. Employees of more aware leaders may regard their leader-member exchange (LMX) connections to be of greater quality. According to the researchers, two other mediating mechanisms supporting this link are improved interactional justice and less employee strain.
7. "Impact of leadership styles on employees' attitude towards their leader and outcomes: Empirical evidence from Pakistani banks."	(Asrar-ul-Haq and Kuchinke, 2016)	Researchers examined the effect of managers' leadership styles on their followers' performance. The impact of leadership styles on employee outcomes is explored theoretically and methodologically in the Pakistani banking sector. According to the findings of this study, transformational leadership and evaluation outcomes have a significant association".

<p>8. "How EL shapes employees' job outcomes: The mediating roles of goal congruence and psychological capital."</p>	<p>(Bouckenooghe, Zafar and Raja, 2015)</p>	<p>Psychological capital and goal congruency mediate the relationship between subordinate style and in-role performance. Results were investigated in this study and established that EL has a favourable impact on followers' in-role employment results, but that this effect is mediated by psychological capital.</p>
<p>9. "EL: Assessing the value of a multi-social exchange perspective."</p>	<p>(Hansen et al., 2013)</p>	<p>Employee engagement, EL, and social exchange are examined in this study. It was also discovered that both directly and indirectly, organisational EL is linked to employee outcomes.</p>
<p>10. "Influence of EL on- Employee Job outcomes."</p>	<p>(Bello, 2012)</p>	<p>An ethical leader is one who possesses specific attributes, the implications of EL on-employee work outcomes, and how organisations may build leaders who are not only trustworthy in person but also effective in action. Two crucial elements, commitment and trust, were explored to understand EL and employee job outcomes better.</p>
<p>11. "Who Displays EL, and why does it matter? An Examination of Antecedents and Consequences of EL."</p>	<p>(Mayer et al., 2012)</p>	<p>When compared with comparable leadership constructs, ethical leadership is differentiated, including inspirational motivation, interpersonal justice, and procedural fairness in this study.</p>
<p>12. "Embedding EL within and across organisational Levels."</p>	<p>(Schaubroeck et al., 2012)</p>	<p>This paper analyses and implements a model that connects ethical leadership to the department's ethical culture along the front</p>

		organisational level and investigates how leadership and culture affect lower-level followers' ethical skills and behaviours.
13. "Linking EI to EO: The Roles of Leader-Member Exchange, Self-Efficacy, and Organizational Identification"	(Walumbwa et al., 2011)	Data from the People's Republic of China was used to examine the relationship between ethical leadership and outcomes. The LMX, self-efficacy, and organisational identity played a mediation role in the ethical leadership–outcomes link. Self-efficacy, LMX, and organizational identity were found to strongly mediate the relationship between ethical leadership and job results.
14. "Improving the "leader-follower" relationship: Top manager or supervisor? The EL trickle-down effect on follower job response."	(Ruiz, Ruiz, and Martinez 2011)	An empirical study is undertaken to better understand the factors that promote good morals in leadership, with a positive representation of the manager-subordinate relationship. We found that followers' job performance is improved when the top manager practices ethics trickle down.
15. "When leadership goes unnoticed: The moderating role of follower self-esteem on the relationship between EL and follower behaviour."	(Avey, Palanski and Walumbwa, 2011)	The researchers assessed the impact on organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) and deviant conduct among followers. Follower OCB and deviant behavior are positively associated with ethical leadership.
16. "Ethical and unEL: Exploring new avenues for future research".	(Brown and Mitchell, 2010)	This study aims to examine significant literature related to the social scientific leadership role and ethics, as well as to assess future research paths. Three major themes in organizational behavior

		literature should be considered in a leadership and ethics study agenda.
17. "EL".	(Mihelic, Lipicnik and Tekavcic, 2010)	The topic of ethical leadership is investigated in this paper. Ethical leaders consider organisational decisions' long-term consequences, drawbacks, and benefits. Leaders create an example for their followers by showing the values established inside a company. They are considered honest, credible, heroic, and operating in good faith.
18. "The Association Between EL and Employee Outcomes—the Malaysian Case."	(Ponnu andTennakoon, 2009),	This research aims to look at how ethical leadership behaviour affects employee behavioural outcomes, including organisational loyalty and cooperation in leaders. The research supports the hypothesis that ethical leadership behaviour is linked to employee commitment to the firm and supervisor trust.
19. "EL: Examining the Relationships with Full Range Leadership Model, Employee Outcomes, and organisational culture".	(Toor and Ofori, 2009)	Singapore's construction business has been investigated empirically for ethical leadership. Transformational leadership, organisational transformational ideals, transactional leadership compensation, leader effectiveness and employee motivation as well as employee endorsements of the leader are all strongly and substantially linked to ethical leadership. Despite this, it has been discovered that there is no link between ethical and transactional leadership.
20. "Do ethical leaders give followers the confidence to go	(Tu and Lu, 2016)	The study examined how ethical leadership enhances

<p>the extra mile? The moderating role of intrinsic motivation."</p>		<p>followers' power. Leadership style training led to higher outcomes for those with intrinsically motivated behaviors. The results of leadership style training were higher for employees who had the essential self, however. Findings suggest ethical leadership influences self-efficacy.</p>
<p>21. "EL, employee wellbeing, and helping".</p>	<p>(Kalshoven and Boon, 2012)</p>	<p>This research proposed a mediated moderation model that links ethical leadership to assisting, with wellbeing as an intermediator and HRM as a contextual moderator. It demonstrated that a significant positive association between ethical leadership and helping occurs when HRM is weak but not when HRM is robust. Job-related wellbeing mediated the connection between ethical leadership, HRM, and employee assistance.</p>
<p>22. "Someone to Look Up to Executive-Follower Ethical Reasoning and Perceptions of EL."</p>	<p>(Jordan et al., 2013)</p>	<p>According to the authors of this study, subordinates' perceptions of ethical leadership are affected by high leadership cognitively moral development (CMD) and by the relationship between top leaders and followers CMD. It has been observed that when the leader's CMD differs from and surpasses the follower's CMD, ethical leadership is increased.</p>
<p>23. "Doing Well by Doing Good? Analysing the Relationship Between CEO EL and Firm outcomes."</p>	<p>(Eisenbeiss, Knippenberg and Fahrback, 2015)</p>	<p>This study recommends a moderated mediation study of the relationship between corporate management ethical leadership and firm outcomes, recognising mediating (overall organisational ethical code of</p>

		conduct) and moderating (corporate executive ethical leadership) variables unique to the organization level assessment.
24. "It is All a Matter of Consensus: Leader Role Modeling Strength as a Moderator of the Links Between EL and Employee Outcomes."	(Ogunfowora, 2014)	The goal of this study is to see if EL affects such consequences that are mediated by leader role modelling capability, a unit-level structure that incorporates the extent to which unit members regard their supervisor as a model for ethical behaviour in the workplace.
25. "The Effects of EL and Ethical Climate on Employee Ethical Behavior in the International Port Context."	(Lu and Lin, 2014)	Individual ethical behavior was examined in relation to ethical climate and ethical leadership. A significant impact of EL can be seen on the ethical climate and employee behavior.
26. "Improving Employee Job outcomes through EL and "Guanxi": The Moderation Effects of Supervisor-Subordinate Guanxi Differentiation."	(Weng 2014)	This study uses the foundational mediating paradigm of manager guanxi to establish ethical leadership as the primary type of influence over employee employment outcomes (i.e., long-standing interactive relationship). The variance in supervisor-subordinate guanxi is also discovered to be a combination of linked characteristics that has a considerable effect on the connection between leader follower guanxi and employee job outcomes.
27. "EL and Job outcomes in China: The Roles of Workplace Friendships and traditionality."	(Liu et al., 2013)	The relationship between ethical leadership as seen by followers, outcomes, and organisational citizenship behaviour was investigated in

		<p>this study. It discovered a connection between ethical leadership and the OCBO and OCBI of subordinates. Furthermore, interactions between employees and their workplaces enhanced the relationship between ethical leadership and positive outcomes.</p>
<p>28. "EL: Assessing the Value of a Multifoci Social Exchange Perspective."</p>	<p>(Hansen et al., 2013)</p>	<p>This study aimed to look at the links between ethical leadership, social interaction, and employees' commitment. Employee loyalty to the company and supervisory ethical leadership have a beneficial relationship. It has also been observed that different kinds of social interaction relationships act as bridges between these partnerships.</p>
<p>29. "The relationship between EL and core job characteristics."</p>	<p>(Piccolo et al., 2010)</p>	<p>Studying ethical leadership, task identity, effort, task importance, and work outcomes using the original job characteristics model (JCM) and a detailed and complicated workflow model. A field experiment was done by polling pairs of coworkers from various organisations. Findings support a fully mediated model linking ethical leadership to employee job outcomes through task importance and moderate effort.</p>
<p>30. "EL across cultures: A comparative analysis of German and US perspectives."</p>	<p>(Martin et al., 2009)</p>	<p>This article aims to investigate two questions: Do middle managers in Germany and the United States have different perspectives on ethical leadership? Do people in these two countries regard ethical</p>

		leaders in different ways? The data demonstrate that middle managers in Germany and the United States differed in their support for each feature.
31. "Leader empathy, EL, and relations-oriented behaviours as antecedents of leader-member exchange quality."	(Mahsud, Yukl and Prussia, 2010)	Although it appears that leader compassion, moral views, and relational behaviour are all necessary for influential leadership, no one has looked at how all three characteristics are related to the quality of leader-member exchange (LMX). This study aims to look into these linkages and test a proposed model for characterising them.
32. "EL: Meta-analytic evidence of criterion-related and incremental validity."	(Ng and Feldman, 2015)	This study explores ethical leadership's set of requirements and progressive authenticity using meta-analytic data (EL). EL established satisfactory criterion-related reasoning with components that investigate followers' job behaviours, work outcomes, and leader assessments. Furthermore, the relationship between EL and job results and attitude was mediated by subordinates' trust in the leader.
33. "The cascading effect of top management's EL: Supervisors or other lower-hierarchical level individuals"?	(Ruiz and Martinez, 2011)	To examine that theory, a study was undertaken in Spanish banking organisations, and it was determined that there was a transient descending impact, not at the top management levels but among peer groups. These findings support the idea that, contrary to popular belief, peers, rather than supervisory levels, have a crucial effect.

<p>34. "The Being of Leadership."</p>	<p>(Wiley and Souba, 2011)</p>	<p>The redesigned leadership paradigm, which distinguishes being a leader as the Epistemological grounds for what leaders recognise, acquire, and indeed do, is crucial to ensuring medicine's ethical base, according to this research. Four ontological pillars of leadership are considered important aspects that underpin this groundwork and the basic conceits of professionalism: knowledge, devotion, truth, and integrity.</p>
<p>35. "Ethical maturity and successful leadership."</p>	<p>(Duffield and McCuen, 2000)</p>	<p>Leaders must be ethically matured individually to be successful in business, and they must strive to increase the ethical development of their subordinates. Mentorships on ethical issues and specialised applications that leaders could have employed to achieve moral maturity within their organisation are discussed.</p>
<p>36. "Implicit motives, leadership, and follower outcomes: An empirical test of CEOs."</p>	<p>(Delbecq et al., 2013),</p>	<p>Three aspects of subordinate motivation, outcomes, and cooperation were studied due to different leadership styles. Only charismatic leaders, according to the studies, have a powerful linkage with all three factors.</p>

<p>37. "From ideal to real: a longitudinal study of the role of implicit leadership theories on leader-member exchanges and employee outcomes".</p>	<p>(Epitropaki and Martin, 2005)</p>	<p>The study's findings revealed the importance of underlying leadership theories (ILTs) for the consistency of leader-member exchanges (LMX) and employees' devotion to the organisation. The difference in implicit versus explicit leadership traits also influenced employee behaviours and obligations.</p>
<p>38. "Leadership behaviour and subordinate wellbeing."</p>	<p>(Dierendonck, Haynes, Borrill, and Stride 2004)</p>	<p>Leadership behavior and follower wellbeing were examined through a longitudinal research design.</p>
<p>39. "Chronic job stressors and job control: Effects on event-related coping success and wellbeing."</p>	<p>(Elfering et al., 2005)</p>	<p>This research examines how persisting work-related characteristics interact with contextual work-related beliefs, as well as how they influence outcomes such as wellbeing, problem-solving skills, and the ability to remain calm. Multi-level assessments demonstrated that work authority was strongly linked with successful soothing down and problem-solving in stressful events in the case of chronic circumstances. However, job causes of stress were inversely associated with instantaneous wellbeing.</p>
<p>40. "Implementing EL: Current Challenges and Solutions".</p>	<p>(Thompson, Thach and Morelli, 2010)</p>	<p>This paper discusses numerous organisational difficulties and suggests remedies based on ethical leadership implications.</p>
<p>41. "Leadership style, organisational culture and outcomes: empirical evidence from UK companies."</p>	<p>(Ogbonna and Harris, 2000).</p>	<p>The study examines leadership and outcomes as well as cultural values. The results of leadership styles are also</p>

		influenced by the organizational culture.
42. "Effects of EL on-employee Outcomes in Uganda."	(Obicci, 2015)	Uganda's public sector employees' outcomes were examined in this research. Employee outcomes are significantly influenced by ethical leadership, according to the study.
43. "Reversing the extraverted leadership advantage: The role of employee proactivity."	(Grant and Hofmann, 2011)	This study aims to find out if extroverted leaders can lead groups more efficiently. A study indicated that when employees were quiet, pizza shops with bosses who were high (low) in openness to experience made more money (proactive). Additionally, groups did better when leaders exhibited high (low) receptivity to knowledge.
44. "Organisational culture and transformational leadership as predictors of employee outcomes."	(Biswas 2009)	Several factors are highlighted that substantially impact individual and organisational efficiency. Human resource development and individual worker outcomes were found to be significantly influenced by organisational culture and transformational leadership. This research aims to see how corporate cultural values and transformational leadership affect an employee's decision to quit their present company.
45. "What EL means to me: Asian, American, and European perspectives."	(Resick et al., 2011)	This research aims to look for areas of agreement and disagreement across cultures by looking at how managers in six different nations view ethical and unethical leadership. Every culture's dominant theme for ethical and unethical leadership is examined in depth in the

		context of that society's underlying cultural values and practices.
46. "Trust in leadership: A multi-level review and integration."	(Burke et al., 2007)	This study observes that the degree to which employees and coworkers recognise a leader significantly impacts his or her ability to be effective in the workplace.
47. "Managing competing values: Leadership styles of mayors and CEOs."	(Martin and Simons, 2002)	In this study, the top executive leadership style and its impacts on the organisation are observed.
48. "Ethical and despotic leadership, relationships with leader's social responsibility, top management team effectiveness and subordinates' optimism: A multi-method study."	(De Hoogh and Den Hartog, 2008)	Social responsibility, power sharing, and autocratic leadership were examined during this study. Research found that leaders with high social responsibility exhibited more ethical leadership.
49. "Leadership in a Wiki World: Leveraging Collective Knowledge to Make the Leap to extraordinary outcomes."	(Collins 2010)	413 Australian mayors and chief executives responded to analogies assessing the effectiveness of their professional partnership in this study. According to Cameron and Quinn's Conceptual Framework, efficient work relationships are more likely when one supervisor's managerial style complements or is identical to the others.
50. "Exploring the process of EL: The mediating role of employee voice and psychological ownership."	(Avey, Wernsing and Palanski, 2012)	An investigation was conducted to determine if ethical leadership is associated with positive job outcomes. Based on the findings of the study, EL has a important contribution to the emotional health and outcomes of the workforce. Psychological wellbeing was linked to ethical

		leadership through employee voice.
51. "Meta-analysis of the impact of positive psychological capital on employee attitudes, behaviours, and outcomes."	(Avey et al., 2011)	The PsyCap study stream has progressed to the point where a quantitative summary analysis of its effects on staff behaviours, habits, and, most crucially, outcomes is needed. The findings demonstrated that PsyCap has the expected substantial relationships with desirable employee behaviours (citizenship) and various outcome metrics.
52. "Remedy for work stress: the impact and mechanism of EL."	(Zhou, Jin and Ma, 2015)	This research aimed to see if and how ethical leadership affects employee stress at work, focusing on the mediating effect of leader-member exchange (LMX), which refers to relational interpersonal interactions between leaders and subordinates in the workplace. Employees' opinions of work were considerably negatively connected with managers' ethical leadership.
53. "Leadership and stress: A meta-analytic review."	(Harms et al., 2017)	Using a meta-analytic method, investigate the relationship between three leadership theories (transformational leadership, leader-member exchange, and workplace bullying) and emotional exhaustion. According to assessments, management styles and leader-follower relationships are essential predictors of extreme stress among followers.
54. "Impact of Stressors (Role conflict, Role overload, Leadership Support and Organisational Politics) on Job	(Parvaiz et al., 2015)	The purpose of this study was to determine whether job stress can be affected by stressors, role conflicts, role overloads,

<p>Stress and its subsequent impact on Turnover Intention."</p>		<p>leadership support, and organizational politics. and, as a result, Intention to Leave the Pakistani academic sector. Job Stress had a strong positive link with Intention to Leave, and Job Strain had a significantly positive correlation with Intent To Move.</p>
<p>55. "Investigating the impact of EL on aspects of burnout."</p>	<p>(Okpozo et al., 2017)</p>	<p>A study is conducted to examine the effects of ethical leadership on the exertion process of large groups of people, as well as the mediating effects of general self-efficacy and managerial support on the effects of ethical leadership on the exhaustion caused by specific exhaustion and ethical leadership behavior. According to the findings, ethical leadership had a significant positive impact on personal accomplishment via general self-efficacy and a critical indirect impact on emotional fatigue".</p>
<p>56." Leadership, job strain and employee behaviour."</p>	<p>(Yao et al., 2014)</p>	<p>As part of this study, researcher examine the relationship between work stress and favourable employee attitudes, along with how transformational and transactional leadership moderates that relationship. According to a study, there is a correlation between job stress and bad attitudes among employees.</p>
<p>57. "The relationship between perceived leadership style and perceived stress on hospital employees."</p>	<p>(Baysak and Yener, 2015)</p>	<p>This quantitative study aimed to see if there was a link between reported strain and perceived leadership style among hospital personnel in</p>

		Istanbul, Turkey, and if so, to what extent. According to the data, there was a transitory link between psychological leadership structure and job strain.
58. "The challenge of EL."	(Fulmer 2004)	This article looks into what some company stakeholders and academics are trying to say and do in response to public concerns regarding various techniques and tactics for developing ethical leadership skills.
59. "The influence of EL and regulatory focus on employee outcome."	(Neubert and Roberts 2013)	The regulatory emphasis hypothesis was proposed to explain the impact of ethical leadership on corporate citizenship behaviours and worker agreements. The findings of the study mainly corroborate the anticipated connections and point to significant implications for ethical leadership in the workplace.
60. "In favour of ethics in business: the linkage between ethical behaviour and outcomes."	(Upadhyay and Singh, 2010)	The essay illustrates the corporate sector's dilemma in recognising ethical business methods. Scientific findings aimed to see if ethical behaviour leads to underside growth on a larger scale. It also means that the conceptual framework must be updated to examine a firm's outcomes.
61. "How does EL flow? Test of a trickle-down model".	(Mayer and Greenbaum, 2009)	It concludes that ethical leadership flows from upper management to lower management within an organization. A positive correlation exists between OCB and group level deviation, while a negative correlation exists between

		OCB and group level deviation.
62. "A Meta-analytic Review of EL Outcomes and Moderators."	(Bedi and Green, 2016)	Based on social learning and social exchange theories, the authors examined the relationship between ethical leadership and followers' work outcomes. Several favourable outcomes can be attributed to ethical leadership, including supervisor fairness perceptions and ethical attitudes among followers.
63. "Unlocking the mask: A look at the process by which authentic leaders impact follower attitudes and behaviours".	(Avolio and Walumbwa, 2004)	Authentic leaders influence followers' behaviors, activities, and outcomes, and this study builds on that foundation. Based on the hypothesised model method, future theoretical development and research proposals were generated.
64. "Effect of leadership development on employee outcomes in Pakistan Pakistan economic and social review."	(Abbas and Yaqoob, 2009)	The study's goal was to see how leadership development affected employee outcomes in Pakistan. This study looked at five aspects of leadership development: mentoring, learning and support, autonomy, involvement, and delegating, and discovered that the cumulative impact of these elements has a 50% impact on staff outcomes.
65. "Mirroring the Boss: EL, Emulation Intentions, and Salesperson outcomes".	(Badrinarayanan and Madhavaram, 2019)	This study claims that sales managers' ethical leadership influences salespeople's motivations, as well as their motivations to create or mimic managers' ethical behaviour, which, in turn, impacts both managers' behaviour and outcomes.

<p>66. "My boss is morally disengaged: The role of EL in explaining the interactive effect of supervisor and employee moral disengagement on an employee."</p>	<p>(Greenbaum and Mayer 2016)</p>	<p>The goal of this study is to see how moral disengagement among supervisors affects perceptions of employees of ethical leadership. The results of a multi-source field study back up our theoretical model in general.</p>
<p>67. "Exploring the process of EL: The mediating role of employee voice and psychological ownership."</p>	<p>(Avey, 2012)</p>	<p>A study investigated the links between ethical leadership and positive employee outcomes, including 845 working individuals from various firms. According to the findings, employees' psychological wellbeing and job happiness are linked to ethical leadership.</p>
<p>68. "When do ethical leaders become less effective? The moderating role of perceived leader ethical conviction on employee discretionary reactions to EL."</p>	<p>(Babalola et al., 2019)</p>	<p>The authors claim that perceived ethical leadership and ethical behavior are moderated by perceived leader moral conviction based on the group engagement model and the research on moral conviction. Leadership and employee OCB".</p>
<p>69. "EL and knowledge hiding: an intervening and interactional analysis."</p>	<p>(Anser et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Among service personnel, meaningful work has the potential to mediate the negative relationship between ethical leadership and knowledge-hiding. Among service employees, harmony work enthusiasm was also studied in relation to the direct relationship between ethical leadership and knowledge-hiding behavior.</p>

2.5.4 Descriptive Analysis

Contributions based on Geographical Distribution

In the focus area, many studies (30) are conducted in the USA. Nineteen countries are represented in which. In terms of research volume, China ranks second. Interestingly, most of the research in this area is conducted in the western world, and very few studies are generated in developing countries. This enhances the importance of research being conducted in developing countries, especially in Pakistan and thus contributes to the significance of the presented research. See Figure [2.4].

Geographical Distribution of studies

Figure 2. 4: Studies Spread by Region

Types of Studies

According to the review's findings, 81% of research is empirical. 3% are literature reviews, and 16% are conceptual, as seen in figure [2.5]. Additionally, 73% of the empirical studies were quantitative, 21% used qualitative, and 6% applied a mixed method approach presented in figure [2.6].

Figure 2. 5: Types of Studies

Empirical studies

Figure 2. 6: Empirical studies

2.6 Method of Data Collection

Data collection was conducted using questionnaires (64%), 34% used case studies and Interviews' (1%) demonstrated in figure [2.7].

Figure 2. 7: Method of Data Collection

2.7 Number of Publications

A five-year analysis of the number of publications in the focused area can be found in Figure [2.8]. Major publications are made from the period of 2001 to 2015. In this period, ethical leadership was the most discussed topic, particularly in the western world, and significant impacts and influences were explored in this period. However, unfortunately, most research was carried out from a western perspective, so the impact of geographical, cultural and organisational differences is not sufficiently explored.

Figure 2. 8: Five-year interval of papers published

2.8 Literature sources

Table [2.9] details the journals in which the focused publications are mainly published. Among all the journals on the list, the Journal of Business Ethics has the most citations, and it is also justified by the fact that it is a highly reported journal perfect for publications about ethical leadership.

Table 2. 8: Highest cited journals

<i>Name of Journal</i>	<i>Number of Papers</i>
“Journal of Business Ethics”	15
“The Leadership Quarterly”	6
“Academy of Management Journal”	4
“Journal of Applied Psychology”	3
“Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology”	3
“Organisational Behavior and Human Decision Processes”	3
“Business Ethics Quarterly”	2

"Electronic Journal of Business Ethics and Organization Studies"	2
"Journal of Human Values"	2
"Journal of Organizational Behavior"	2
"Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences"	2
"African Journal of Business Management"	1
"Asia Pacific Management Review"	1
"Australian Journal of Public Administration"	1
"Business Ethics, A European Review"	1
"J Public Health"	1
"Chinese Management Studies"	1
"Ethics and Behavior"	1
"Future Business Journal"	1
"Human Relations"	1
"Human Resource Development Quarterly"	1
"Insights to a Changing World Journal"	1
"Institute for Corporate Ethics"	1
"International Journal of Business and Management Invention"	1
"International Journal of Social Science"s	1
"International Journal of Management and Information System"	1
"Journal of Business Research"	1
"Journal of Leadership and Organizational Studies"	1
"Journal of Management and Information Systems"	1
"Journal of Managerial Psychology"	1
"Journal of Personnel Psychology"	1
"Journal of Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice"	1
"Leadership and Organization Development Journal"	1
"Net journal of business management"	1
"Organizational Dynamics"	1

"Philosophy, Ethics, and Humanities in Medicine"	1
Total	69

2.9 Citation

Figure [2.9] shows the top five articles with the highest citations. The most cited article is by Brown and Trevino (2006), with 3209 citations. This is not surprising because Brown and Trevino have unparalleled contributions in the research related to ethical leadership.

Figure 2. 9: Number of citations

This figure gives a spread of citations across years.

2.9.1 Spread of Citations by five-year interval

It can easily be seen in figure [2.10] that the maximum number of citations is between 2006 to 2010 and then till 2015. During this period, maximum research was conducted in ethical leadership and carried out in the western world, whereas the eastern world remains barren to carry

out research. This factor enhances the significance of an investigation to be carried out in the eastern world, especially the developing countries, so that the influence of geographical and cultural changes can be observed.

Figure 2. 10: Citations by five-year interval

Q1: What is the impression of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes?

According to research on ethical leadership, it positively impacts employees within companies. Sixty-nine studies were identified as responding to the question, out of which 15 research answered this question and showed a positive connection between ethical leadership and employee outcomes, and four were conducted on job strain. Leadership relation concluded a negative association between ethical leadership and job stress. This research is 100% based on empirical findings and observations. Only 13% of research is conducted in developing countries, whereas 86% of empirical evidence is from developed countries, mainly in the west.

Table 2. 9: Papers that helped in answering the first question

Title	Authors
"Do ethical leaders give followers the confidence to go the extra mile? The moderating role of intrinsic motivation."	Tu and Lu (2016)
"How Ethical Leadership Shapes Employees' Job outcomes: The Mediating Roles of Goal Congruence and Psychological capital."	Bouckennooghe, Zafar and Raja, (2015)
"Remedy for job strain: the impact and mechanism of ethical leadership."	Ma, Cheng and Zhou (2013)
"The relationship between ethical leadership and core job characteristics"	Piccolo et al., (2010)
"The cascading effect of top management's ethical leadership: Supervisors or other lower-hierarchical level individuals"?	Ruiz and Martínez, (2011)
"Implicit motives, leadership, and follower outcomes: An empirical test of CEOs"	Delbec et al., (2013)
"Leadership style, organisational culture and outcomes: empirical evidence from UK companies"	Ogbonna and Harris, (2000).
"Effects of ethical leadership on employee Outcomes in Uganda"	Obicci, (2015)
"Leadership and stress: A meta-analytic review"	Harms et al. (2017)
"Improving Employee Job outcomes through Ethical Leadership and "Guanxi": The Moderation Effects of Supervisor-Subordinate Guanxi Differentiation."	Weng, (2014)
"Investigating the impact of ethical leadership on aspects of burnout."	Okpozo et al. (2017)
"In favour of ethics in business: the linkage between ethical behaviour and outcomes"	Upadhyay and Singh (2010)
"Impact of Stressors (Role conflict, Role overload, Leadership Support and Organisational Politics) on	Parvaiz et al. (2015)

Job Stress and its subsequent impact on Turnover Intention”	
“The relationship between perceived leadership style and perceived stress on hospital employees”	Baysak and Yener (2015)
“Mirroring the Boss: Ethical Leadership, Emulation Intentions, and Salesperson outcomes”.	Badrinarayanan, Ramachandran and Madhavaram, (2019)

Q2: Does organisational compassion moderate the relationship between ethical leadership and employee job strain and outcomes?

Acknowledging the influence of organisational compassion in an organisational environment (Kanov et al., 2004). The concept of organisational compassion is the act of sharing the subprocesses as a response to the distress of members in an organisation, which is facilitated by a variety of organisational factors such as culture, routines, networks, and leadership (Dutton et al., 2014; Kanov et al., 2016; Worline and Dutton, 2017). This conceptualisation acknowledges organisational factors as crucial to facilitating organisational compassion (Simpson et al., 2015). Literature reviews indicate that empirical studies have typically focused on compassion at work, examining compassion within organisational contexts while neglecting leadership influences. As a moderator, the present study examined organisational compassion as an overall characteristic of an organisation that has received little attention in quantitative studies (Worline and Dutton, 2017).

2.10 Summary

While the production of knowledge within the field of business research is accelerating at a rapid pace, it remains fragmented and interdisciplinary. Due to this, it is difficult to remain current with state-of-the-art research and to be at the forefront, as well as to assess the collective evidence in a particular field of research. This is one of the reasons why literature reviews are more relevant today than ever before. Literature reviews are a systematic way of gathering and synthesizing previous research (Baumeister & Leary, 1997; Tranfield, Denyer, & Smart, 2003). The use of a well-conducted and effective literature review as a research method contributes to the advancement of knowledge and facilitates the development of theories (Webster & Watson, 2002).

Literature reviews provide a unique opportunity to address research questions by integrating findings and perspectives from a wide range of empirical studies. The purpose of this study literature review is to provide an overview of areas in which research has been conducted that are disparate and interdisciplinary. This literature review provides an excellent way of synthesizing research findings to uncover areas of research that need to be further explored, which is an integral part of the process of creating theoretical frameworks and building conceptual models. However, traditional methods of describing and portraying the literature lack thoroughness and are not conducted systematically (Tranfield et al., 2003). Consequently, it is impossible to determine what the collection of studies means or what it is pointing towards. Therefore, there is a high probability that authors will base their research on flawed assumptions. Whenever researchers ignore research that points in the opposite direction, serious problems can arise because they are selective in their choice of evidence. In addition, even when the methodology of the reviews is valid, there are often questions regarding what constitutes a valuable contribution to the field.

The literature review outlines the study's main themes and shows how they relate. First, it discussed in detail the independent variable, which was ethical leadership. The literature suggests that ethical leadership concepts have a significant impact on a variety of employee and organisational outcomes, including work strain (Bass and Avolio, 1993; Bavik et al., 2018; Haakonsson et al., 2008), work satisfaction (Chang, 2016; Tu and Lu, 2016), and performance (Bass and Avolio, 1993; Bavik et al., 2018; Haakonsson et al., 2008; Ghadi et al., 2013; Demirtas, 2015; Vincent-Hoerper et al., 2012). It further discussed two independent variables: employee job strain and employee outcomes. The literature explored the connections between variables in different contexts. One of the crucial variables, organisational compassion, that served as moderator was discussed. All the direct and indirect relationships between variables were explored, which led to the theoretical framework presented in chapter 3. Based on explored knowledge, hypotheses were generated that further guided the research.

In addition, systematic reviews aim to identify all research addressing a specific question to provide an unbiased and balanced overview of the literature. In order to identify studies to be included in systematic reviews, methods have been developed specifically to identify negative

studies published in low impact journals or conference proceedings. These studies may not be indexed in bibliographic databases, but which may balance out the results of more easily identified positive studies.

As part of a systematic literature review, a comprehensive overview of literature related to a research question is presented. Furthermore, all prior work was synthesized to strengthen the research question's foundation of knowledge, while adhering to the principles of transparency and bias reduction.

Chapter 3

Theoretical Perspective

The theoretical framework of a study is based on some theory or theories (for instance, motivation theory). Theory, on the other hand, can serve as the foundation for developing a conceptual framework. This chapter explains the theories that support the theoretical framework presented in this research. It also presented the research hypothesis, further tested, and results generated for the research.

3.1 Introduction

This chapter explains the theories that support this research's theoretical framework. It also presented the hypothesis of the research, which was further tested, and results generated for the research. This study conceptualized that the job strain of employees in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan can be reduced considerably, and outcomes can be enhanced if organizational compassion is executed along with ethical leadership in the organization. This context would allow the companies to enhance the health of employees and the business's health. The literature review shows that leadership has some connection with employee job strain and outcomes. Therefore, in the theoretical framework, ethical leadership practice is taken as an independent variable, organizational compassion as the moderating factor, and employee job strain and outcomes as a dependent variable.

3.2 Theoretical Underpinning

This study conceptualized four theories to explain the effects of ethical leadership on employees' job strain and outcomes. First is a theory of social learning, which believes that individuals learn from the values and behaviors of individuals in authority and then replicate those values and behaviors in their own behavior (Bandura and Walters, 1977). In ethical leadership and outcomes research, social learning theory is widely used (Tu and Lu, 2016). Social learning involves both behaviour and inspiration on the part of ethical leaders. From one perspective, ethical leaders are defined as "moral managers" who enforce an appropriate level of ethics in their daily affairs and personalities, serving as ethical mentors for coworkers (Gibson, 2004; Davis and Luthans, 1980).

The "moral manager" concept of ethical leadership, on the other hand, relates to effective communication of aspirations and responses to subordinates' attitudes and actions (Trevino et al., 2000; Ogunfowora, 2014). The connection between ethical leadership and social learning is undeniable regarding ethical attitudes and morals. Additionally, it has been used to facilitate leader-member exchange (Dhar, 2017), organizational citizenship behaviour (Páez and Salgado, 2016), and innovation (Chen and Hou, 2016). There has been criticism that social learning theory employs excessively in this framework, particularly relating to its relevance to the context and outcomes studied (Ogunfowora, 2014; Zhu et al., 2015). Further theoretical underpinnings should give insight into the processes entailed.

However, this thorough application of social learning theory demonstrates the theory's value and importance in the ethical leadership and outcomes literature. In organizations, leaders serve as role models and convey followers' ethical values. From the behaviour of an ethical leader, the employee can learn to sustain job pressures and finish the tasks adequately and effectively contribute to the organization (Mahsud, Yukl, and Prussia, 2010). The second theoretical foundation on which this research is anchored is the social exchange process theory, which, like social learning theory, proposes that individuals make choices by knowingly or unknowingly weighing the risks and consequences of a connection or response, eventually seeking to increase their benefit (Homans, 1989). Under the impact of ethical leadership, social exchange theory provides a sound theoretical framework for examining if and how subordinates are motivated to achieve required outcomes. As a result, it was proposed that social interaction assisted the association between ethical leadership and subordinate job pressure and outcomes.

This study is also supported by the expectancy theory developed by Victor Vroom in 1970. This theory proposes that one can influence individual motivation through a particular behavior to generate a particular outcome or behavior (Oliver, 1974). Motivated individuals are expected to achieve a specific outcome because they are motivated in a specific manner. This theory helps in the conceptualization that the organization expects specific behaviour in response to practices fostered in the organization. Specifically, in this study, the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan expects reduced job strain and high employee performance due to the implications of ethical leadership practices and organizational compassion.

The fourth theory that this study utilises as a framework to examine is the affective events theory (Weiss and Cropanzano, 1996), which suggests that positive workplace events shape positive behaviour and additional positive energy. It creates an environment of ongoing emotional positive behaviour at the workplace. Effective events theory further suggests that these emotional and positive behaviours at the workplace build stable working situations over a period. Therefore, it is suggested based on affective events theory that compassion at work and an ethical leadership role may contribute to outcomes enhancement of individuals at the workplace.

Figure [3.1] shows the theoretical model of the research. This conceptual model resulted in four hypotheses that guided the research.

Figure 3. 1: Conceptual Model

Connection between theoretical and conceptual framework

As social science researchers begin with models, they progress to concepts that represent identified research questions within a subject matter. They then collect data to understand and establish connections between these concepts. Since concepts are the building blocks of theory, they become theoretical structures. Concepts can be measured, and measurement is an essential component of operationalization. To measure each concept, researchers identify indicators. There may be several indicators associated with each concept, and in this case the researcher must determine the relative weight of the indicators. It is not always clear what the difference is between a model and a theory (Sriraman & English, 2010). The purpose of a model is to describe a phenomenon and to embody a theory. The purpose of a model is to describe a phenomenon and to embody a theory. A model, on the other hand, is merely a description of a phenomenon as opposed than a theory, which can explain and predict it. Propositions or hypotheses are used to test theories using a methodology that is consistent with the model or theory. Strauss and Corbin (1994:278) state that "theory consists of plausible relationships based on concepts and sets of concepts." According to Puttergill (2000:19), theories are based on concepts, and certain aspects may therefore be considered as conceptual frameworks.

3.3 Hypothesis Development:

The following hypotheses were proposed for investigation considering the literature reviewed, the problem statement, and the research objectives.

3.3.1 Hypothesis

Ethical leadership occurs in the organization when leaders take an interest in developing good relationships with others (Franczukowska et al., 2021). Ethical leadership is a social exchange process involving the exchange of valued things (Bass and Riggio, 2006). According to Kante (2022), the use of ethical behaviour can work as an incentive and reward to influence the behaviour of employees. Ethical leadership is when leaders influence subordinates' behaviour to rectify their deviances (Cox, 2021).

Studies showed the link between ethical leadership and employee outcomes. Ismail, Zainuddin, and Ibrahim's (2010) research show a strong association between leadership style and

employee job fulfilment. Charles (2007) and Katherine (2007) also found a significant relationship between leadership styles transactional and ethical with the satisfaction of employees. Another study confirmed the substantial influence of organizational leadership on employee performance (Ofori and Toor, 2009). Research conducted by Resick et al. (2011) exhibited an essential connection between ethical leadership and employee improved behaviours.

The perception that a leader possesses moral and ethical values can influence employees' behaviour and commitment to their jobs and outcomes (Ruiz, Ruiz andMartínez, 2011a).

Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H-1. Ethical leadership has a positive impact on employee outcomes.

In contemporary research, an argument is made that the work environment that also includes ethical values is quite supportive and contributes to the well-being of people (Humphrey, Nahrgang, and Morgeson, 2007). Leaders in the organization strongly influence how the work is designed and the pressure taken by employees towards work (Wrzesniewski, Dutton, and Debebe, 2003). In addition to the work environment, the ethical leader also influences the way people experience workload tensions (Adıgüzel, Bhatti, and Öztürk, 2021). As the ethical leader is concerned with the well-being of employees, through his or her moral and social support, he or she helps the employees to deal with the job pressures. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H-2 Ethical leadership has an indirect and opposite influence on employees' level of job strain experienced.

A study conducted by Sprang, Clark, and Woosley (2007) concluded that compassion could significantly influence a person's performance and professional health. The education system at the Maharishi University of Management is recognized based on this principle. Moreover, in this regard, organizations actively participate in the commencement of seminars and workshops to enable employees to improve their performance and growth (Paais and Pattiruhu 2020). Several research streams recommend that workplace compassion is strongly connected with positive behaviour and improving outcomes for people (Nas, 2021; Zonash, Arouj, and Jamala, 2021; Balinbin et al., 2020). The most desirable and sentimental action at the workplace is to give and receive compassion for substantial results (Worline and Dutton, 2017). Feelings of connection with

one another increase when people receive compassion, generating many positive outcomes (Ling, Petrakis, and Olver, 2021). By reviewing these references, it is hypothesized that.

H-3 Organizational compassion moderates the influence of ethical leadership on employees' outcomes.

In some cases, compassion experienced at work depends more on workplace conditions than other situations (Eldor, 2018).

It is specified in research studies that compassion factors such as support, care, honour, and admiration of efforts made by people influence in a supportive way to exhibit encouraging behaviour towards job strain. It is also supported by a study that investigated individuals from diverse professional backgrounds who were experiencing compassion and felt a connection at work (Walumbwa et al., 2011). According to Subba and Rao (2016), compassion values can be essential to educating employees regarding their ethical and compassionate sources of energy, their organizational and personal life objectives, and how they can incorporate their efforts to achieve individual and professional goals. A study by Samaie and Farahani (2011) revealed that organizational compassion could moderate the relationship between rumination and job strain. On the bases of literature supported in this regard; it is therefore hypothesized that.

H-4 Organizational compassion moderates the impact of ethical leadership on employees' level of job strain experienced.

Alternative Theories

There are bunch of other theories that might be considered in support of theoretical framework these theories include three needs theory by David McClelland (1960) which states that needs for achievement, affiliation, and power affect the actions of people from a managerial context. Another theory in this context is two factor theory by Frederick Herzberg (1959). The two-factor theory is a concept that states the factors that affect an individual's behavior. These two factors are job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction. Theory X and theory Y by Douglas McGregor (1950) could be other consideration for developing conceptual frame work but these theories are not considered by the researcher because the main objective of the research is to investigate the

relationship between ethical leader and employee job strain and outcomes. And consideration of the theoretical support is focused from leadership perspective not the individual motivational perspective. Therefore, it is more appropriate to consider the theories that are supporting leadership effectiveness and influencing followers' behaviour instead of individuals personal motivation towards achievement of objectives.

3.4 Summary

Four fundamental theories found predominantly support the conceptual model of this research and the relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study.

According to social learning theory, employees may learn through observation and impersonating others who have a powerful influence on them (Gibson, 2004; Bandura, 1971; Zheng et al., 2015). Furthermore, they understand what is acceptable by analyzing the after-effects of people's actions, which supervisors frequently ascertain. Leaders in an organization can be effective role models for their followers because they have a solid impact on the participants and are responsible for assessing and enacting required behaviours (Babalola et al., 2018). Role modelling is a significant element of ethical leadership, and it is an inspirational, motivational dimension. Ethical leadership demonstrates a compassionate individual who exhibits suitable conduct and a moral leader who imposes good conduct. The application of social learning appears to be fitting for explaining the impact of ethical leadership on employee outcomes.

Social exchange process theory suggests that individuals make choices by balancing the risks and consequences of an association or reaction to increase their advantage (Homans, 1989). Social exchange theory is a good theoretical framework for studying if and how employees are encouraged to accomplish desired results under the influence of ethical leadership. As a result, it was hypothesized that social engagement aided the relationship between ethical leadership and employees' job strain and outcomes.

Expectancy theory has two perspectives in this research. The individual perspective and organizational perspective. This theory tells that an individual performs a job appropriately when motivated by the consequences of the task. This theory confirms that an individual can achieve desirable actions if inspirational factors are associated with them. From the individual perspective,

these inspirational factors came from ethical leadership, and the desired behaviour is the practical outcome. From an organizational perspective, when the company incorporates ethical leadership practices and organizational compassion, results like reduced job strain and improved employee outcomes are expected. So, the expectancy theory appropriately seems to support the current research from individual and organizational perspectives.

Affective events theory is a psychological model that explains the link between workplace emotional states and work performance, work satisfaction, and conduct. According to the theory of the effective event, these emotional and positive work behaviours help create stable working environments over time. To explain the influence of organizational compassion and ethical leadership as moderators and independent variables, the theory of the emotional event has been appropriately incorporated into the theoretical framework of this study.

Chapter 4

Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the methodology used to empirically test the hypothesis generated in this study. It explains the population of the research, sample method, data collection technique, data collection process, survey instruments and data analysis.

A researcher can select from various research designs to choose an appropriate methodology. They are, however, not purely unbiased research tools, as various approaches are frequently grounded in specific philosophies and ideologies (Scandura and Williams, 2000). Different approaches facilitate a researcher to address various types of inquiries and reach inferences from the study results (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2018). In this aspect, the type of research methodology selected influences the questions the research can provide answers to (Ates, 2008; Blaikie, 2003). According to Bryman and Cramer (2009), those who aim to develop a new theory and those who aim to test an existing theory use different methods for concept development and theory testing. Research objectives necessitate research designs to collect the required data for each objective. When selecting a suitable research design, the primary concern should be the research objective (Gaus, 2017; Arbnor and Bjerke, 2008).

It is important to note that the various methodological approaches are intended to answer specific research questions and represent an author's philosophical viewpoint (Bryman and Bell, 2015). According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016), a researcher's perspective is based on his or her research philosophy, which describes the way knowledge is conceptualised and the conclusions derived from that information.

Discussing the research philosophy is vital so the readers can assess and comprehend the study's findings. Ontological and epistemological stances are commonly used to introduce research philosophy. These are concerns related to the researcher's knowledge of the concept of truth (ontology) and understanding (epistemology) and thus establish the fundamental suppositions that affect the study (Crotty, 1998). These presuppositions affect not only what type of knowledge a researcher seeks to establish but also the methodology used to collect and analyse information that

has been recognised as credible (Gaus, 2017). The researcher's philosophical considerations influence the methodology chosen by the researcher's design (Arbnor and Bjerke, 2009).

This chapter is divided into three sections. It begins by discussing major research philosophies. A broader introduction of widely accepted ontological and epistemological positions and various research paradigms is presented, followed by a review of the research method. Second, following the research aim and purpose, it includes an explanation of the methods employed in this research. Third, it provides a detailed description of the research process and data analysis, as well as the sample and measures used in this research. The structure of the methodology chapter is presented in Figure [4.1].

Figure 4 1: Methodology Structure

4.2 Research Paradigm

Research is the scholarly study of phenomena, which aims to explore knowledge that is not known before and investigate new ideas to find information of one’s interest (Silverman, 2016). The term paradigm refers to the ideas (or beliefs) guiding our actions and how we view the world, which help us to determine and comprehend the relationships between things (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2009). As a broader framework, it encompasses diverse insights, beliefs, and perspectives that are incorporated into different practices and theories used in the research process (Hyde, 2000; Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2002). According to Kuhn (1962), the research paradigm can be defined as a set of common beliefs and agreements among researchers regarding how they see problems and how to solve them. In other words, their research questions are based on how they perceive the world and seek to answer them (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

Educational research uses the term "world view" for the paradigm. The worldview is the school of thought, set of shared beliefs, researcher's perspective, way of thinking and the conceptual lens through which the researcher interprets the world, and it is the whole scenario in which the research is developed (Adams and Lawrence, 2018). Researchers employ paradigms to determine what they are going to investigate, how they will investigate it, and how they will interpret their findings (Blanchflower, 2018).

Researchers use a variety of philosophical stances as guides for their research, primarily positivism, constructivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism (Goldstein, 2018). However, the debate on the superiority of each paradigm has continued, particularly between positivists and interpretivism. While proponents of the positivistic paradigm believed that their paradigm was the most suitable for research, interpretivism purists argued that their paradigm was more appropriate to the positivistic paradigm (Brierley, 2017; Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Part of the research base should be being able to explain the decision to accept or reject a theory. Therefore, it is critical to understand these paradigms, their origins, and fundamentals to determine which one is appropriate for a study. A research paradigm is a set of opinions related to the actuality of presence under research, which is also investigated in terms of ontology and epistemology. Research should scrutinise this since it affects the collecting and analysing of data.

4.2.1 Epistemology

In this school of thought, the issue is how information can be acquired and what appropriate information is (or should be) considered in a discipline (Ates and Bititci, 2008). As a means of understanding, it responds to questions beginning with 'how' and 'what' with the help of epistemology, imagination, observation, explanation, and even faith. The main epistemological perspectives are empiricism and constructivism, discussed here.

One of the two forms of fundamentalist philosophy is empiricism. Often it is associated with positivism, a school of thought that holds that information ought to be unbiased and free from personal views and opinions (Ryan, 2018). In positivism, theories (or research questions) derived from current science theories are tested against empirical understanding to determine whether they are accurate or reasonable (Bell, Bryman, and Harley, 2018). This philosophical approach has created a body of knowledge that other researchers can verify by using exact

quantitative measurements derived from statistical analysis. Positivism is generally associated with quantitative analysis and is a form of progression (Benton and Craib, 2010). Any knowledge that cannot be evaluated via experimentation and observation is thus denied, implying undetectable objects or occurrences are rejected from objectivist studies (Nind et al., 2013).

The second viewpoint, constructivism, see the world from the interpretive point of view and believes that good knowledge of fact can only be acquired through socialising with objects, thus opposing objectivist and empiricist opinions. The interpretive researcher is also seen as playing a considerable part in understanding and explaining the data obtained. It would also be accurate to assume that interpretation incorporates general interest into research and acknowledges individual differences (Moisander, Närvänen and Valtonen, 2020). They have an ontological perspective which is 'relativist.' Relativists argue that only collectively formed concepts make the truth known and that there is no single universal fact (Hackley, 2019). Unlike positivism, the use of qualitative research over quantitative or statistical research to derive the findings is stressed in the interpretive perspective.

4.2.2 Ontology

This metaphysical category (philosophy regarding the general principle of what things are) is concerned with the analysis of reality or with objects that demonstrate truth. It poses the question, 'What is?' Physical objects, thoughts, happenings, assets, beliefs, and ambiguous entities such as numbers and sets could all be considered abstract entities that constitute this universe's ontology (or inventory) (Limbaugh et al., 2020). For a deeper understanding of ontology, a researcher should examine the aspects of objectivism, constructivism, and pragmatism. Objectivism asserts that human experience and beliefs are empirical and that truth is determined by empirical evidence (Coşkun, 2020). The thoughts have not built them. If it is raining, for example, it is for real and will thus be known by any living person. Constructivism's philosophical position emphasises the development of the body of knowledge and the formation of notions because of individuals' interactions and decision-making.

In contrast to what we observe with objectivism, constructivism insists that truth relies on social characters or is created by them (Laurence and Rhoads, 2020). Pragmatism's point of view

focuses on the relationship between theory and reality. It argues that objectivism and constructivism are realistic and appropriate ways of approaching any science, and both can be used effortlessly to solve problems. The selection of ontological stance and its impact can be seen from the beginning of the research. It is reflected in research objectives and questions. If the researcher chooses an objective perspective, the questions focus on cause-and-effect analysis, whereas the subjective stance focuses more on people's viewpoints, perceptions and understanding of the phenomena. So, the selection of ontological stance plays a crucial role in research question selection.

4.2.3 Choice of Research Philosophy

This study's objective was to examine the association between ethical leadership and employee job strain and outcomes, which served as the basis for selecting an appropriate research paradigm to guide this study. The purpose was to test such connections and, hence required to use standard principles instead of acquiring detailed comprehension of the complicated concepts. This research demonstrates an objective ontology that believes the world comprises individual objective entities. Ethical leadership, employee job strain, and outcomes are associated with and arranged through basic laws that can be examined, validated, or disproved (Ates, 2008). Focusing on the connection between variables also conforms with empiricist epistemology, which requires thorough testing instead of rational theory building to obtain reliable knowledge. Therefore, this research adopts a positivist research paradigm. While initial positivism was primarily inductive, this study is deductive according to Popper's falsification principle. This involves positing a hypothesis or set of hypotheses and accepting them conditionally, not before they are proven false (Crotty, 1998). Therefore, the study aims to support or refute those hypotheses (Bryman and Cramer, 2009; Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Saunders, 2012)

The primary category in which this study falls is organisational behaviour. The significance of organisational behaviour research cannot be ignored because they respond to organisational problems by proposing behavioural strategies and actions in acquiring and disseminating knowledge for better productivity and outcomes (Griffin, Neal and Parker, 2007). Organisational behavioural research is encouraged to enhance the performance and effectiveness of organisations and human resource wellbeing (Leroy and Ramanantsoa, 1997). In such conceptualisations,

organisational behaviour researches are crucial and have significant potential to direct and suggest organisational strategies on a strategic and individual level to solve behavioural problems and overall organisational health (Templeton, Lewis and Snyder, 2002). As there is no universal research framework to investigate and measure in versatile organisational behaviour studies, organisational behaviour research scholars support using broadly divergent research techniques. However, the dominant objective of organisational behaviour research is to find and generate results; therefore, this research proposes positivism compared to interpretive and critical philosophy because of its benefits in terms of time-saving, validity and generalizability.

As a positivistic approach, it takes inspiration from Auguste Comte, who encouraged the investigation of social events as physical science-like phenomena. Similarly, this research also believes in the stance of scientific objectivity and argues that it is possible to investigate the human world objectively. With the stance that factual knowledge gained through sense, including facts, figures and measurement, is the only trustworthy knowledge in which the researcher's role is objective and very limited in data collection and interpretation (Halle, Switzer and Winkler, 2004). The research findings are measurable and observable and lead to statistical analysis, as the researcher is not involved subjectively in the study; therefore, there is no provision for human biases and interests. This research intended to proceed with a mind-independent reality assumption (Popkewitz, 2012), consider social events and the physical world parallel and assume that social phenomena can be studied as physical phenomena (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004).

This research supports that truth and knowledge are corresponding and believes in the theory of truth, which asserts that truth is in reality (Phillips and Burbules, 2000). Therefore, any report, research or statement would be considered authentic if related to referent reality. Also, if empirical methods are employed for verification, they would have more acceptability and reliability by reasonable people (Walker and Evers, 1999). This study agreed that statistical methods are essential for producing adequate knowledge and empirical procedure contributes significantly to the validity and reliability of the knowledge generated (Bamberger, 2000). This study believes that methodological approaches to the verification process should be used and assumes that these approaches are unbiased and do not impact what is being examined in such a way that positivist methodology is ideally suited for this study. Researchers should express themselves in the investigative process beyond ordinary and subjective definitions in value-

neutral, empirical language, resulting in objective and factual statements and laws about the environment (Park, Konge and Artino, 2020). In doing so, most people's knowledge is acceptable because it is based on facts and supporting numeric (Borsboom, Mellenbergh and Van Heerden, 2004). The positivistic approach is most appropriate for this study because it believes that empirical methods determine the validity of the structure of scientific research, so results are formulated, proven and checked. The positivistic approach follows the scientific pattern. The researcher generally starts by finding a new trend or research gap and poses it as an issue to be examined. Hypotheses are then proposed after further exploration, in which predictions are deduced. The researcher generally elucidated and presented the hypothesis as valid information if proven accurate. The information presented here was gathered through a process, as it was an objective representation of reality, as it had been rigorously empirically evaluated.

A realistic stance is not suitable for this research because the chances of biases towards findings are much higher, it is difficult to judge and explain role conflicts, it requires an extensive amount of time and money to complete research and most of all, it may receive expected response rather than actual knowledge or attitudes.

This study's objectives are highly compatible and aligned with positivistic applications that seek to determine the impact of one variable on others. Since it employs empiricism to organise and collect facts with a questionnaire and evaluate the outcomes, this study follows a positivistic paradigm.

4.3 Research Design

A research design is a collection of methods and techniques used to gather and analyse the variables identified in the research problem. The design of a study defines the study type (whether it is exploratory, descriptive, exploratory, co-relational or meta-analytic), research problem, variables (dependent and independent), data collection methods and statistical techniques. An effective research design is a step-by-step process that assists researchers in identifying and answering questions systematically, precisely, effectively, and efficiently (Kovera, 2010).

Research design can be described in broader categories of descriptive and explanatory research. Descriptive studies mainly find out "what is"? (Siedlecki, 2020). It also employs graphical representations, which assist the reader in understanding how the information is disseminated.

An individual's mind cannot absorb the entire import of an enormous amount of raw data; it helps obtain meaningful information by reducing the data to a manageable form. Descriptive statistics use data collection and analysis techniques that yield reports on prominent trends, variation, and correlation measurements. Description research is distinguished from other types of research by its characteristic summary and correlation statistics. In addition, it is distinguished by the specific type of research concerns, approaches, and conclusions it addresses (Nassaji, 2015). The three primary research purposes are to describe, interpret, and verify the findings. An exploration of creative possibilities leads to the description that organises conclusions so that they can be justified and then measured or validated (Leary, 2014).

Explanatory research is carried out to assist in identifying the issue that was not researched in detail before. Rather than providing definitive evidence, explanation research helps the researcher to understand a subject more effectively (Möttus et al., 2020). While conducting the study, the researchers consider the latest data and knowledge. Explanatory research gives the researcher an in-depth understanding of a precise topic that gives rise to more topics and provides more opportunities for researchers to analyse new things and ask about additional issues (Akhtar, 2016).

An exploratory study is defined as a study that investigates a problem that has not been identified. Detailed research is being conducted to understand the existing problem better, but the results will be inconclusive, and the results will be used to define specific problems for further research (Nardi, 2018). It is essential that the researcher is capable of changing course if new data or information becomes available. Typically, a study of this type is conducted at a preliminary stage where an issue has been identified. This approach is sometimes referred to as an interpretive analysis or grounded theory approach since it addresses questions such as what, why, and how (Yin, 2003).

Since the present research describes the relationship between variables and intends to explain the impact of one variable over other variables, this study is descriptive and explanatory. Additionally, this research aims at obtaining information about existing circumstances or situations for explanation and understanding. This type of research is known as descriptive research (Aggarwal, 2008).

This research gathers and tabulates facts and includes proper analyses, interpretations, comparisons, trend identification and relationships. This study provides valuable knowledge for solutions to local problems. This analysis is accurate and therefore provides actual knowledge. This study uses scientific method techniques through critical examination and review of source materials, analysis of data, generalisation, interpretation, and projection. The objectives of this study are stated earlier to identify 1) The impact of ethical leadership on employees' job strain and outcomes and 2) And if organisational compassion moderates the impact of ethical leadership on employees' work strain and outcomes.

4.3.1 Research approach, strategy, and method

A research approach is a systematically organised plan of action that directs individual thoughts and efforts, enabling the individual to conduct systematic and scheduled research to produce high-quality and comprehensive analysis (Saunders and Lewis, 2012). A research approach can be deductive or inductive, and its selection is also influenced by prior decisions, study objectives, limitations, and personal preferences (Azungah, 2018). The inductive method, also found as inductive reasoning, commences with observations, and ends with concepts presented at the end of the research process. Patterns, correlations, and regularities in experience are identified to draw conclusions or develop theory. An inductive approach is used when there is little evidence on a subject which follows a pattern from particular to general (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Commonly, this approach is used for qualitative studies, the interview method is selected, and data can then be analysed for correlations between respondents (Power et al., 2018).

The deductive approach to science appears to move from generic to specific Any researcher who employs deductive reasoning will begin with the school of thought and progress to study objectives, which are then validated through data gathering (Kothari, 2004). The deductive

method builds the hypothesis on an existing school of thought and then develops the evaluation methodology to assess it (Silverman, 2016). Ultimately, conclusions resulting from the data obtained will either validate or falsify the research question or hypothesis. The deductive approach is especially suited to the positivism philosophy, as it permits the conceptualisations of propositions and statistical testing of possible results to an agreed level of probability (Snieder and Larner, 2009). However, with qualitative research methods, a deductive method can also be used, but in these contexts, the suppositions engendered by prior research will be developed differently than those generated by hypothesis testing (Saunders and Lewis, 2012). Quantitative research requires a deductive approach, whereas qualitative research is often related to an inductive method.

This study followed a deductive approach because of these reasons. Deductive reasoning allows the researcher to develop a hypothesis from propositions of established theory and then test that hypothesis (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). As clear from the word deductive, it is deducing meaning/knowledge from propositions, particular to general phenomena. If the causal relationship is tested under a specific theory, it might be true in many situations, enhancing generalizability (Adcock, 2001). The deductive approach follows anticipated patterns and is tested against observations, while induction begins with observation and seek to develop pattern afterwards (Babbie, Wagner and Zaino, 2018). The deductive approach is advantageous when the causal relationship between concepts and variables is explained, along with the possibility of generalizability and measuring variables in a quantitative pattern (Ryan, 2018). A considerable advantage is that within a short time, the researcher can complete investigations and generate findings (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2006).

The research strategy for this dissertation was developed by adopting a way in which the research objectives could be addressed. A deductive approach is used in this study, in which hypotheses are derived from existing theories and data is collected in order to verify the hypotheses (O'Reilly, 2009). The survey strategy used in this study is a popular and widely accepted strategy in management research that is usually associated with the deductive research approach and is effective for collecting a large amount of data cost-effectively (Saunders et al., 2019). It is a well-known and conventional business and management methodology. Sometimes used to respond to who, what, where how much, and how many questions. As a result, it does seem to be used in exploratory and descriptive research. In this study, survey research was chosen for presenting a

population and describing the relationships between variables which allowed the study's objectives to be met. Accordingly, the quantitative method was chosen as an appropriate research method to achieve the aims and goals of the research by effectively measuring and analysing the relationship between ethical leadership, employee job strain, outcomes, and organisational compassion. The community views the survey technique as conclusive and relatively straightforward to characterise and fully understand. As an additional benefit of survey data collection, possible explanations for specific relationships among variables can be suggested, and models of such relationships can be generated. If a research design is used, more flexibility can be allowed over the survey's conduct, and the costs can be reduced when sampling is used to obtain outputs representative of the general population.

The research purpose, objectives and questions direct the research methods and data required (Williams, 2007). In this study, the variables were viewed as observable phenomena accommodating to behavioural regulations and hence generalisation, which was just according to the positivistic epistemological stance. Positivism holds that knowledge can and should be produced objectively, which means that throughout data collection, the researcher must remain objective and avoid interacting with respondents (Buchanan and Hvizdak, 2009). This can be accomplished by implementing strictly defined study protocols that minimise researcher bias as much as possible.

There are two main types of research methods: qualitative and quantitative. The qualitative approach to science is characterised by interpreting the question from a humanistic or idealistic perspective. Qualitative research focuses on studying the opinions, perceptions, beliefs, attitudes, and communication of individuals. As a method of evaluating human behaviour, qualitative research was initially applied in psychology when researchers found it difficult to evaluate human behaviour with numerical data. Until then, it was used in other fields of research. A quantitative test is a method by which numerical data is collected to measure the problem through a statistical method that is available to the general public. In addition to measuring actions, beliefs, behaviours, and other specific variables, this technique can also be used to generalise findings from a larger sample.

A quantitative approach aims to understand the social environment and create awareness. Social scientists use quantitative research to understand phenomena and occurrences that affect individuals. Social scientists are concerned with analysing people. Quantitative analysis refers to the method of analysing a particular population of individuals, known as a sample population. Based on empirical research, a quantitative analysis is carried out using data that has been analysed or calculated to answer questions about the participant population.

An efficient way to test the hypothesis is using the quantitative method, which is the most widely used and crucial frame of investigation in empirical research (Black, 1999). Using the quantitative method, data is analysed systematically and comes up with quantitative findings as results, conclusions, and recommendations (Elqayam, Bonnefon and Over, 2018). To generate reliable results and meaningful conclusions for this study, a quantitative approach is projected that does include statistical techniques and numerical data usage (Johnson and Turner, 2003). A quantitative approach presents results that are most appropriate to the business and expert community (Samani, 2018). Morris (2008) argues that the quantitative approach is the most appropriate framework for empirical investigation. In the quantitative approach, objective data is used to observe statistical facts and outcomes. The standardisation of each stand in quantitative research facilitates the reduction of bias in the analysis of data (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2012). Quantitative approaches are based on numerical facts, so the results produced are reliable and generalizable (Payne and Williams, 2005).

This study followed a quantitative approach. Therefore, it aims to explain the phenomenon and development of the hypothesis through deductive reasoning in which quantitative data is gathered, hypotheses are tested, and results are generated so that meaningful conclusions can be made by analysing variables included in the central construct of the study. As this study is correlational and investigates relationships among variables, a quantitative approach and deductive reasoning is the most suitable approach for this study. Also, a quantitative approach is most appropriate to reduce biases, control errors and exclude unwanted influences (Khemlani, 2018). This approach is also very suitable as respondents may feel hesitant in the interview to answer the questions related to job strain and their behaviour, so the questionnaire method is more appropriate for this research (Lund, 2012).

Quantitative methods generate numerical information, regarded as a consistent and formalised method of depicting empirical data (Neuman et al., 2013). The data could then be statistically analysed with descriptive and inferential statistics, allowing for replication and generalisation (Eyisi, 2016). When compared to other quantitative techniques, such as observation and interviews, this study made better use of time and money by using structured questionnaires. Questionnaires are also helpful in gathering sensitive information because they permit participant confidentiality and minimise researcher bias which further facilitates adhering to the principle of scientific rigour stipulated by the deductive method by keeping the research non-participated (Saunders et al., 2019). According to Saunders et al. (2019), it is critical to have clarity on the examined phenomenon prior to the data collection process. The phenomenon of job strain in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector had been entirely ignored, so it was critical to investigate the potential application of health-related distress concerning business organisations. Likewise, the limited studies on compassion and lack of evidence also made it inevitable to explore it and get the detailed connection of variables.

4.4.1 Research Population

This study aims to examine the influence of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes and determine the significance of organisational compassion as a moderator in this relationship in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan. Islamic banking plays a significant role in generating employment and economic growth in Pakistan, therefore conducting research in this area is crucial. Twenty-two Islamic banks are operating in Pakistan; branches have been selected in Lahore, Islamabad, Rawalpindi, Multan, and Faisalabad. The population of this study was the employees of the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan, particularly senior, front line and middle-level employees. The foremost reason for selecting these level positions employees was the presence of probably more encounter the job strain than clerical staff as Senaratne and Rasagopalasingam's (2017) study found more overall strain at work in these levels in comparison to administrative staff.

4.4.2 Sampling

An analysis of a larger population based on a predetermined number of observations is called sampling. It depends on the type of study conducted and how a broader population is

sampled. In research, a sample refers to a collection of individuals, artefacts, or objects chosen from a larger group for analysis.

A representative sample should be drawn from the population so that the results can be generalised from the sample to the whole population. The population contains all items, while the sample is just a portion of the population. There are several explanations for why we are not attempting to deal with populations. The population is usually huge, and it is impossible to generate data from the whole population. Furthermore, data collection is costly, so the higher the sample, the greater the cost. There are various methods for selecting a sample of participants, including some that attempt representative sampling and others that constitute a settlement on this optimal outcome of sampling (Blaikie, 2003, p. 199). There are two categories: probability sampling, which aims for accurate representations of the population, and non-probability sampling, which generally compromises on population representation (Phellas, Bloch and Seale, 2011).

Within probability, sampling comes stratified sampling (which divides the population into groups known as strata. For example, the population could be split into males and females. From each of these strata, a sample is collected), simple random sampling in which sample participants are chosen by chance but with a defined selection probability. Random sampling is the same as putting everyone else's names in a hat and going to draw many names. Every factor in the population gets an equal opportunity of occurring. While this is the most common type of sampling, it is still difficult to execute. It entails compiling a complete list of every item in the population. Lastly, cluster sampling is a probability sampling methodology that divides the number of individuals into many sample units. Using a basic random sampling technique or systematic random sampling technique, researchers select random groups for data gathering. Cluster sampling is accomplished by grouping the population, most territorially based. These units are referred to as Blocks or Clusters. The clusters are selected randomly, and each item will be included in the chosen clusters.

Samples selected by convenience, purposive, snowball or quota are non-probability samples. A convenience sample is one in which individuals are sampled because they are researchers' "efficient and easy" data sources. The purposive sample is a non-probability sample selected according to the characteristics of the study population and the purpose of the study. In

contrast to convenience sampling, purposive sampling can also be referred to as selected, subjective, or judgmental sampling.

A snowball sampling method is a convenient way to collect samples. This method is utilised when locating subjects with the required characteristics is difficult. The method involves recruiting future research subjects from the social circle of the current study subjects. Sampling will continue until the data is saturated. According to Palinkas et al. (2013), this method, also widely recognised as the "chain method," is efficient and reliable for reaching people who would otherwise be challenging to reach. As a result of the snowball method, not only does the researcher save time, but they can also communicate with the samples more effectively. This is because they are familiar with the first sample, and the first sample is associated with the researcher. People who are reluctant to reveal their identities can be located through this type of networking (Bazen, Barg and Takeshita, 2021). This approach is encouraged by Buchanan et al. (1988), who assert that gaining access is more likely successful where you can use existing contacts. The snowball sampling strategy entails the researcher initially contacting a particular group of people and using their sources to approach new residents, i.e. sample of the study (Bryman and Cramer, 2009).

Snowball sampling can be applied to both quantitative and qualitative research, producing more accuracy than traditional probability sampling when emphasising or observing interpersonal relationships. As a result, there are enough prior precedents to consider snowball sampling appropriate for this research. The rationale for using the snowball sampling method is based on the facilitation of reaching the respondents. There are several advantages of the snowball sampling technique. A significant advantage is the availability of data. Data can be obtained in a facilitated way, and it saves precious time. This technique would allow data collection to take a much shorter than other methods. This is because an exhaustive analysis of the whole population does not need to be done, so it is also cost-effective. Snowball sampling allows primary data to be collected about the subject. These results can be used as guides, which can help with further intervention in the decision.

4.4.3 Procedure

The procedure chosen for this research was consistent not only with the positivist approach but also with the purpose and objectives of the research. The research paradigm links philosophy

and methodology (Arbnor and Bjerke 2009). The methodology is primarily determined by the paradigm once it has been identified and selected. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the methodology after the paradigm has been recognised and chosen because it must be consistent as an approach to the paradigm (Creswell, 2021; Collis and Hussey, 2013). Positivism is mainly associated with the studies conducted quantitatively, which employ surveys and interpretations following an empiricist epistemology to evaluate theories and examine the relationships (Crotty, 1998). Research into leadership and employee outcomes is predominantly based on survey-based quantitative studies.

Continuing to follow tradition, this study employs approaches and methods like that found in previous studies. In line with existing literature, this study employs a sample-survey approach to data collection via online questionnaires. In several ways, this method corresponds to the suppositions of positivist epistemology. To begin, according to the general laws, a sample survey represents a portion of the total population. Compared to other research approaches, such as experimental or field research, the sample survey provides greater generalizability and facilitates generalisation from the sample to the whole population (McGrath, 1981). An essential characteristic of positivism is a generalisation.

A structured questionnaire enabled the researcher to gather data from a wide range of participants, but it restricted the variety of possible responses, resulting in a trade-off between accuracy and the number of responses (Patton, 1990). It aims to quantify the ideas embodied within the conceptual model, which serves as the foundation for the formulation of hypotheses and evaluation of them. It is undeniable that the positivistic paradigm is consistent with a focus placed on empirical evaluation.

The closed-ended questions and Likert scale responses produce formalised data that can be examined using statistical methods. The measuring instruments and method are decided mainly by published studies and leave no choice for the researcher's viewpoints and opinions on the research. The goal of a survey design is not to intrude on the occurrences but to capture an overview of what is going on (Arnold, 1982; Crano, Brewer and Lac, 2014). Having followed this reasoning, using a quantitative method within positivistic research appeared to be an appropriate option for this research.

Although the author of this research is the primary investigator, the lead supervisor was also a prominent member of the research team. The primary investigator's responsibility in processing and examining primary data included defining eligibility standards for appropriate associations, choosing the investigation tools, conversing with the organisations, carrying out data evaluation and assessment, and interpreting the data. The lead supervisor's role was primarily recommendatory, providing feedback on all the tasks performed by the researcher.

Considering the context and population of this research, which was the Islamic banks of Pakistan, the sample was taken from Pakistan's top five cities, covering the entire Punjab region. In the first stage, the list of leading Islamic Banks in Pakistan is made from the list provided by the State Bank of Pakistan. At present, there are a total of 22 leading Islamic banks operating in Pakistan. These banks have over 3000 branches all over Pakistan and more than 1000 branches in the top five cities, including Islamabad, Rawalpindi, Lahore, Multan and Faisalabad. In the second stage, Lahore, Islamabad, Multan, Rawalpindi and Faisalabad-based branches of Islamic Banks were contacted and sent online questionnaires. In the third stage, questionnaires were delivered to 500 employees, including front-line, middle-level, and senior-level, and 255 responses were received, representing a 50% response rate. Participants had to answer every question, so only those questionnaires completed in response were selected for the next stage. This resulted in 210 responses in total. While screening for outliers, ten responses were rejected. The overall sample was 200 responses.

4.4.4 Justification of the sample size

A critical component of designing an empirical study is justifying the sample size. As part of a sample size justification, it is imperative to explain how the collected data will provide valuable information according to the inferential objectives of the study. The researcher employed the theory of item scale by (Heir et al, 2014) to determine the sample size. According to item scale theory, 5 responses per question in a questionnaire represent an appropriate sample size. In this case, the research consists of 37 questions in a total of four questionnaires. This resulted in 185 responses. A total of 500 questionnaires were sent out in the context of the poor research culture in Pakistan and the Covid-19 situation at the time of data collection.

The researcher chose snowball, a non-probability sampling technique, for data collection. The projected sample size was 500 participants, but only 255 responses were received because of factors that were beyond the researcher's control. This shows 50 percent response rate. After excluding unfinished responses 200 questionnaires were finalized for further analysis. It is important to note here that at this level data was saturated and no new information was generating therefore, this sample size considered to be appropriate for further data analysis. Even though the sample size in the current study may not be fully representative of the Islamic banking sector in Pakistan's five major cities, this does not lessen the accuracy of the results or invalidate any conclusions. Instead, a larger number of samples may simply reveal more findings.

The Covid-19 worldwide online questionnaire survey was the most appropriate technique to adopt. The data was collected from May to August 2021. Traditionally, research data collection has been done using paper and pencil, but this has been time-consuming and expensive. It frequently entails visiting institutions (fieldwork) to ensure that data gathering is completed correctly. It may require that the researcher access employees and students who can assist with data collection. Conducting online surveys is an alternative. These look to have the ability—and are being utilised worldwide—to collect massive amounts of data quickly and effectively. Even while educational researchers are just beginning to collect data online, there are already several advantages. Although online data collecting is underutilised for this purpose, Mertler (2002) noted that compared with the more conventional method of obtaining information from the student, teacher, and parent, it is an effective and practical way to do so. Online surveys are time and money efficient since they promise to collect responses in a relatively short amount of time. Researchers can also access a sizable, diversified, and international population via the Internet, which has the potential to accumulate enormous volumes of data. According to academics, online data collection also safeguards against data loss and makes it easier to put data into a database for analysis.

This study followed the recommendations of Podsakoff et al. (2003) in attempting to enhance the target population's responses. Also, employees were made aware that their responses were utterly anonymous to decrease the risk of biases in the answers. Respondents were informed that participating in the research was voluntary. This information was noted on the questionnaires.

4.5 Validity, Reliability and Generalizability of Research

In a quantitative study, validity refers to the accuracy with which a concept is measured. Research must be both reliable and valid in order to be considered credible. For example, the scale is trustworthy because it consistently reports the same weight daily. Validity is a judgement based on different types of scientific proof. The current study's validity was established early when the researcher decided on the data collection method. The researcher ensured that the measurement techniques were high quality and targeted the research aims and objectives. The current study is thorough and founded on existing knowledge. The research results provide evidence that the data support the theoretical framework. The current research is valid and reliable because it is based on a robust research design. It relies on an appropriate research methodology and sample and has been conducted carefully and consistently.

Research in social sciences has been heavily influenced by the positivist tradition, which strongly polarised the concept of generalizability (Ormston et al., 2014; Flyvbjerg, 2001). Natural sciences, which are fundamentally descriptive, have unquestionably dominated Western culture, highlighted instrumental rationality, and emphasised generalisability (Winter, 2000). A primary objective of quantitative research, as described by the positivist tradition, is to create laws that can describe and control all observations and to establish a fundamental truth that is constant throughout time and space (Delmar, 2010; Falk et al., 2009). In this context, generalizability is the core of value, as Morse (2008) has highlighted. Therefore, quantitative techniques have been used as a method of testing hypotheses and drawing inferences with the assumption that the researcher is unbiased and objective (Falk, Rocha, and Warnick, 2009).

Also, to restrict any potential elements of bias in the study procedure (Davies and Dodd, 2002). The generalisable conclusions are based on an in-depth research process that adheres to methodological rigour. In the positivist tradition, a study's rigour is determined by how it was planned, collected, analysed, and reported (Marquart, 2017). A reliable and valid measurement, such as the assessment of objective scores, can be used to replicate results from one study and generalise them to other studies (Claydon, 2015). According to Polit and Beck (2010), probabilistic generalisation is used in quantitative research to generalise results based on samples representative of the entire population. In quantitative approaches, statistical generalizability remains a

fundamental principle (Winter, 2000). It has been argued, however, that convenience sampling bias undermines the reliability of research (Gheondea-Eladi, 2014).

An essential consideration for determining credibility in quantitative research is external validity, which covers the degree to which causality can be inferred between two factors (Bryman, Becker, and Sempik, 2008). Generalizability refers to external validity, which only incorporates the probabilistic implication of the original concept (Flyvbjerg, 2001; Lee and Baskerville, 2003). Thus, positivist approaches have driven generalizability, and their quantitative impact has been established.

The quantitative nature of this study lends credence to its results since it relies on statistics for the generation and analysis of data. The reliability and objectivity of quantitative data are generally considered to be higher. Evidence of validity and reliability is required to ensure that a measurement instrument is valid and reliable (Kimberlin and Winterstein, 2008). Because the current study ensures the data are sound and reproducible, and the results are accurate, it is a reliable and valid study. The scales used in this research are valid and reliable and have an established reputation.

The generalizability of research findings has long been thought to be the exclusive domain of quantitative research. The preference of an appropriate and random sample, as well as the correlation of the study population with the sample, are methods that enable the quantitative study results to be transferred to the study population and to similar populations. This research aims to test ethical leadership theory and transfer acquired knowledge. As part of this research, demographic characteristics are used to ensure the comparability of the sample with the study population. Since the demographic variables in the randomly selected sample are like those in the population, it is reasonable to assume that the findings from the sample will be similar to those of the entire population if the entire population is studied. During the data analysis, there was a focus on ensuring that the theory is comprehensive, the data collected is complete, saturated, and that negative cases are taken into account. Knowledge gained from the theory was applicable to all scenarios that might be observed in a larger population. It applies to all similar situations, questions, and problems, regardless of the demographic composition of the groups. The theory can also be applied beyond this immediate group.

Based on the positivist tradition, this research seeks to develop universal knowledge (Delmar, 2010) that always holds true in all places and (Falk et al., 2009) and is invariable in all circumstances. Therefore, quantitative experimental methods have been employed to test hypotheses and infer generalizable conclusions by exercising an impartial and objective researcher's involvement (Winter, 2000) to limit any possible forms of influence in the research process (Davies & Dodd, 2002). As a result of a rigorous methodological approach to the research process, generalizable conclusions have been reached.

4.6 Survey Instrument

The scales utilised in this study have been used in previous research and have published psychometric data. However, Brace et al. (2009) advise assessing the dependability of scales, whether they are created or already exist. Adequate validity needs to be a priority, and internal consistency determines if a scale truly measures what it claims to measure (Kline, 2000). The most popular and widely accepted internal consistency measurement is Cronbach's alpha (Boateng et al., 2018). The Cronbach alpha coefficient is advised not to drop below 0.7 Boateng et al., (2018). Every scale used in this study has a Cronbach alpha of more than 0.7. As a result, the instruments' internal consistency and reliability were deemed adequate. For the negative effect sub-scale, earlier studies in related contexts also discovered lower alpha values; a Cronbach alpha of 0.65 was observed Wong et al., (2011), implying that the low-reliability level may be a result of the instrument's design. It may also be worth mentioning that for scales with fewer items (10 or less), Cronbach alpha tends to be low; accordingly, an alpha of 0.6 is considered acceptable for scales of less than ten items (Ursachi et al., 2015; Loewenthal and Lewis, 2018).

4.6.1 Questionnaire

This study has employed a structured questionnaire as a primary tool for data collection. According to Baker and Wilson (2000); Bryman and Cramer (2004), for studies measuring or quantifying concepts to present the results numerically to the world, the questionnaire is a more appropriate method. The questionnaire technique is a technique in which the respondent is asked to respond to the same set of predetermined questionnaires in an organised and determined order. For getting meaningful data when the population is large, observations are not easy to make, and

the research objectives are exploratory, then the best choice is the survey method (Oso and Onen, 2008).

In order to minimise the risk of bias, the most effective way is to use questionnaires to collect the information (Zikmund et al., 2003). As this study investigates the personal experiences of respondents, so the anonymous nature of the questionnaire is a more appropriate approach to use so that respondents may feel free to answer the questions. In order to work according to the context of the study, closed questions are incorporated in the questionnaire related to ethical leadership, organisational compassion, employee strain and employee outcomes. The essential study variables are engaged with 1 to 5 Likert scales so the respondents could point out their experiences with the investigated variables. The questionnaire is designed to gather basic information before moving on to questions that probe deeply into the perceptions of ethical leadership, job strain, emotions when beginning to experience organisational compassion, and impacts on achievement.

The instrument measuring source for organisation compassion is the questionnaire developed by the University of Michigan at the compassion lab centre (Worline and Dutton, 2017). Employee outcomes are adopted from Wideower (2001), and Ethical leadership is measured by a scale adopted from (Brown, Treviño and Harrison, 2005). Job Strain is measured by an instrument developed by (Parker and DeCotiis, 1983).

As the population is literate and the English language is the second most spoken language in Pakistan, the information through a questionnaire (in English) approach is comfortable to adopt. This study instrument contains 37 questions/items that measure ethical leadership, organisational compassion, and job strain and outcomes. To produce reliable results, quantitative research should at least yield five responses to each question/item (Hair Jr et al., 2014). The instrument for this study contains 37 questions/items and therefore needs to obtain approx—185 (37*5) responses from the respondents. A sample size of 185-190 respondents reduces error chances to 5% (Niles, 2006). In this scenario, the numbers of responses (200-210) are appropriate and suitable for the study.

4.6.2 Ethical leadership

The ethical leadership scale was adapted from Brown, Trevino and Harrison's (2005) used in this study. It consisted of 10 items. All parameters of ethical leadership were assessed using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, with 1 being strongly disagreed and 5 strongly agreeing. This scale is reliable, easy to respond and has also been used in other research, such as Piccolo et al. (2010); Newman et al. (2014); Zhu et al. (2015); Schaubroeck et al. (2012); and Tu and Lu (2016) and as well to generate reliable and authentic results (Stevison, Dent and White, 2009).

4.6.3 Organisational compassion

The instrument measuring source for organisation compassion is a questionnaire developed at the compassion lab centre, the University of Michigan (Worline and Dutton, 2010), with a 5-point Likert scale that ranges from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree. Participants were asked how often they had encountered compassion at work, from their line manager and coworkers, using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (very always). Although this scale does not distinguish between individual and collective compassion feelings, it was deemed the most appropriate for this study. This was justified in the absence of scales that make a clear distinction. The difficulty of making a clear distinction was exacerbated by the fact that this study was designed to provide a general assessment of organisational compassion rather than to investigate how compassion manifests after an incident. Additionally, this may explain why most research on organisational compassion has been qualitative and focused on single incidents of suffering (Dutton et al., 2006; Simpson et al., 2015; Peticca-Harris, 2018). The scale selected has been tested in several studies by Lilius et al. (2008), Chu (2016); Moon et al. (2014); Hur et al. (2016) and was found to have satisfactory reliability ($\alpha=0.79$).

4.6.4 Job strain

Job Strain is measured by an instrument developed by (Parker and DeCotiis, 1983). This study's instrument had a 5-point Likert - type scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." A while back, this occupational strain measurement was used by (Wickramasinghe, 2012).

4.6.5 Employee outcome

The employee outcomes measurement tool is adopted (Wiedower, 2002). All dimensions of employee outcomes are evaluated on a five-point Likert scale extending from (strongly disagree

to strongly agree). The instrument is reliable and has been recently used by Varshney and Varshney (2017). An example of the question – dimensions were "Quality of work," Quantity of Work." Alpha value reliability is 0.699.

4.7 Ethical Considerations

It is the responsibility of the researcher to abide by ethical guidelines that are set out by their institution and that relate to the participants of the research. First, the UWS ethics committee provided permission for the survey to be conducted. Second, the researcher ensured that participant confidentiality was maintained during the entire study. It was necessary to obtain the consent of the participants and key members of the organizations in this regard. Participants in the survey were informed of the research objectives prior to conducting the survey. In every aspect of research, it is the researcher's responsibility to assess the possibility of harm to any participant and to minimize it.

In conducting research, ethical considerations correspond to what is morally and ethically acceptable (Arbnor and Bjerke, 2009). Following Tracey (2017), Gaus categorises ethical conduct into three types: procedural ethics, which address the prevention of harm, privacy, and free will. Applied ethics is related to the study framework, which pertains to the confidentiality and privacy of participants. According to UWS's Code of Practice on Research Ethics, this research incorporates all three categories of ethical considerations. The company consented to allow access to its employees for the objective of this study. Voluntary participation is a critical ethical issue (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Employees and managers were free to choose whether to participate in this survey, even though it was distributed via the workplace email system (Frankfort-Nachmias and Nachmias, 1992). Participants were free to withdraw from the study at any time without providing any reason. After all the relevant aspects of the research have been discussed with participants, it is essential to obtain confirmation of their consent to generate knowledge. Therefore, the researcher has taken care of all ethical aspects in this regard.

Research ethics discussions involve a number of different topics. The most significant ethical concerns in research can also be grouped into four critical considerations (Diener and Crandell, 1978).

1. Harm to participants

In any aspect of research, the researcher is responsible for assessing the possibility of harm to participants and minimizing it (Doloriert and Sambrook, 2009). Participant confidentiality and anonymity are at the center of this issue. Anonymity and confidentiality of research participants should be respected, in accordance with the AOM (2004) code of ethics. This means that individuals and organizations must maintain the confidentiality of their identities and records upon request. It is essential for researchers to take great care and responsibility when publishing the results of their research. In the present study, the data collection method used is the survey, which is a quantitative approach. The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between stated variables and ethical leadership so that possible solutions to issues such as strain and performance enhancement can be found. The findings of this study are expected to be useful to a wide audience. Additionally, there is no risk to the research participants.

2. Privacy attacks?

The investigation should be conducted in a manner that does not violate the tenet's privacy. Researchers are not allowed to violate the privacy of the participants as part of the purpose of the research. The ethical code of conduct provides clear guidance. Participants' privacy must be protected at all times by researchers, and they must respect their values. As mentioned in the first question, the privacy issue is related to the confidentiality of the participant. It is important to maintain the confidentiality of the personal information of participants. It is important for the researcher to carefully consider whether and to what extent it is permissible to record the private information of participants during the research process. This issue is sensitive in some cases and less so in others. For instance, when a researcher is dealing with photographs or other sensitive information, it may become more sensitive. As this study focuses on leadership practices and their impact on job strain and outcomes, there is minimal involvement of private information about participants. To ensure the privacy of participants' data is collected anonymously, and all the data/information obtained from participants is secured in password-protected files.

3. Lack of informed consent?

Informed consent is the process by which participants in research are informed of the goals and objectives of the study (Riese, 2019). They are asked whether they are willing to participate in the study. It is both an ethical and legal requirement that participants confirm their willingness to participate in an investigation once they have been informed of all aspects of the study. This is for the advancement of welfare and the generation of knowledge. Research involving human participants must obtain informed consent to be conducted. By providing informed consent, researchers inform the participants about their rights, the objectives and aims of the investigation, the expected benefits associated with the research, the anticipated completion date for the research, the procedure, as well as possible risks associated with the research. By providing these details, participants will not only be able to gain a better understanding of the significance of the research but will also be able to make an informed decision regarding whether to participate in it.

The UWS ethical code of conduct requires that participants in research processes be fully informed prior to their participation. When participants are not given a full explanation of the research process and its implications, informed consent may not be obtained. To obtain the satisfactory consent of participants in the research, the information about the study, including its purpose, objectives, and purpose, the research benefits, procedures adopted for ensuring data protection/confidentiality/, as well as the length of time personal data will be stored, were presented to participants.

4. Involvement of deception

The term deception in research refers to researchers intentionally misrepresenting the study's purpose and concealing details that may influence respondents' decisions (Tourish, 2019). It is necessary to avoid deception as much as possible as part of the UWS ethical code of conduct. To avoid any deception in the investigation process, this study provides participants with details about the research process. This was accomplished by sending participants a letter explaining all the necessary details in order to win their confidence.

4.8 Statistical Analysis

Statistical data analysis is a method of executing various statistical procedures. Descriptive data, such as surveys and qualitative data, are commonly found in quantitative data. Statistical methods include preparing, designing, collecting, analysing, interpreting, and presenting data accurately. It is all about using the proper techniques for statistical analysis, which is how we organise and collect data to discover trends and patterns. In order to present the findings effectively, the researcher needs to be aware of the proper techniques to collect data, use a suitable methodology, and use the proper statistical analysis. Our ability to make scientific discoveries, make data-driven decisions, and make forecasts is greatly influenced by statistics. This analysis has five choices: mean, standard deviation, regression, hypothesis test and sample size determination.

Some of the most common and reliable statistical methods for quantifying such comparisons are the F-test, t-test and regression analysis.

An **F-statistic** of approximately one is calculated under the null hypothesis by combining two nearly equivalent quantities. Having a high F-value is essential for rejecting the null hypothesis. A high F-value (one that exceeds the critical F value in a table) indicates that something is of substantial importance, whereas a small p-value indicates that everything is significant.

T-tests are inferential statistics used to determine whether specific characteristics of two groups are significantly different. In statistics, the t-test is among the methods for testing hypotheses. They are called t-tests because each t-test reduces the data of the sample reduced to one number, the t-value.

Regression analysis is a powerful method that facilitates the analysis of the association between relevant factors. Despite the many different types of regression analysis, they all focus on the impacts of an independent variable on the dependent variable. Usually, a regression analysis is conducted to forecast the change in the dependent variable levels for participants for whom data on the independent variables is accessible or to evaluate the influence of any defining factor on the analysed variable.

There are two elementary categories of regression. One is linear regression, and the other is multiple regression.

Linear regression analysis is a linear process for estimating the association between one or more independent variables (or independent variables) and a scalar response (or dependent variable). The instance of one descriptive variable is referred to as simple linear regression. Simple linear regression is a mathematical means of getting a formula to determine the values of one variable from another where the two variables have a causal association. The formula for a straight line is the most fundamental to simple linear regression. Regression analysis can determine which variables are crucial, which factors can be left unconsidered, and their interactions.

Multiple Regression Analysis is a linear regression extension. It is used when we want to estimate a variable's value based on two or more other variables. The variable we would like to evaluate is considered the dependent variable. The multiple regression analysis is a statistical tool that allows researchers to determine the significance and strength of relationships between outcomes (the dependent variable) and predictors, frequently after removing the influence of other variables.

Relationships between variables are generated through linear and multiple regression analysis. A statistical analysis of this study is conducted using SPSS 21. An alpha test, or Cronbach's alpha, is used to determine the reliability of the instrument that is employed in this study. The Kenny and Ledermann (2010) suggest running simple linear regressions for testing influences and multiple regressions for testing moderation.

Data Collection

Using personal contacts, the researcher established contact with senior executives in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan. Contacts were established in five major cities of Pakistan, namely Islamabad, Lahore, Rawalpindi, Faisalabad, and Multan. In selecting these cities, the researcher carefully considered the fact that they represent the top cities in Pakistan in terms of Islamic banking operations. There are more than 1000 Islamic banks in these cities on average. Since these cities represent the largest percentage of Islamic banking operations in terms of employees, a sample from these branches was appropriate. A formal email was then sent to the first contacts. As part of the email, the study aims were explained, the length of time expected to complete the survey, a confidential web address was provided, and assurance was given that the questionnaires were 100% anonymous and non-traceable. Online questionnaires were used since

they provide easy and quick access to participants and are convenient for automated data collection (Wright, 2005; Buchanan & Hvizdak, 2009).

The questionnaires were provided through an online survey tool (Google form) that allowed respondents to access the questionnaire via their mobile phone or computer. A web-based questionnaire facilitates the creation and distribution of online surveys, as well as exporting responses to statistical software packages (Wright, 2005). The survey was also designed in a way that allowed respondents to save and complete it at their convenience. Furthermore, the use of Google forms eliminated the possibility of ballot-box stuffing, one of the limitations of online surveys (Wright, 2005). As an additional benefit, it enhanced the assurance of respondent anonymity since responses were recorded directly on the webform, without the need for an email address. To spread out the questionnaires further, an effective snowball sampling method was used with the assistance of a first established resourceful contact with the researcher. Managers, middle managers, and frontline employees were the respondents to the research, as they are the employees performing the main duties and suffering the most stress from their jobs.

Impact of Covid-19 on Research

Throughout the world, the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted many common systems, including society, economy, health, environment, education, and politics. Additionally, it dissuaded traditional methods of conducting research, especially gathering data. The collection of data for research could have been easily accomplished through actual surveys, personal interviews, focus groups, and an extensive literature review prior to the pandemic. However, all of these became unworkable and difficult with the onset of the pandemic, primarily due to quarantine restrictions and other health protocols imposed by the local governments. Thus, the COVID-19 pandemic has created a challenging research environment (Dodds and Hess, 2020). Due to a lack of logistical support, researchers worldwide paused their work to eliminate unnecessary burden on respondents and participants, relieve themselves from possible health risks, and avoid unnecessary burden on respondents and participants (Townsend et al., 2020). In addition, Sy et al (2020) noted that many traditional data collection methods are becoming impractical as a result of physical distance, as research and academic staff work from home, often with a skeletal workforce,

hindering the progress of research initiatives. As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, local governments around the world have implemented strict social distancing and quarantine protocols. This presents a significant challenge in the collection of data using a traditional survey that involves individual interaction with many respondents. During the pandemic, this is strictly prohibited to prevent the spread of Coronavirus. Consequently, considering these limitations, an online survey becomes inevitable as a method of collecting data. In an online survey, respondents receive the instrument or questionnaire via an online platform. Even though personal distribution of surveys is desirable in order to improve response rates, electronic distribution is a very feasible alternative, given current restrictions (Sy et al., 2020).

4.8 Data Analysis

The questionnaire data was saved in an SPSS file for analysis, where several statistical tools were used, including t-tests, correlations, regressions, and ANOVAs. Generally, sampling distributions tend to be expected when sample sizes are large enough (Ghasemi and Zahediasl, 2012). For sample sizes greater than 50, it is not recommended to test for normality if there are no significant deviations from normality (Elliot and Woodward, 2007). An examination of the data revealed no significant deviations from normality. A significance level of 0.05 and 0.01 has been determined to be statistically significant for the data results. All variables were measured using descriptive statistics that derived minimums, maximums, means, and standard deviations. In addition to frequency distribution tables, a breakdown of the descriptive statistics for each scale item was calculated. The researcher examined high deviations in variable mean scores for the entire sample and variables based on demographic information. According to Cohen's (1988) interpretation, a correlation coefficient of 0.10-0.29 implies a weak association, 0.30- 0.49 implies a moderately significant association and 0.50-1 indicates a highly significant relationship.

Analysing data begins with preparing the data. It includes an explanation of the process by which user data was determined, how outliers were detected and handled, and how essential considerations concerning normality and bias were managed. Following the preparation of data and identification of a usable dataset, the next step was to investigate the reliability of the scales used (as discussed earlier in this chapter). Statistical packages for the social sciences (SPSS) were primarily used to analyse the data.

Since CFA is not available in SPSS, AMOS was used. It was necessary to perform several procedures for the preparation and cleaning of the data prior to the use of the data to test the hypothesised relationships to determine the appropriateness of the data for further processing in the subsequent steps. This analysis excludes answers with missing information. Data preparation begins with the identification of outliers. The second step is to assess the assumption that the data will be normally distributed. Lastly, tests are conducted to determine the statistical validity of the data. The concept of outliers must be understood since these are instances when data display a very high value compared to the overall data can cause errors in the evaluation and inferences derived from the data (Aguinis, Gottfredson and Joo, 2013; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). Also, inaccurate data entry, ambiguous data codes, sampling errors, or non-normal distributions can produce outliers (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) suggest screening the data for outliers. As a means of identifying possible outliers, this study observes Aguinis et al. (2013) in recognising possible errors resulting from inaccurate data entry or sampling. In contrast, SPSS identifies potential outliers within the normality analysis. Following Emerson and Strenio (1983), the standardised scores (z-scores) were analysed using Tabachnick and Fidell's (2007) approach. Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) define the term 'outlier' to refer to cases with z-scores greater than 3.29.

It is common, however, to find cases with z-scores above 3.29 in datasets with large sample sizes (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). No obvious errors were identified in an investigation of possible sampling errors or incorrect data entry. An analysis of the z-scores reveals eight cases with z-scores higher than 3.29. These cases were 17, 63, 74, 122, 151, 146, 148, and 174. A review of possible sampling errors or errors in data entry has not revealed any obvious errors in sampling. Each of the eight respondents is affiliated with a separate organisational unit.

Interestingly, these five cases appear to have reversed the general trend regarding the responses, i.e., where most respondents agree with the statements listed, these respondents appear to disagree. As a result, it may be possible to misinterpret the scale anchors, resulting in reverse responses. However, it is also possible that these respondents have chosen the statements with different ratings deliberately. The argument for conscientious rating is further supported by the fact that respondents identified the specific questions, suggesting an understanding of the scale

and engagement with the questionnaire. Aguinis et al. (2013) do not consider these outliers error outliers. The anonymity of the respondents prevents follow-up data collection, and the explanation for the extreme values is not identified.

Consequently, these responses were not included in the analysis. To identify the other outliers, the Mahalanobis distance was calculated. For the dataset of four variables, based on Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), the appropriate cut-off is 20.151 at $p < 0.001$. Two outliers were identified and removed from the dataset with Mahalanobis distances of 27.296 and 25.864. So, 200 employees make up the total employee sample size. Data was analysed using mainly the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) 23 including Hayes' process 2.16.3 plug-in for the moderated analysis. It was necessary to perform several data cleaning and preparation procedures prior to the data being used to test the hypothesised relationships. This was done to ensure that the data were suitable for the statistical analysis that would follow in the next steps. Missing data responses are already excluded from this analysis. Screening for outliers is the first step in the data preparation process. In the second step, we examine the assumption that the data will be normally distributed before considering potential bias due to non-response bias or single source bias. The data is then tested for statistical validity before being further analysed.

An analysis of simple linear regression was performed to answer the first research question. The results of this analysis provided insight into the influence of ethical leadership on employee job satisfaction and outcomes. For estimating the relationship between two quantitative variables, simple linear regression is used. Using simple linear regression is an effective method for determining the strength of the relationship between two variables. A multiple regression analysis was conducted to investigate and answer the second research question. The second research question pertains to the impact of organizational compassion as a moderator. Through multiple regression analysis, the researcher was able to determine the moderation influences of organizational compassion on the relationship between ethical leadership and employee job strain as well as the relationship between ethical leadership and employee outcomes. As part of the analysis of variance (ANOVA), a basic moderator effect was calculated and presented to illustrate the influence of organizational compassion on the interactions between independent and dependent variables.

4.9 Managing Bias

It is paramount to investigate any potential bias within the data during the data entry process. Common method bias is one the most frequently arising in the literature on leadership and employee outcomes. It is vital to consider common technique bias and its impacts because it might distort study results by exaggerating links between the variables, offering a different explanation for the associations that were measured, and so on (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Hassan et al., 2013). While many statistical methods are available for identifying and reducing bias, Harman's one-factor test is often adopted in employee outcomes and leadership research. According to Podsakoff et al. (2003), a research design that lessens the likelihood and possibility of common method bias creates the application of statistical processes largely redundant.

As for the research design, this study follows the suggestions of Podsakoff et al. (2003). In the first step, data for independent and dependent variables were initially accumulated from several sources; for example, managers provided data for independent variables, whereas employees provided data for dependent variables. By doing this, single source bias and its various causes—such as the need for consistency in their responses and the need to have underlying theories or assumptions represented in all answers were avoided.

Second, the data collection was divided into two rounds, separated by three weeks. This changed the scenario in which the data was obtained and avoided typical contextual cues and impacts. Third, the scale interpretations varied across the independent and dependent variables, despite using Likert scales. Fourth, the dependent variables were gathered using a 1 (never) to 5 (strong) measure, whilst the independent variable was collected on a 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) measure. In addition, every independent measure included a reverse-negatively phrased element to prevent automated responses and enhance participants' involvement in the survey (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

In the multisource sample of managers as well as the employee sample, these factors led to a variety of procedural and design elements aimed at reducing common method bias. It was examined whether there was a nonresponse bias in the employee data, which may occur when not all requests can or are willing to be fulfilled (Adams, Kahn, Raeside and White, 2007; Couper, 2000). Data from the employee database was reviewed for nonresponse bias, which may occur

when not all requested individuals can respond (Adams, Kahn, Raeside and White, 2007; Couper, 2000). Accordingly, SPSS was used to compare survey responses' first and final quartiles using t-tests with two samples for continuous or scaled data as well as chi-square tests.

The homogeneity of variance for the t-test was examined using Levene's test, which assumes equal variance for $p > 0.05$. Participants' answers were divided into quartiles primarily on the commencement time of the survey to evaluate early and late responders. Based on demographic characteristics, responses were evaluated. Regarding gender and educational attainment, the two groups (first and last quartile participants) were comparable; however, the evaluation revealed substantial variations in age ($\chi^2=12.2$, $df=4$, $p=0.015$). In contrast to early respondents, who were younger, who made up 25.9% of the late respondents, 47.6% were older than 45. The calculations demonstrate the fact that the late responses are frequently older. The measurement's key variables appear to be unaffected by this possible sampling bias.

4.10 Conclusion

Data have been collected through adopted questionnaires and exported all the material in SPSS software. Different analyses like frequency distribution of demographics, reliability, and correlation. Moreover, regression has been run through this software. Collected data are normal as the researcher checked the mean and standard deviation values. Data results have been significant at the 0.05 and 0.01 significance levels. Descriptive statistics tables were generated via SPSS, with minimum and maximum values of all the variables. Characteristics of most of the respondents were also analysed via frequency distribution tables. Extracted results show that most respondents are male and have master's degrees. In this chapter, with the usage of AMOS, the researcher has run a confirmatory factor analysis. In confirmatory factor analysis, the researcher dropped the items with less than 0.30 loads (Brown, 2006). Organisational compassion moderates the impact of ethical leadership on employees' level of job strain experienced. All hypotheses are accepted.

Chapter 5

Results

The purpose of this study was to determine the correlation between ethical leadership, employee work strain, and outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan. The goal of this chapter is to explain the findings of the research and the statistical procedures used. An evaluation of the demographic characteristics of participants is presented at the beginning of the chapter. Detailed analysis related to the relationship of the study variables is presented. Next, the testing hypothesis is followed to check the relations between variables. A description of data analysis and results, as well as statistical values, are provided in this chapter.

The participants' demographic information is depicted in Table [5.1], followed by the description of tools, reliability and validity testing of our tools, i.e., questionnaires used for this study. After testing convergence and reliability of scales, SPSS has been employed to run multiple regression and moderated regression analysis. Consequently, the results of this regression analysis helped to conclude the hypothesis of this study.

5.1 Demographic Analysis

The characteristics of respondents are summarised in Table [5.1] below (n=200) based on their gender (Male, Female), Age (25 years or less, 25-45 years, 45 years or older), Qualification (Graduation, Master's, MPhil), Designation level (front, middle, and senior level), and experience (5 years or less, five- ten years, eleven-fifteen years, fifteen years or more).

A healthy sample comprises male organisational employees (n=158, 79%). About 77.5 % (n= 155) of the respondents were between 25 and 45 years of age. Most employees (n=147, 73.5 %) have a master's degree or have completed 16 years of education. A total of 20 percent [n= 40] of the respondents had a 14-year education, while six percent (n= 13) had an additional master's degree or 18 years of education. Most respondents (n=86) work at middle and front management levels (front-level employees are directly involved in serving customers). The number of

employees employed at the senior level was only 18.4 percent (n=34), with 43 percent (n=86) working at the middle management level.

Table 5. 1: Demographics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	158	79
Female	42	21
Age		
Less than 25 years	22	11
25-45years	155	77.5
More than 45 years	23	11.5
Years of Education		
Graduation	40	20.0
Masters	147	73.5
M.Phil.	13	6.5
Management Level		
Front level	75	37.5
Middle level	86	43
Senior level	39	19.5
Experience		
Less than five years	61	30.5

5-10years	85	42.5
11-15years	23	11.5
More than 15 years	31	15.5

Concerning the length of the period respondents have been working in their organisations, 30.5% (n=61) reported less than five years, 42.5% of them (n=85) reported their experience of 5 -10 years, 11.5% (n=23) reported 11-15 years and 15.5% (n=31) reported extensive experience of more than fifteen years. Middle-aged respondents made up the majority of respondents. They are well educated, as analysed by socio-demographic analysis.

Employees of middle and upper-level management in organisations are respondents in this research. Regarding ethical leadership, respondents give feedback about their immediate supervisors, and their responses are based on their self-perception and experience of ethical leadership of their supervisors. Respondents detailed mentioned to whom they were going to give feedback and what are their experiences. Similarly, in case of job strain, employees have shared their experiences of job strain while working in the organisation. Demographics are depicted graphically in the form of bar charts in Figures [5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 and 5.5] below:

Figure 5. 1: Demographics of the respondents

Figure 5. 2: Age

Figure 5. 3: Management Level

Figure 5. 4: Experience

Figure 5. 5: Years of Education

5.2 The Instrument's Validity and Reliability

Checking both validity and reliability is a vital part of research work. Sometimes concerned data is reliable but not valid. So first, researchers must check the reliability of the data.

5.2.1 Ethical Leadership (EL)

In this study, Brown, Trevino, and Harrison's (2005) measurement tool for ethical leadership was used. It consists of ten questions. Whose answers were Poor, Fair, Acceptable, Good and Excellent (ranked 1 to 5 where one is taken as poor and five as excellent)? This tool is provided below in Table [5.2], along with the means and standard deviations of the responses to the questions.

Table 5. 2: Ethical Leadership Tool

	Ethical Leadership	Mean	St Dev.
1	“Listens to what employees have to say”.	4.175	1.14496
2	“Disciplines employees who violate ethical standards”.	4.06	1.02059
3	“Conducts his/her personal life ethically”.	3.65	0.69996
4	“Has the best interests of employees in mind”.	3.635	1.11264
5	“Makes fair and balanced decisions”.	3.915	1.04076
6	“Can be trusted”.	4.37	0.68955
7	“Discusses business ethics or values with employees”.	3.945	1.23271
8	“Sets an example of how to do things the right way in terms of ethics”.	3.59	0.83389
9	“Defines success not just by results but also by how they are obtained”.	3.76	0.91465
10	“When making decisions, asks, what is the right thing to do”?	3.845	1.24043

5.2.2 Employee's Outcome (EO)

The employee performance scale is adapted from Wiedower (2001), It has five areas, and answers again include five multiple choices 1 = Unsatisfactory to 5 = Excellent. This tool is given here in Table [5.3] with the mean and standard deviations of the answers by respondents.

Table 5. 3: Employees' Performance Tool

	Performance Area	Mean	St Dev.
1	Timeliness.	4.205	0.99898
2	Quality of work.	4.03	1.05101
3	Quantity of work.	3.43	0.91063
4	Need for Supervision.	3.695	0.93076
5	Interpersonal Impact.	3.845	1.10775

5.2.3 Employees' Job Strain (EJS)

In (1979) House, McMichael, Wells, Kaplan, and Landerman established the Organizational Strain Scale (EJS) adopted in this research. It has 15 items with five multiple choices from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree", ranking 1 to 5. These responses are given in Table [5.4], along with their means and standard deviations.

Table 5. 4: Job Stress Tool

	Occupational Stress Scale	Mean	St Dev.
	Task stress items:		
1	“Feeling you have too much responsibility for the work of others”.	2.07	1.31673

2	“Having to do things where mistakes could be quite costly”.	2.18	1.32529
3	“Not having help or equipment to get the job done well”.	2.435	1.23426
	Value-related items:		
4	“Thinking that the amount of work you have to do may interfere with how well it gets done”.	2.675	0.8907
5	“Feeling that you have to do things that are against your better judgments”.	2.5	1.1518
6	“Feeling unable to influence your immediate supervisor's decisions and actions that affect you”.	2.745	1.22371
	Role ambiguity items:		
7	“Thinking that you will not be able to meet the conflicting demands of various people you work with”.	2.63	0.92051
8	“Not knowing what the people you work with expectations of you”.	2.47	1.06526
9	“Having to deal with or satisfy too many people”.	2.54	1.12906
	Work and non-work issues:		
10	“Feeling that your job tends to interfere with your family life”.	2.185	1.14776
11	“Being asked to work overtime when you do not want to”.	2.2	1.41421
12	“Feeling trapped in a job you do not like but cannot get out of”.	2.13	1.27327
	Workload items:		
13	“How often does your job require you to work very fast”?	2.03	1.18156

14	“How often does your job require you to work very hard (physically or mentally)”?	2.36	1.16066
15	“How often does your job leave you little time to get everything done”?	2.14	1.2115

5.2.4 Organization Compassion (OC)

The organisational compassion scale was adopted by Worline and Dutton (2017). There are 16 questions in this tool for measuring compassion in the organisation and six other questions for demographic data. The questions have five possible answers ranking 1 to 5, representing "Never" to "Always". The trend of responses is noted through their means and variations in Table [5.5].

Table 5. 5: Organizational Compassion Tool

	Organisation Compassion Scale	Mean	St Dev.
1	“When I see someone in my organisation is hurting somehow, I feel comfortable offering assistance or help”.	4.44	0.54579
2	“In my organisation, people are expected to leave their emotions at the door and not share their troubles”.	4.2	0.80201
3	“When someone is in need, my organisation uses its communication channels, such as an internal newsletter, to notify members of ways we can help and support that person”.	3.68	0.88403
4	“The leaders in my organisation take time to talk and listen to people who are having a hard time”.	3.84	0.7858
5	“People in my organisation feel comfortable revealing that they are stressed out, suffering, feeling burdened, or experiencing hardships”.	3.93	0.97974

6	“When I feel distressed, I sense that others in my organisation feel concerned for me”.	4.48	0.50085
7	“I hear stories in my organisation about colleagues receiving support from one another during difficult times, such as through meals, cards, flowers, or other expressions of care”.	4.175	0.81714
8	“In my organisation, everyone is too busy to pay attention to whether someone is suffering or not”.	3.67	0.89167
9	“When my organisation is looking for new members, we discuss care and compassion as part of what makes someone fit”.	3.825	0.78579
10	“My organisation sponsors ways for us to help others in need, such as donation programs, fundraisers, financial support or vacation donation funds for colleagues”.	3.92	0.97897
11	“When someone at my organisation talks about his or her troubles, it makes other people anxious and wants to avoid that person”.	4.46	0.51937
12	“I feel that the leaders in my organisation support efforts to respond to someone who needs help or care”.	4.2	0.80201
13	“When I am in my organisation, I feel valued as a whole person”.	3.665	0.88128
14	“In my organisation, it is seen as a sign of weakness to ask for help, flexibility, or accommodations if someone is facing painful circumstances”.	3.855	0.77263
15	“When someone in my organisation expresses that they are having a hard time, most people believe they deserve a caring response”.	3.925	0.9768

16	“When people in my organisation help someone in need, they consider that individual's unique preferences and needs rather than responding more generically”.	3.665	0.88697
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5.2.5 Calculation of Cronbach's alpha for the validity of tools

It should be noted that all the scales used in this study are existing scales with a well-established reputation. However, Brace et al. (2009) recommend the analysis of scale reliability, regardless of whether the scale is constructed or already exists. An analysis was conducted here to determine whether the scales used in the study were reliable and valid. A scale's internal consistency is a measure of its ability to measure what it is meant to measure and is a requirement for high validity (Kline, 2000). Cronbach's alpha has been the most used measure of internal consistency and has received general approval (Boateng et al., 2018). Brace et al. (2009) and Boateng et al. (2018) recommend that the Cronbach alpha coefficient not fall below 0.7.

Analysing the data carefully, it was observed that mean of the responses not only shows the reliability of the tools used but also confirms the hypotheses tested for the relationships between the variables in the coming sections. As it can be seen that the mean responses of EL, EO and OC are slightly greater than the middle, showing agreement (positive relation between these variables), while the mean responses of EJS are slightly towards the lower side, showing a negative correlation of EJS with the others. The variation of the responses is not high, which also confirms the consistency of the items in the tools.

However, to ensure the validity of the tools, the researcher used the statistical procedures presented in the following sections. Therefore, before moving on to calculations, the researcher also checked the reliability of the questionnaires. To ensure reliability, one of the approaches widely used by researchers is Cronbach's alpha, which assesses the internal reliability of the tools used for the study (Cortina, 1993). Reliability analysis was run in SPSS. It is frequently used when multiple Likert queries in a survey questionnaire form a scale, and it is desired to ascertain the scale's reliability. The acceptable range of Cronbach Alpha is more than 0.6. If the values cross

0.8, then it is considered excellent values. Table [5.6] exhibits Cronbach's alpha for the four scales utilised in this research.

Table 5. 6: Validity and Reliability of Scale in Current Study

Scale Name	Number of Items	Cronbach Alpha
Ethical Leadership	10	0.905
Employee Outcome	5	0.754
Employee Job Strain	15	0.954
Organisational Compassion	16	0.719

All the scales used in this study have a Cronbach alpha value of at least 0.7, indicative of satisfactory internal consistency and reliability. A Cronbach alpha of 0.65 has been reported in earlier studies using similar instruments, suggesting that the low-reliability level may be due to the nature of the instrument (Wong et al., 2011). Additionally, an alpha of 0.6 is considered acceptable for scales with fewer than ten items (Ursachi et al., 2015; Loewenthal and Lewis, 2018). Cronbach's alpha for Ethical Leadership is 0.905 representing excellent consistency of the tool. The employee outcomes scale adopted by Wiedower (2001) and the value of Cronbach's alpha is 0.754.

As there are different sections in the EJS tool, the researcher has calculated the alpha for each section and the overall questionnaire. Coefficient alpha values ranged for employee strain cases from 0.747 to 0.9598. For responsibility pressure, it is 0.88; the alpha for quality concerns is 0.914, and it is 0.747 for role conflict. The value of alpha for a job vs non-job conflict item is 0.9598 and 0.9031 for workload strain. However, the overall alpha for all sections of this employee job strain measurement tool is 0.954, which proves its excellent consistency. Similarly, Cronbach's alpha for organisational compassion is 0.719 showing the acceptability and reliability of this instrument again.

5.3 Factor analysis

In the research, in-depth CFA was carried out on a sample of 200 responses, and the total number of factors extracted through confirmatory factor analysis was confirmed.

5.3.1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

To evaluate the research models, it is necessary to check confirmatory factor analysis on each variable using AMOS 21.

According to Byrne (2001), the consequences of confirmatory factor analysis indicated that the values of the model lie between satisfactory ranges. All the values meet the standard criteria.

5.3.2 Ethical Leadership

A necessary point in evaluating the conceptual models is that the reasonableness of the computed factors must be checked. The consequences of the Confirmatory factor study (CFA) showed one factor in the construct of ethical leadership. These components were additionally affirmed through a Confirmatory factor study by utilising AMOS 23. The development of ethical leadership (EL) was comprised of 10 items adopted from Brown, Treviño and Harrison (2005) to research the degree to which ethical leadership in employees can influence employee's job performance.

Criteria for removal of any item introduced by Brown (2006) that show the factor loading less than 0.30. The attempt was made, and a single factor was tried to demonstrate the effect of EL on dependent variables, as shown in figure [5.6]. Every one of the ten items was loaded on a “single factor”. A single-factor model produced favourable results, and the Chi-square value was near the good range as well. For holding items, the range of standardised factor loadings is from .37 to .84, which is a very satisfactory range.

Table [5.7] presents a Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Ethical Leadership. Table [5.8] represents the retained item of ethical leadership.

Table 5. 7: CFA of Ethical Leadership

Statistics	Index (Fit)	Threshold value (Adequate)	1 factor
Absolute Fit	χ^2	Zero or as close as possible	156.076
	DF	Zero or as close as possible	34
	CMIN/ DF	Low as two and high as five	4.5905
	GFI	More than .95	.957

Table 5. 8: Retained Items of Ethical Leadership

Item Number	Retained Items	Factor Loadings
L1	“Listens to what employees have to say”.	.54
L2	“Disciplines employees who violate ethical standards”.	.44
L3	“Conducts his/her personal life ethically”.	.39
L4	“Has the best interests of employees in mind”.	.37
L5	“Make fair and balanced decisions”.	.41
L6	“Can be trusted”.	.84
L7	“Discusses business ethics or values with employees”.	.73
L8	“Sets an example of how to do things the right way in terms of ethics”.	.51
L9	“Defines success not just by results but also by the way that they are obtained”.	.63

L10	"When making decisions, what is the right thing to do"?	.68
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Figure 5. 6: Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Ethical Leadership

5.3.3 Organization Compassion

The construct of organisational compassion comprised 16 items adopted from Worline and Dutton (2017) to explore the degree to which organisational compassion can influence an employee's job performance.

A single factor of items of organisation compassion was computed by AMOS and shown in figure [5.7]. Each of the 16 items was loaded on a single factor. After model specification, each item has a factor loading of more than the minimum value, so we retain all the items of organisational compassion. In the model specification, each item has a factor loading that exceeds the minimum value, so we retain all the items of organisational compassion. In the single-factor model, the results were perfect, and the Chi-square value was also within a reasonable range. A satisfactory range was determined by the standardised factor loadings single factor model, which ranged between .39 and .79.

According to Brown (2006), only those items will retain that show the factor loading value more than or equal to 0.30. table [5.9] shows a confirmatory factor analysis of organisation compassion, and Table [5.10] presents the retained items of organisation compassion.

Table 5. 9: CFA of Organization compassion

Statistics	Index (Fit)	Threshold value (Adequate)	1 factor
Absolute Fit	χ^2	Zero or as close as possible	561.153
	DF	Zero or as close as possible	119
	CMIN/ DF	Low as two and high as five	4.716
	GFI	More than .95	.843

Table 5. 10: Retained Items of Organization compassion

Item Number	Items Retained	Factor Loadings
OC 1	“When I see that someone in my organisation is hurting in some way, I feel comfortable offering assistance or help”.	.777
OC 2	“In my organisation, people are expected to leave their emotions at the door and not share their troubles”.	.803
OC 3	“When someone is in need, my organisation uses its communication channels, such as an internal newsletter or email update, to notify members of ways we can help and support that person”.	.623
OC 4	“The leaders in my organisation take time to talk and listen to people who are having a hard time”.	.598
OC 5	"People in my organisation feel comfortable revealing that they are stressed out, suffering, feeling burdened, or experiencing hardships".	.455
OC 6	"When I feel distressed, I sense that others in my organisation feel concerned for me".	.489
OC 7	“I hear stories in my organisation about colleagues receiving support from one another during difficult times, such as through meals, cards, flowers, or other expressions of care”.	.510
OC 8	“In my organisation, everyone is too busy to pay attention to whether someone is suffering or not”.	.551
OC 9	“When my organisation is looking for new members, we talk about care and compassion as part of what makes someone fit”.	.504
OC 10	“My organisation sponsors ways for us to help others in need, such as donation programs, fundraisers, financial support or vacation donation funds for colleagues”.	.660

OC 11	"When someone at my organisation talks about his or her troubles, it makes other people anxious and wants to avoid that person".	.557
OC 12	"I feel that the leaders in my organisation support efforts to respond to someone who needs help or care".	.591
OC 13	"When I am in my organisation, I feel valued as a whole person".	.580
OC 14	"In my organisation, it is seen as a sign of weakness to ask for help, flexibility, or accommodations if someone is facing painful circumstances".	.527
OC 15	"When someone in my organisation expresses that they are having a hard time, most people believe they deserve a caring response".	.442
OC 16	"When people in my organisation help someone in need, they consider that individual's unique preferences and needs rather than responding in a more generic way".	.425

Figure 5. 7: Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Organization compassion

5.3.3 Stress

According to House, McMichael, Wells, Kaplan and Landerman's (1979) scale, 15 items are selected to investigate how strain contributed to employees' job performance; confirmatory factor analysis is performed.

Factors establishing strain in employees were confirmed through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). A factor loading analysis of 15 items of job strain is shown in figure [5.8]. The CFA model produces highly satisfactory results, and the Chi-square value is very good. As can be seen in figure [5.8], the standardised factor loadings range for a single factor model is 1, which is a satisfactory range. .47 to .75 is a satisfactory range for standardised factor loadings single factor models. Table [5.11] presents a confirmatory factor analysis of job strain, and Table [5.12] presents retained items of job strain.

Table 5. 11: CFA of job strain

Statistics	Index (Fit)	Threshold value (Adequate)	1 factor
Absolute Fit	χ^2	Zero or as close as possible	368.778
	DF	Zero or as close as possible	90
	CMIN/ DF	low as Two and as high as Five	4.0973
	GFI	More than .95	.871

Table 5. 12: Job Strain retained Items

Item Number	Items Retained	Factor Loadings
S1	“Feeling you have too much responsibility for the work of others”.	.634
S2	“Having to do or decide things where mistakes could be quite costly”.	.681
S3	“Not having enough help or equipment to get the job done well”.	.668
S4	“Thinking that the amount of work you have to do may interfere with how well it gets done”.	.549
S5	“Feeling that you have to do things that are against your better judgment”.	.626
S6	“Feeling unable to influence your immediate supervisor's decisions and actions that affect you”.	.749
S7	“Thinking that you’ll not be able to meet the conflicting demands of various people you work with”.	.716
S8	“Not knowing what the people you work with expectations of you”.	.667

S9	"Having to deal with or satisfy too many people".	.605
S10	"Feeling that your job tends to interfere with your family life".	.680
S11	"Being asked to work overtime when you do not want to".	.737
S12	"Feeling trapped in a job you don't like but cannot get out of".	.673
S13	"How often does your job require you to work very fast"?	.750
S14	"How often does your job require you to work very hard (physically or mentally)"?	.592
S15	"How often does your job leave you little time to get everything done"?	.472

Figure 5. 8: Confirmatory Factor Analysis of job Strain

5.3.4 Employee's outcome

A CFA was conducted following the adoption of 5 items of employee outcome by Wiedower (2001). The results of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) confirmed factors that enhance employees' job performance. Figure [5.9] revealed factor loadings of employee outcomes in five items. The CFA model provided excellent results, with a Chi-square value in the very good range. Fig. [5.9] shows that the standardised array of loadings for a “single factor model” is 1, which is satisfactory. It is satisfactory that the limit of standardised factor loadings for the “single factor model” is between 0.51 to 0.70. Table [5.13] presents a confirmatory factor analysis of employee outcomes, and Table [5.14] presents retained items of employee outcomes.

Table 5. 13: Confirmatory Factor Analysis of employee outcomes

Statistics	Index (Fit)	Threshold value (Adequate)	1 factor
Absolute Fit	χ^2	Zero or as close as possible	14.502
	DF	Zero or as close as possible	5
	CMIN/ DF	low as two and high as five	2.9004
	GFI	more than .95	.991

Table 5. 14: Retained Items of employee's outcome

Item Number	Items Retained	Factor Loadings
EJP1	“Consider the degree to which an activity is completed, or a result produced at the earliest time desirable from the standpoints of coordinating with the outputs of others and maximising the time available for other activities”.	.511
EJP2	“Consider neatness, accuracy, and dependability of results regardless of volume”.	.582
EJP3	“Consider the volume of work produced under normal conditions. Disregard errors”.	.699
EJP4	“Consider the degree to which you carry out a job function without either having to request supervisory assistance or requiring supervisory intervention”.	.635
EJP5	“Consider the degree to which you promote feelings of self-esteem, goodwill, and cooperativeness among co-workers and leaders”.	.628

Figure 5. 9: Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Employees' outcomes

5.4 Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix

In this section, the average response score of each tool, their standard deviations and the correlation matrix for the main study variables have been calculated and presented in Table [5.15].

In the results, a strong positive correlation has been found between Ethical Leadership (EL) and Employee outcome (EOC). Between these two factors ($r=0.92$), EL has a robust negative correlation with Employee Job Strain, i.e., EJS has $r= -0.60$. A positive correlation can be seen between Organizational Compassion (OC) and EO ($r=0.59$), whereas EJS and OC are negatively correlated ($r=-0.10$), indicating that compassion reduces the employee's job strain. In addition, EO and EJS ($r=-0.53$) have a strong negative correlation, indicating that increased strain decreases employee outcomes. Moreover, the positive correlation ($r=0.44$) between the EL and OC explains that ethical leadership will give rise to organisational compassion. All these results lead to the design of the hypotheses in the current study. In the coming sections, the researcher has carried out the process of hypothesis testing to conclude which of these relationships are statistically significant.

Table 5. 15: Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlation Matrix

Variables	Mean	SD	EL	EO	EJS	OC
EL	3.8945	0.74268	1			
EO	3.841	0.7118	0.92	1		
EJS	2.35267	0.92457	-0.60	-0.53	1	
OC	3.99563	0.35651	0.44	0.59	-0.10	1

Note. **EL** = Ethical Leadership; **EOC** = Employee Outcomes; **EJS**=Employee Job strain; **OC**=Organizational Compassion.

5.5 Linear Regression Analysis

5.4.1 Simple Regression between EO and EL

In Table [5.16], simple regression analysis results are presented, taking ethical leadership (EL) as the individual factor representing the independent factor and employee outcomes "EO" as the dependent variable. This regression was run through "Statistical Program for Social Sciences (SPSS)". Model summary, its ANOVA table and regression coefficients of this model are presented in the following tables, and the results are explained.

The path coefficients depicted strong and statistically significant associations between EL and the EOC in the predicted direction. The value of R^2 tells us how much the considered independent variable explains the dependent variable's variation. In Table [5.16], the value of $R^2 = 0.853$ (85.3%) shows the highly explained variability of EO by EL. The standardised path coefficients displayed a strong and direct relationship of EL with EO ($\beta = 0.885$) as proposed in Hypothesis 1 of the following section. Table [5.17] shows ANOVA for EO on EL, whereas Table [5.18] shows coefficients of EO and EL, respectively.

Table 5. 16: Summary Statistic of Model EO on EL

Model 1	R	R²	Adjusted R²	Std Error
EO by EL	0.923	0.853	0.852	0.2738

Table 5. 17: ANOVA for Model 1 (EO on EL)

Model 1	SS	DF	MS	(F) Statistic	(p) value
Regression	85.977	1	85.977	1146.603	<0.001
Residual	14.847	198	.075		
Total	100.824	199			

Table 5. 18: Intercept and Regression Coefficient of Model 1

Model 1	Coefficients	Std. Error	t	Sig.
Constant	0.394	0.104	3.805	<0.001
EL	0.885	0.026	33.862	<0.001

Dependent Variable: EO

Using coefficients calculated in Table [5.19] above, model 1 can be written as:

$$EO = 0.394 + 0.885 * EL \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Figure 5. 10: Best Fit line of EO against EL

5.4.2 Simple Regression between EJS and EL

In model 2, a Simple regression analysis was run, taking ethical leadership "EL" as an independent variable where employee's job strain "EJS" is the dependent variable. This regression was again run through SPSS. The regression summary, ANOVA table and regression coefficients of this model are presented in the tables [5.19-5.21] below, and the results are interpreted.

Table 5. 19: Summary Statistic of Model 2(EJS on EL)

Model 2	R	R²	Adjusted R²	Std Error
EJS by EL	-0.6	0.36	0.354	0.743

Table 5. 20: ANOVA for Model 2 (EJS on EL)

Model 2	SS	DF	MS	(F) Statistic	(p) value
Regression	60.829	1	60.829	110.211	<.001
Residual	109.283	198	.552		
Total	170.112	199			

Table 5. 21: Intercept and Regression Coefficient of Model 2

Model 2	Coefficients	Std. Error	t	Sig.
Constant	5.252	0.281	18.682	<0.001
EL	-0.744	0.071	-10.5	<0.001

Dependent Variable: EJS

Using regression coefficients and intercept from Table [22], model 2 can be written as:

$$EJS = 5.252 - 0.744 * EL \tag{Eq. (2)}$$

Figure 5. 11: Best Fit line showing the effect of EL on EJS

Again, the path coefficients depicted strong and statistically important associations between EL and employee job strain in the predicted direction. In model 2, the value of R^2 shows reasonably explained variability of EJS by EL. The path coefficient displayed a negative relationship of EL with EJS ($\beta = -0.774$) as proposed in Hypothesis 2 of the following section.

5.4.3 Test of Significance for Simple Regression Models

Before the moderated regression analysis in the next section, which is the main theme of the current study, the researcher realised the need to test the statistical significance of both the above simple regression relations. Testing will be conducted on the following two hypotheses:

H-1. Ethical leadership has a positive impact on employee performance.

H-2 Ethical leadership has a negative impact on employees' level of job strain experienced.

For hypothesis 1, the ANOVA and coefficient tables already generated by SPSS in the simple regression analysis were used. If the t-value of a test is higher or the p-value is smaller, the test is considered statistically significant. From Table [5.20], the researcher noted that both constant and b have p-values of < 0.001 (and high t-values), so the coefficients are significant, and model 1 is statistically valid. It leads to the acceptance of hypothesis H-1, i.e., EL positively impacts EO.

Similarly, Table [5.20] and Table [5.21] verify the statistical significance of model 2, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis presented in H-2 as again having small p-values < 0.001 (and high t-values). So, it is also concluded statistically that EL has a negative impact on EJS.

5.6 Moderated Regression Analysis

The most widely used analytical testing technique for moderation is moderated hierarchical regression, the most specific testing technique for interactive term hypothesis (Arnold, 1982). This technique is designed to measure whether one single element or set of variables describes the variation's proportion over previous sets of variables (Memon et al., 2019). To test the hypothesis

and fully comprehend the deviation made, a contribution by independent and moderator variables, moderated hierarchical regression, was used. All predictor variables and moderators are mean-centred, and regression analysis employs standardised scores (Bolin, 2014). In three steps, the centred independent variables are introduced into the equation. Hayes and Rockwood (2017) demonstrate a moderated effect as the interaction terms compute significant variation in the variables. Therefore, change in R square, and F statistic is examined at each step.

For examining the collaborative effects of organisational compassion on job strain and outcomes, the methods proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986) are used. The three steps for measuring moderation are as follows:

1. Path – a, evaluating the influence of ethical leadership.
2. Path – b, evaluating the influence of Organisational compassion.
3. Path – c, the product of both a and b, i.e., ethical leadership and organisational compassion.

According to Baron and Kenny (1986) and evidence of moderation, the interaction of path a – c is significant ($p < 0.05$). With SPSS, hierarchical regression analysis was carried out based on this method to test the conceptual model presented in fig [5.12] below:

Figure 5. 12: Moderation Model.

5.5.1 Multiple Regression of EO on EL in the presence of OC

Multiple regression is run with ethical leadership and organisation compassion as independent variables, while employee job strain is taken as a dependent variable. The impact of

ethical leadership and organisational compassion can be observed on the dependent variable by the results of multiple regressions depicted in Table [5.22].

Table 5. 22: Summary Statistic of Model 3 (EO on EL and OC)

Model 3	R	R²	Adjusted R²	Std Error
EO	0.946	0.896	0.894	0.23125

Dependent Variable: EO

Predictors: (Constant), OC, EL

Tables [5.23-5.24] show the moderating effect of organisational compassion on EOC with the combined impact of EL. Here the values of coefficients, their standard errors, t-statistic and p-values for these variables are displayed. If we compare the values of r (0.946) and R² (0.896) of model 3 with the values of r (0.923) and R² (0.853) of model 1, it is noted that the relation of EO with EL is strengthened in the presence of OC. The increase in the value of R² shows that this moderated regression is more explained than the previous simple regression.

ANOVA table for Model 3 asserts the same conclusion that model 3 is more explained as the sum of the square of regression is increased from 85.977 to 90.289 while the sum of the square of residuals is decreased from 14.847 to 10.535.

Table 5. 23: ANOVA for Model 3

Model 3	SS	DF	MS	(F)Statistic	(P)value
Regression	90.289	2	45.145	844.205	< 0.001
Residual	10.535	197	0.053		
Total	100.824	199			

Dependent Variable: EO

Predictors: (Constant), OC, EL

The relationship of ethical leadership with Employee outcomes shows a co-efficient of 0.885, indicating a positive regression slope of the independent variable, and in the subsequent case showing 0.9815, indicating a considerable enhancement in outcomes which supports the hypothesis made in this research. The connection of organisational compassion with employee outcomes is also significantly positive ($b=0.615$, $p<0.001$). Using data depicted in Table [5.24] for hypothesis testing, the conclusion is drawn that the coefficient of all the variables in multiple regression is significant. It can be observed that compassion has significantly enhanced employee outcomes. This shows the significant and valuable effect of moderation.

5.5.2 Hypothesis Testing for Moderating Effect of OC on EO

To evaluate the significance of the moderation effect of OC on EO by EL, the researcher formally states the hypothesis as follows:

H-3 “Organisational compassion moderates the impact of ethical leadership on Employees' outcomes”.

As the p-value of the test is almost equal to zero, as seen from Table [5.24], it shows that regression with moderating effect is significant and cannot be ignored. Hence the hypothesis that organisation compassion moderates the effect of EL on EOC is also valid.

Table 5. 24: Multiple regression analysis of EO by EL and OC

Antecedent	Consequent							
	Y(EO)				Y (EO)			
		Co-efficient	SE	(P) value		Co-efficient	SE	(p)value
X (EL)	A	0.885	0.0267	<0.001	C	0.9815	0.2122	<0.001
M (OC)		-----	-----	-----	B	0.615	0.129	<0.001
		$R^2 = 0.853$				$R^2 = 0.896$		

5.5.3 Multiple Regression of EJS on EL in the presence of OC

Using simple linear regression, the coefficient $b = -0.744$ indicates that ethical leadership negatively impacts employee job strain. In Table [5.25], we have already given the R-square value of 0.36 for this regression showing that the regression relation between these variables is 36.0 % well explained.

Table 5. 25: Summary Statistic of Model 4 (EJS on EL and OC)

Model 4	R	R²	Std Error
EJS	0.628	0.363	0.723

Dependent Variable: EJS

Predictors: (Constant), OC, EL

This coefficient of ethical leadership becomes -0.86 when related to employee strain (showing a negative effect) in the presence of a moderator variable, i.e., compassion. The small p-value (< 0.00001) shows the significance of this coefficient, and the p-value for the coefficient of the interaction term has also shown significance.

Similarly, in the case of the relationship between organisational compassion and employee job strain, a negative relationship can be observed as ($b = -0.553$). R-square value shows that by changing one per cent, there must be a change of 39% in another variable. This shows that the moderator variable has enhanced the negative influence on employee job strain, i.e., employee job strain. The relationship presents in Table [5.26].

Table 5. 26: Multiple Regression Analysis of Employee's Job Strain

	Consequent							
	Y(EJS)				Y (EJS)			
Antecedent	Co-efficient	SE	(P) value		Co-efficient	SE	(p) value	

X (EL)	A	-0.744	0.071	<0.001	C	-0.86	0.077	<0.001
M (OC)		-----	-----	-----	B	-0.553	0.16	<0.001
		$R^2 = 0.36$				$R^2 = 0.394$		
	$F=110.21, p = <0.001$				$F =64.143, p = <0.001$			

Dependent Variable: EJS

Predictors: (Constant), OC, EL

5.5.4 Hypothesis Testing for the Moderating Effect of OC on EO

Then multiple regression is run with ethical leadership and organisation compassion as independent variables, while employee strain is taken as the dependent variable. Here in this section, the statistical conclusion is drawn based on the process of hypothesis testing for the following hypothesis:

H-4 “Organisational compassion moderates the impact of ethical leadership on employees' level of work strain experienced”.

Table 5. 27: Regression Coefficients of EJS by EL and OC

Variables	Co-efficient	Std. Error	(t)value	(p)value
Constant	3.494	0.577	6.053	<0.001
EL	-0.860	0.077	-11.215	<0.001
OC	-0.553	0.160	-3.460	<0.001

Dependent Variable: EJS

Table [5.27] displays the values of coefficients, their standard errors, and t-statistic and p-values for these variables. Using data generated in Table [5.28] for hypothesis testing, the conclusion is drawn that the coefficients of all the variables in multiple regression are significant. Hence it is confirmed that organisation compassion (t-value = -3.46 and p-value < 0.01) is also significant, and it moderates the ethical leadership’s impact on employee strain. The increase in

the coefficient value for EL from -0.774 to -0.86 shows that the moderator variable has enhanced the negative effect on the dependent variable, i.e., employee job strain. Hence the conclusion of the study is achieved.

5.5 Summary

Table 5. 28: Summary of Results for the Research Hypotheses

H1	“Ethical leadership has a positive impact on employee outcomes”.	Accepted
H2	“Ethical leadership has an indirect and opposite influence on employees’ level of job strain experienced”.	Accepted
H3	“Organisational compassion moderates the influence of ethical leadership on employees' outcomes”.	Accepted
H4	“Organisational compassion moderates the impact of ethical leadership on employees' level of job strain experienced”.	Accepted

This chapter presents mean values, standard deviations, and correlations. The results indicated a strong connection between EL and EOC ($R = 0.6$, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, a regression model was applied, resulting in an R^2 of 0.896, confirming the validity of hypothesis H1. According to the results of the study, there is a correlation between leadership and job strain.

The second hypothesis suggested that EL is indirectly correlated to the job strain of an employee. As the researcher predicted, EL was inversely linked with employee job strain ($R^2 = 0.36$, $P < 0.001$). The presence of ethical leadership negatively impacts job strain in a significant way. This finding underscores the importance of the behaviour of senior managers in Islamic banks

of Pakistan for the behaviour of their subordinates. A sense of security is gained when an employee knows that their boss values ethics, avoids unethical behaviour, does not endorse double standards, and appreciates truthfulness and honesty. This gives them a sense of peace, knowing they are in good hands and will be treated fairly if there are any issues. Hence, by practising ethical behaviours, supervisors can directly impact the job strain experienced by customer-contact employees.

The third hypothesis suggests a moderated effect. To test the moderation of indirect relationships, SPSS was utilised. Since moderation was predicted to affect the interactions among the variables, multiple correlation analysis was chosen for the data analysis. Regression coefficients that do not contain 0 indicate significant regression. Table [5.24] presents the results. Based on the results shown in Table [5.24], organisational compassion has a significant moderating effect between EL and EOC ($R^2 = 89\%$). The fourth hypothesis predicts that organisational compassion moderates the indirect association between EJS. Interaction effects are significant in the results ($\beta=0.55$, $p=0.001$) and a significant moderated effect (86%). The research results support the conclusion that organisational compassion completely moderates the association between EL and employee level of job strain and outcomes. Hypotheses 3 and 4 were supported.

Chapter 6

Discussion

6.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the data analysis and results presented in the previous section are discussed. The purpose, methodological approach, and findings are reviewed concisely. The results are described in detail in the previous chapter. In this section, results are clarified in terms of their possible explanations by evaluating the hypotheses proposed in the research. The main objective of this research was to assess the ethical leadership influences on employees' job strain and their consequential outcomes also, the moderating impact of organizational compassion on the association between EL and EJS and OC. In general, the relationships proposed in the theoretical model are supported by the data analysis.

6.2 Ethical Leadership and employee outcomes

Workers must be adequately trained to complete day-to-day tasks more effectively for better outcomes. How can workers be skilled enough to enhance their personal and organizational performance? A strong management plan developed by leaders can provide a competitive advantage in achieving distinctiveness among employees (Hassan, 2007). Aguinis (2009) argues that the outcome measure focuses only on the behaviour itself and not the outcome of the behaviour. The worker's output reflects his or her work-related behaviour and contributes to the overall organizational success. Descriptive, operational, and motivational understanding contribute to a worker's superior performance (Ahmad and Shahzad, 2011). Asencio (2019) contend that leadership practices result in beneficial effects, manifesting themselves in employee actions, proving a positive relationship between them. According to Malik et al. (2016), effective leadership must evolve for employees' progress in an organization. Ethical leadership is a powerful tool for attracting employees' optimum abilities and expertise (Ouma, 2017). As a result, employees authorized by ethical leadership can be efficient in raising their personal and organizational outcomes.

This research investigated ethical leadership influences on employee outcomes. It established a substantial direct association between the two variables, 75%, which means that

ethical leadership affects employee outcomes by 75%, which is considerable for organizations to take notice of. These results are compatible with most earlier research conducted in various contexts worldwide (Abbas and Yaqoob, 2009; Bass, 1985; Trevino, Hartman and Brown, 2000), where ethical leadership has been explored as a major factor affecting employee job strain and outcomes. Ethical leadership's impact on employee outcomes is quite notable in this study. These findings were suggested by Kefela (2010). These impacts follow research published by Selart (2010), which observed a high association between ethical leadership and employee outcomes with $r = 0.9$, $p < 0.01$. The regression analysis was used, and the results were $R \text{ square} = 0.9$ and $F \text{ value} = 7.0$, $p < 0.01$, demonstrating the direct link between EL and EOC. The literature supports the research findings and confirms the positive influence of EL on EOC. Considerable research contribution in this regard has been completed by other scholars (Walumbwa, 2012; Bello, 2012; Sabir et al., 2012; Obicci, 2015). The positive connection between ethical leadership and employee outcomes has also been investigated by researchers in academia. Kelidbari, Fadaei and Ebrahimi (2016) conducted research at Guilan University and confirmed the clear impacts of EL on EOC. Research conducted in the developmental sector in Pakistan also revealed the same correlation between ethical leadership and employee outcomes (Sheraz, Zaheer and Nadeem, 2012).

Ethical leaders are strong advocates who perform an effective role within organizations by providing dedicated support to their workers to assist them in achieving personal and organizational goals (Day, Zaccaro and Klimoski, 2001). The study results showed that ethical leadership is clearly correlated with employee performance. Particularly, the present study's findings revealed that EL was significantly connected with employee outcomes. It can be concluded that when leaders in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector displayed greater ethical behaviour, their employees performed more effectively at their jobs. Accordingly, the results support the researcher's hypotheses. The published research on ethical leadership confirms the findings of the current study. According to a study conducted by Detert et al. (2007), leadership assists workers in exploring and improving their capabilities to contribute to the achievement of the organization's objectives.

According to Brown and Trevino (2006), ethical leadership highlights fairness, equality, common interests, and truthfulness in personnel activities. As a result of ethical leaders, employees are empowered to engage in positive behaviours, their sense of loyalty to an organization is

strengthened, and their perceptions of the nature of their work are altered. Following the literature, this study demonstrated the importance of ethical leadership in improving employee outcomes.

The research findings align with previous scholars who argue that leadership behaviour was a significant factor in determining job satisfaction and perceived performance (Hernandez, 2008). In addition, Walumbwa et al. (2009) emphasized the importance of supervisors as they can influence their employees' perceptions and motivate them to perform well at work. The research findings are consistent with the numerous studies over the past few years, which have demonstrated the relevance of ethical leadership in influencing others' outcomes (Trevino et al., 2003; Kanungo, 2001). EL is characterized by delegating authority to subordinates and engaging them in the managerial process (Brown et al., 2005). Consistent with Elci et al. (2012) findings, ethical leadership negatively correlates to work-related strain. In addition, ethical leadership is crucial at all levels of the organization, but immediate supervisors have a tremendous effect on employee ethical behaviour since they are the ones who direct employees to adhere to the values of the organization (Mayer et al., 2009). DeConinck (2015) suggests that ethical leadership influences the attitude and behaviour of employees at work.

According to Mayer et al. (2009), executive ethical leadership flows to workers via supervisors' ethical leadership. Brown et al. (2005) demonstrates in their study that many critical employee outcomes are positively influenced by ethical leadership. A study by Piccolo et al. (2010) revealed a connection between ethical leadership and employee motivation. The conclusions of Schwepker and Dimitriou (2021) suggest that ethical leadership perspectives enhance psychological safety, thereby promoting employee voice. The findings and literature thus ascertain the acceptance of the first hypothesis that ethical leadership is directly correlated with employee outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan.

6.3 Ethical leadership and employee job strain

As a result of major shifts in society, policies, economics, and business settings over the last decade, education has skyrocketed, technological breakthroughs have appeared, and multinational corporations have entered the marketplace, putting massive pressure on labour standards and affecting the economy globally and regionally.

Excessive job requirements and a rapidly changing environment have caused higher levels of strain among employees in all sectors in Pakistan. Ethical leadership is attempting to significantly reduce high levels of pressure, as argued in this research project. In today's work environment, employees are under great strain. Strain at work affects employees physically and mentally, but it also significantly impacts organizations. The goal of this research was to establish if there is a link between ethical leadership and employees' perceptions of job strain.

The research findings showed that employees would experience less strain at the workplace if leaders exhibited ethical behaviour. In terms of demonstrating consideration, ethical leaders can help employees relieve work strain by treating them fairly, establishing effective communication, and ensuring appropriate job autonomy.

The primary goal of this study was to expand on previous work strain research by looking into the influences of EL on employees' perceptions of JS. The study discovered a substantial understanding of the entire hypothesis and concerns raised in the research. According to the study's findings, employees in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan witnessed job strain ranging from mild to intense levels due to various work-related activities, and ethical leadership has a significant negative correlation with job strain. The ratio is 79%, which means that almost 79% of the job strain is decreased and managed by applying ethical leadership practices, which is very considerable to notice. These findings, therefore, confirmed the acceptance of a second hypothesis according to which ethical leadership is negatively correlated with employee job strain in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan.

This study confirms the findings of Kirkpatrick and Locke (1996) and Al-Dmour and Awamleh (2002) studies which also resulted in numerous workplace outcomes, such as work motivation and employee productivity, that are directly linked to ethical leadership and employee job strain. The finding of this study on ethical leadership will impact employee job strain which is also consistent with the study of Avolio and Gardner (2005), who observed an indirect association between ethical leadership and job strain. The study revealed how ethical leadership exerts a powerful negative influence on job strain. Theoretically, ethical leaders foster encouragement through their behaviour and priorities. However, the social learning theory states

that ethical leaders serve as role models, providing guidelines and demonstrating behaviours that employees can emulate, enhancing the influence of leadership (Mendonca, 2001).

The negative correlation between EL and employee job strain is also confirmed by the research conducted by Schwepker and Dimitriou (2021) in the health service. So, the results of this research comply with their research. The researcher also tested the influence of EL on followers by proposing job strain as a mediator (Elçi et al., 2012) and revealed the significant impact of EL on turnover intentions and job strain. According to the findings, employees who take aspirations from their supervisors are more willing to handle pressure at work. The findings of this study are in accordance with those of Schwepker and Ingram (2016) conducted in the business sector. They proposed a test model, investigated the impacts of ethical leadership in creating customer value and job strain, and reported notable ethical leadership. According to the findings, workers are more likely to participate in related tasks when they trust their supervisors.

This result is supported by Chen et al. (2008), who stated that trusting leaders who are better able to build respect and understanding enhance employee outcomes. Michaelis, Stegmaier and Sonntag (2009) predicted that employees would form associations with leaders who were considered sincere or trustworthy. According to the findings of this study, employees who perceive their leaders to be trustworthy are more likely to remain committed to the organization. Similarly, Fritz et al. (2013) reported an association by referring to trust as a critical characteristic of a leader that aids in developing organizational commitment in employees. Ethical leadership is a significant source of reducing job strain in the organization. Researchers have presented the results, which confirm that employees who experience less than genuine ethical behaviour feel job strain (Kim and Brymer, 2011). When employees are treated equally and with respect, they are recognized as human capital and appreciated as intellectual assets in the organization. (Fang, Gao and Hu, 2021). This acknowledgement becomes the source of reduction in their job strain (Ramlawati et al., 2021). They feel connected, emotional and socially secure (Ettah and Gbolagade, 2021). This relationship is empirically tested and described in a study conducted by (Ponnu and Tennakoon, 2009).

6.3 Organizational compassion and employee job strain and outcome

The goal of this study was to provide organizations with valuable suggestions; consequently, it was necessary to identify objectively the other aspects that contribute to job strain management in order to initiate effective strain management and effective strategies for the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan, the banking sector in general, and general business organizations. Therefore, in this study, organizational compassion was identified and measured as a moderating factor in ethical leadership and employee job strain and outcomes. An organization's compassion emphasizes both organizational interest and individual interest.

These organizations play a vital role in supporting the achievement of their strategic objectives under contexts that vary from time to time. Ethical values are constructive in all ways, not only for individuals but also for organizations (Ahmer et al., 2021). When an employee experiences job strain in their organizations, one of the reasons behind it is a lack of social support (Jimmieson et al., 2021). Organizations can provide progression to employees by providing social support instead of inducing a feeling of being deprived of psychological well-being (Frost and Harris, 2003).

Indeed ethical values and organizational compassion practices provide social security, a chance for improvement, feelings of belonging, self-determination and competence to the employees (Rego and Cunha, 2008). According to Alessandri, Caprara, Eisenberg, and Steca (2009), experiencing compassion can boost perceptions of self-achievement as a capable participant. People with feelings of high self-achievement are more effective in successfully utilizing and developing resources in their work to achieve complex tasks (Schaubroeck and Merritt, 1997). People who receive compassion are more capable of resolving perceived threats and strainful circumstances, according to Lawton (2015), suggesting that workers who self-identify as potent and effective because of sharing compassion are more likely to be able to resolve a crisis or adapt to the emotional exhaustion of their job (Heuven, Bakker, Schaufeli, and Huisman, 2006). To put it another way, those who show compassion to others may be able to improve their job performance by raising their self-perceived efficacy.

Organizational compassion may also elicit pleasant feelings, influencing the provider's performance. Delivering compassion in the workplace can be viewed as a necessary affective

experience that, once started, can elicit other pleasant emotions (Weiss and Cropanzano, 1996). People's feelings in their connections with others are increased when they show compassion, resulting in positive attitudes (Dutton, 2003). Compared to individuals who do not have a highly positive mood, those with generally favourable feelings perform better at work (Chu, 2016). In conclusion, because delivering compassion to others produces desirable results such as feelings of self-efficacy and positive emotions, delivering compassion in the workplace may increase an employee's job performance. Chu (2016) discovered that employees treated with compassion in the workplace perform better. This study also supports these findings, whereby employees who are frequently shown compassion in their workplace perform better in their job.

The study results show a strong direct link between organizational compassion and employee outcomes, plus a robust negative correlation between organizational compassion and employee work strain. The moderating impact of organizational compassion between EL and EOC was observed to be enhanced from 5.6% to 6.1%, which shows that employee outcomes are raised to 61% because of organizational compassion. These results are similar to a study conducted by Samaie and Farahani (2011) in which compassion is a moderating factor between the association of self-reflection and strain. The results state that compassion moderates the relationship from 3.2% to 4.1%.

Similarly, the solid moderating effect of organizational compassion is observed between ethical leadership and employee job strain as job strain reduced to -2.9 from -1.4%. The empirical findings of this study also corroborate the same observation made by other researchers (Way and Tracy, 2012; Canevello and Crocker, 2011; Mikulincer et al., 2001). However, in Pakistan, it is essential to note that the configuration of all variables in equipping levels of job strain and work outcomes are not the same.

The correlation between employee outcomes and the ethical leadership coefficient shows a fair, encouraging association between EL behaviours and EOC in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan; thus, the objective of this research is established and achieved. Based on the material and results, the connection between EL and EOC, involving job strain and organizational compassion, is profound and moderates between ethical leadership, employees' job strain, and outcomes.

The analysis reveals that ethical leadership, if practised correctly, can significantly impact employee outcomes. Research has shown that ethical leadership promotes consciousness, employee morale, and self-reliance on knowledge and understanding, consequently leading to maintenance, motivation and achievement of the organization's overall goals (Toor and Ofori, 2009; Jing and Avery, 2008). Ethical leadership is a powerful tool for attracting personnel with the best expertise and capabilities (Bakar and Akyürek, 2021). So, the employees motivated by EL can be valuable to enhance the outcome levels of the organization.

Consequently, all the hypotheses of ethical leadership, employee outcomes, and employee job strain were significantly correlated, as previously stated by Caldwell et al. (2007). Research has shown that corporate ethical values significantly affect organizational leadership (Saha et al., 2020). Corporate ethical values are essential for the organization's leaders to perform at their best. Organizational ethical standards can be used for various purposes, one of which is to address ethical concerns among the organization's employees (Dion, 2017).

In fact, by providing a supportive working culture in the workplace, managers can improve their effectiveness and decrease occupational strain, which is critical for an organization's sustenance and development. One possible explanation for the elevated level of job strain experienced by the workforce in Pakistan could be that Pakistan is supposed to be a society where individualism and collectivism are commonplace, with social homogeneity and connectedness required as a casual part of the culture. Managers must deal with diverse human resources from various cultures, beliefs, and orientations to build and maintain this harmony. Managing a diversified workforce is difficult; it can increase job strain. To the researcher's knowledge, no other research has examined the interactive effects of organizational compassion, ethical leadership-job strain and outcomes relationships previously in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan; As a matter of fact, this study is significant in a way that it allowed the researcher to fill a gap in recognition of the dynamics of ethical leadership and employee job strain, outcomes and organizational compassion in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan.

Organizational compassion moderates the relationship between ethical leadership and employee job strain indicate that there will be a negative relationship between organizational compassion and employee job strain was supported where a significant and negative correlation

was found ($r = -0.247$, $p = 0.026$). The findings indicate that organizational compassion from organizational sources is negatively associated with employee level of sufferings. For instance, compassion from managers but not from co-workers correlated significantly and negatively with feeling 'worried or anxious. This provides support to a study that reported a negative relationship between total compassion at work and job strain (Choi et al., 2016). The finding is relevant to previous research that suggests that support from superiors is critical for a balanced work-personal life and reduced inter-role conflict (Allen, 2001) which consequently is associated with lower anxiety (Kossek & Cynthia, 1998). Furthermore, organizational compassion connects people, allowing for a closer relationship between employees and their supervisors which was found to be significant in reducing the degree of stress, role conflict and role ambiguity (Coelho et al., 2011). On the other hand, compassion from co-workers correlated significantly and negatively with feeling hopeless, lonely, abandoned, and rejected. The findings are significant in that they suggest that organizational compassion may be related to a wider array of psychological symptoms that may not be exclusively work related, thus, contributing to the literature that tended to focus on work related negative experiences such as anxiety, stress or burnout.

6.4 Summary

To summarize, organizational compassion significantly moderates the connection between EL, job strain, and outcomes. This result is supported by published studies, where a trustable, inspiring, and collaborative environment lowers job strain and strengthens overall outcomes (Bouckenooghe, Zafar and Raja, 2015; Vigoda-Gadot, 2007; Asrar-ul-Haq and Kuchinke, 2016). Management may want to consider gentle and more collaborative, people-oriented strategies in the workplace environment in corporations with highly bureaucratic or demanding, assertive, innovative cultures to enhance effectiveness by reducing strain levels. Overall, the findings support the hypothesis that supportive organizational compassion exists, primarily in interaction with ethical leadership, which may lower the job strain of employees and hence improve outcomes. Employees who demonstrate elevated levels of commitment to their jobs, as evidenced by productive work, a feeling of togetherness, astonishment, pleasure, and correlation, will be less prone to job strain if the organizational compassion is interpreted as nurturing supportive values and norms. As a result, the connection between EL, job strain and EOC are far more noticeable in

organizational cultures with instilled values such as collaboration, encouragement, and inspiration. Consequently, ethical leadership alone is insufficient to improve employee outcomes; favourable management values such as organizational compassion are also necessary.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

This section describes the study's limitations, conclusions, and future directions. The primary goal of this research was to shed light on the association between ethical leadership and employee outcome and job strain, as well as the moderating effect of organisational compassion in the Islamic Banking sector of Pakistan.

7.1 Reiterating the Research Questions

Considering the goal mentioned earlier, the following specific questions were investigated.

1. What is the influence of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes in the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan?
2. Does organisational compassion moderate the effect of ethical leadership on employee job strain and outcomes?

7.2 Overall Research Conclusions – Summary of Findings

This research intended to determine the association between ethical leadership and employee work strain and overall outcomes in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector. Aside from the preceding, the current research investigated the role of organisational compassion as a moderating element in the correlation between EL and EJS and OC.

Based on previous research, this study confirms the connection between leadership and employee outcomes. Likewise, Gumusluoglu and Jiang et al. (2015) found that transformational leadership was associated with positive employee outcomes. Ethical leaders significantly impact employees' overall performance by incorporating shared visions, openness to change, individualised treatment considerations, and motivation to carry out innovative and productive avenues. Ethical leaders motivate employees through their behaviour, but they also serve as examples based on social learning theory (Bandura, 1971), providing guidelines and modelling behaviours that employees can emulate, increasing ethical leadership's effectiveness. This study

also investigated the impact of ethical leadership on employees' job strain. As a result of the study, ethical leadership is negatively linked to work strain. Ethical leaders establish the requirements for elevated employee outcomes by creating a more engaging and stress-free environment. The literature on EL and EJS is comprehensive (e.g., Schwepker and Dimitriou, 2021; Arjenaki and Dalvi, 2014; Zhou and Jin, 2015; Kim and Kim, 2020; Quade, Perry and Hunter, 2019; Shoul and Hakimi, 2018). Overall, the results of this study confirm the indirect association between EL and EJS, which is consistent with findings reported in the existing literature.

On the other hand, the literature on organisational compassion as a moderator is limited to date. While organisational compassion can be theoretically linked to ethical leadership using the Effective Events theory (Weiss and Cropanzano, 1996), no studies have been conducted in this respect. The results of this research provide a valuable addition to the existing literature by establishing a relationship between EL and EJS, and OC via organisational compassion, implying that organisational compassion influences play a significant part in enhancing the influences of ethical leadership.

Previous research looked at a variety of contextual moderators in the relationship between EL and EJS and OC, such as organisational commitment (Elik, Dedeolu, and Inanir, 2015), trust (Chughtai and Byrne, 2015), employee voice (Avey and Palanski, 2012), and psychological empowerment (Qing, Asif, Hussain and Jameel, 2020). However, this study focused on organisational compassion, an unexplored variable as a moderator. As discussed in the literature review, organisational compassion truly concentrates on the assistance given and received within relationships between supervisors and coworkers, resulting in high levels of cooperation and information exchange, innovativeness, engagement, professional growth, and trust (Madden and Duchon, 2012; Lilius, Kanov and Dutton, 2012; Neikam, 2017). Using the concept of organisational compassion as a moderator in the ethical leadership influences extends the current body of knowledge.

As a moderator in the study, organisational compassion significantly contributed to the indirect link between ethical leadership and employee work strain. Similarly, the interaction effect demonstrates that organisational compassion added valuable significance to the relationship between EL and EOC. According to the findings, stronger collaboration between leader and

follower leads to less fatigue and more efficient individual performance, while establishing organisational compassion leads to a stronger bond between the ethical leader and follower.

One of the key findings in this study, which addresses the knowledge gap identified in chapter one, is the negative relationship between EL and EJS in eastern culture. This adds to the body of knowledge on ethical leadership and works strain, particularly on the eastern side, which has been underserved by research scholars. In terms of investigating the connection between EL and EOC, this study somewhat mirrors related literature on the above variables by demonstrating a positive relationship between EL and EOC.

There have been few studies on leadership and job strain in Pakistan's banking sector and none in the Islamic banking sector. Similarly, most studies on ethical leadership and work strain are conducted in the Western world. Prior research, however, focused primarily on establishing a link between leadership and strain. As a result, this study has gone above and beyond in filling a research gap by looking at the impact of EL on EJS and overall outcomes in eastern culture, specifically in Pakistan's Islamic banking sector. None of the previous studies on ethical leadership and work strain has looked at organisational compassion as a moderator in this relationship, and the current study is the first to include organisational compassion as a moderating factor in the literature on ethical leadership, work strain, and employee's job outcomes in the context of Pakistan's Islamic banking sector. Thus suggesting one of the desired implementation of organizational compassion along with ethical leadership practices to address effectively the main issue of strain and performance in this sector.

Examining the impacts of EL on both job strain and work outcomes was critical. This has been addressed in the current research to better understand the connection between ethical leadership, strain, and outcomes. Additionally, organisational compassion has been postulated as a distinct component that has proven to be a key moderator in this relationship.

Ethical leadership, along with organisational compassion, is highly effective support in reducing employee job strain. The need for high performance of employees has become essential for organisations all around the world, and the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan is not exempt. In this scenario, the enhancement of employee outcomes by reducing their job strain is not only in favour of the employee but the overall wellbeing of the sector. The reliable interaction between

the two dimensions' ethical leadership and organisational compassion especially suggested that high coordination between these two dimensions could aid not only the Islamic banking sector but the entire business industry in Pakistan. Hence, it is suggested that organisational compassion, along with ethical leadership behaviour, is a driver for enhancing employee outcomes by significantly reducing job strain. The findings address this gap in the literature and provide empirical evidence of a considerable association between ethical leadership relationships. The confirmation of previously unexamined interactive effects of organisational compassion on job strain and employee outcomes has opened the door for additional ethical leadership theory expansion. There is a need to better understand when and under what conditions ethical leadership and organisational compassion affect workplace strain and employee outcomes.

The findings of this study are also confirmed by various assertions and recommendations mentioned by Brown and Trevino (2005). Brown and Trevino (2006) predicted early that ethical leaders employ moral foundations to enhance the productivity of individuals and overall organisations. The entire set of hypotheses established for the evaluation is correlated significantly with one another. Organisational compassion is the most powerful factor among the factors that impact and moderate ethical leadership to enhance the outcomes of employees and significantly reduce the job strain experienced by them at the workplace. The study also showed that ethical leadership and organisational compassion are ubiquitous. Despite cultural differences, organisational compassion and ethical leadership have a unifying impact on human nature. It nourishes, heals, comforts individual interactions, and has a universal effect on people. It is a communication of love and affection that has the same effects on everyone, regardless of culture.

Organisations must keep their employees in a learning environment. As a result, leaders and organisational employees must work together to know and understand moral standards and behave to improve their outcomes. These morally acceptable and compassionate principles are critical for organisational success. The study's findings revealed the ethical dimension as the most dominantly perceived type of organisational management of the Islamic Banking sector in Pakistan, followed by supportive measurement. The least perceived management type was the ethical aspect. The perception of ethical leadership might be the nature of the whole Islamic banking sector which is oppressed due to job strainers such as high demands, strict deadlines and cutthroat competition (Pradhan, 2021). Some job strainers are associated with a power-dominated

culture, resulting in task discrimination, stiff competition, huge challenges, and pressures to meet expectations (Badawy and Schieman, 2021).

In this study, ethical leadership and organisational compassion weakened the adverse effects of job strain and supportive culture lessened the negative effects. Therefore, ethical leadership in the workplace reduced the job strain experiences of staff and concluded that their outcomes could be fostered by creating supportive management of organisational compassion that, as a result, may lead to individual and organisational effectiveness. As previous studies on compassion in organisations reveal it as a constructive and very influential element (Miralles-Armenteros et al., 2021; Schabram and Heng; Graham, 2021), compassion is proved to be one of the chief elements of this study as well. Incorporating its organisational framework along with ethical leadership practices can prove to be most crucial in solving strain-oriented issues in organisations and can provide the lost sense of belongingness and commitment in stressful circumstances (Neubert et al., 2009), which can enhance the outcomes of the employees (Kanov et al., 2004).

The literature review identified that traditionally, ethical leadership has been fundamentally linked to job strain. Ethical leadership showed compatibility along organizational compassion concept. The recent emerging expanded view of compassion that addresses both suffering and wellbeing. Nevertheless, these conceptual views of compassion have not been tested empirically. Furthermore, and in relation to the context of this study, the review has identified that little is known about Islamic banking sector's employee job strain and experiences of organizational compassion. This study aimed to fill these gaps by examining relationships between ethical leadership, employee job strain and outcomes at Islamic banking sector of Pakistan. The study included four variables, one independent which is ethical leadership, two dependents which are employee job strain and outcomes and one moderator which is organizational compassion. variables were measured using existing, valid, and reliable instruments. The key findings of the study showed a substantial negative relationship between ethical leadership and employee job strain, a direct relationship with employee outcomes, and a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between organisational compassion, employee job strain and outcomes. Study found that if leaders in Islamic banking exhibit ethical behavior the employees perform effectively. Key findings include that ethical leadership in Islamic banking promote fairness, equality, and

commitment in employees. Employees feel less stressed when managers in Islamic banking establish effective communication and ensure job autonomy. Study found that the employees who take inspiration from ethical behavior of leader are more willing to handle job pressures. Research results found organizational compassion to be the most significant variable in the entire relationship. Organizational compassion strengthened bond between ethical leader and follower and promote feeling of connectedness. Organizational compassion enhanced the influences of ethical leadership to significant level.

7.3 Theoretical Implications

The findings of this study have extended current research on ethical leadership knowledge and made a significant contribution. The basic concept of ethical leadership's influence on followers was presented by Brown (2005) on the bases of two primary theories. The first is the social exchange theory (Blau, 1964), and the second is the social learning theory (Bandura, 1977). This study makes significant contributions along this line, linking ethical leadership. First, this study discovered organisational compassion as a significant intervening factor in the ethical leadership and outcome relationship, which is coherent with Brown's theorising. This study makes important contributions along this line, linking ethical leadership. The study found organisational compassion to be a significant intervening factor in the ethical leadership and employee outcome link, consistent with Brown's theory.

Therefore, it lends support to the knowledge of ethical leadership by empirically assessing the social perspectives that demonstrate the ethical leadership–employee outcome relationship. Study results empirically assist the significance of the connection between EL and EJS and the moderating effect of organisational compassion. This study's findings provided an empirical contribution to the significance of conceptualisations of leadership with a moderating role of organisational compassion. According to the researcher's best knowledge, no empirical investigation has explored the influence of ethical leadership on job strain in which organisational compassion worked as a moderating factor in the context of the Islamic banking sector of Pakistan. This study contributes grist to the growing body of scholarly research involving leadership, job strain, and organisational compassion, particularly concerning Islamic banking. Therefore, this research aimed to clarify the nature of the connections between various work experiences and a

critical occupational health outcome: job strain. Coupling the study of the ethical leadership domain with occupational health outcomes is an important theoretical development in management literature.

7.4 Practical Implications

The finding of significant direct influence involving ethical leadership and organisational compassion on job strain and outcomes of employees has practical implications for leaders to concentrate their efforts to boost workplace morale. Compassion-boosting programs have a solid potential to facilitate compassionated experiences by providing freedom of expression to each employee to share his/her personal views on compassion and by respecting each employee's ethical values. Moreover, Some practices of organisational compassion at the workplace include sharing knowledge, organising meditation spaces, and displaying emotional wellbeing and stability initiatives for individuals in the workplace (Krishnakumar and Neck, 2002). In order to attain maximum benefits, awareness workshops and seminars have great potential to facilitate organisational compassion at work (Bell and Taylor, 2004; Zaidman and Gidoni, 2021).

According to the study's findings, leaders should intend to inspire their followers and participate with one another, thereby creating a team atmosphere and providing employees with the opportunity to utilise their abilities and collaborate more effectively. Following Spell et al. (2014) conceptualisation and recommendations, leaders must provide adequate support to followers, such as mentorship or coaching, professional development, and task assistance. Similarly, they should create a stress-free working environment where coworkers support one another. Ethical leaders are in an excellent position to model and implement required behaviour as social learning theory states that followers look to their trusted leaders to demonstrate such behaviour. The implications for ethical leaders are equivalent to those for HR professionals involved in leadership advancement within their companies. Identifying the impact of ethical leadership on employee outcomes permits future leadership aspirants and practices to be evaluated and tailored. This will enable them to focus on and meet the behaviours necessary for fostering organisational performance. This would lead to the selection of ethical leaders within the organisation, establishing a guideline for positive leadership that the organisation strives to achieve.

This study suggests that ethical leadership responds to calls for elevated amounts of moral behaviour and achieves higher levels of individual outcomes, especially in an environment where a high level of ethical leadership has been required in the wake of corporate scandals. This exploration can be valuable to organisations in dynamic sectors in making a case for more ethical leadership that goes beyond ethics and responsibility, which could therefore help implement ethical leadership in the organisation and help develop leadership skills.

Furthermore, confirming the unexamined interactive relationships of ethical leadership and organisational compassion at work has opened the door for further research and broadened workplace management. The results of moderation impact indicated that supportive organisational compassion actions strengthen the relationship between employment outcomes and stress reduction at work. Besides focusing on the means to develop and foster employees' experiences of stress at work, organisations may better help the employees by lessening the effects of job strain by creating a supportive culture of ethical leadership and organisational compassion. HR departments may benefit from this study by promoting those core beliefs about organisational compassion that are reliable, communitarian, empowering, people-oriented, and collaborative. As a result of these beliefs, a feeling of individual liberation is generated, which can restore employee motivation and confidence at work and reduce employee strain.

Rather than formulating a shift in overall strategy and behaviour patterns, organisations can bring positive changes in their approach by implementing compassionated values (Bishnoi, Gupta and Mathews, 2012).

The conclusions and results generated from this study will be constructive for not only Pakistan's Islamic banking sector, but all business sectors and industries will also benefit by enhancing the outcomes and wellbeing of their human resources, especially in the fields of HRM and HRD. By promoting organisational ethics and compassion, employee-based strategies can significantly improve organisational planning and implementation. The formulation of these strategies can be facilitated by identifying and revealing the distress of employees at work. This study can assist in evaluating the association between organisational compassion and job strain.

7.5 Study limitations

This research yields startling contributions in the context of ethical leadership, its impact on job strain and the moderating role of organisational compassion in affecting this relationship. These, however, are supplemented by some restrictions. First, demographic factors may have an impact on the results. For example, males predominated in a chosen sample, raising questions about whether the same results would be obtained with a different gender composition.

Given that all variables are measured within the same sector, it was entirely justified to consider the effects of common method bias. Although this study investigated all the variables of interest, the survey was limited primarily in the questions it could include. Further research could investigate differentiating compassion perspectives for those who receive, deliver, and observe it, as well as distinguishing between individual and collective organisational compassion. Furthermore, the study did not account for other variables related to organisational compassion, such as the leader's personality traits (Dutton et al., 2014). Future research should therefore endeavour to diagnose the influence of other variables.

7.6 Directions for Future Research

This study encourages future research endeavours to replicate findings regarding the conceptual distinctiveness of the ethical leadership and organisational compassion construct and to confirm hypotheses in different job settings. The results of these hypotheses can also be compared between private and public sector banks. Organisational compassion at work is a novel concept; it is possible to obtain valuable observations by investigating how compassion at work affects various attitudinal and organisational outcomes in different cultural contexts. Future studies might also look into the differences in feedback to the variables studied within and between various groups of people from different backgrounds and demographics.

In addition, longitudinal designs might generate a meaningful analysis of the impact of ethical leadership and organisational compassion. Further studies may also investigate potential moderators and mediators like the organisational culture on ethical leadership dimensions and outcomes other than those investigated in this study, such as intentions to quit or organisational citizenship behaviours and so on in different cultural contexts. Another interesting area of research is to examine other potential moderators such as other leadership styles, organisational structure,

and contextual factors which might mitigate this effect. In addition, this study adopted a positivistic stance and led to quantitative research, and more insights could be explored by taking the stance of qualitative research in this regard.

Future research may investigate emotional forms of organisational compassion (Chen et al., 2016), which will logically differ in expertise. The positive emotion resulting from social events and non-social activities operate differently (Gilbert, 2009). Future research may establish this more strongly. As a result, researchers interested in studying organisational compassion should distinguish between the various sources of organisational compassion and further investigate how various forms and competence of organisational compassion relate to distress and outcomes. To examine the influence of organisational compassion on negative affect via the mediating role of positive affect, future research would need to gather data at different points in time in order to acquire longitudinal variation of variables and give enough time for personal resources to accumulate, possibly months apart (Fredrickson et al., 2008).

This research did not extend the investigation to employee job satisfaction. Previous research suggests that organisational compassion and job satisfaction are positively related. The positive relationship between life fulfilment and job satisfaction has been well documented (Thoresen et al., 2003; Bowling et al., 2010), lending support to the "spillover theory," which implies that positive interactions at work spill over into positive outcomes in other areas of life (Judge and Watanabe, 1994; Bowling et al., 2010). However, there are multiple alternative explanations in the literature on the job satisfaction relationship, with some claiming that positive work experiences may not positively influence other life domains. This highlights the need for additional research into the three-way relationship between organisational compassion, job satisfaction, and wellbeing.

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Annexure-A

Anx- A: Consent Form

Consent Form to Participate in a Research Study

Title of the Study: Impact of Ethical leadership on Employee Job Stress and Performance; moderating role of organizational compassion Empirical evidences from Islamic Banking sector of Pakistan

Principal Investigator: Zoofishan Hayat. Doctoral candidate. University of The West of Scotland Paisley Campus.

INTRODUCTION:

You are invited to participate in a research study. Before you agree to participate in this study, you should know enough about it to make an informed decision. If you have any questions, ask the investigator. You should be satisfied with the answer before you agree to be in the study.

BACKGROUND/PURPOSE:

The purpose of this study is to provide empirical support and generate evidences regarding influences of ethical leadership and organizational compassionate practices on employees' work stress and performance with in Islamic banking sector of Pakistan.

INFORMATION:

If you agree to participate in the study, you will be asked to complete the following:

1. Sign two copies of the consent form, one for you and the other copy to be kept by the principal investigator.
2. Complete the demographic data collection tool
3. Complete two questionnaires relating to your work experience as registered employee in your current employment.
4. Place completed questionnaire.

Participation in this study will involve about 15-20 minutes for the completion of the study instruments.

ALTERNATIVES TO PARTICIPATION:

The research is completely voluntary. There are no alternatives to participation.

RISKS:

There are no known risks by participating in this study.

BENEFITS:

Participation in this study may not benefit you directly. However, the knowledge that we obtained from your participation will benefit the employees in the future by better understanding of the contributors towards aim of research.

Initials: _____

ANONYMITY:

This research is anonymous. Anonymous means that I will record no information about you that could identify you. This means that I will not record your name, address, phone number, date of birth or any information that may be directly linked to you.

COMPENSATION:

For participating in this study you will not receive monetary compensation. You will be given a small token in appreciation for completing the questionnaire. You may withdraw from the study prior to its completion without penalty or risk to present or future employment in the Islamic Banking Sector.

COST STATEMENT:

There will be no cost to you for participating in this research.

CONTACT:

If you have questions at any time about the research or the procedures, you may contact the researcher, Zoofishan Hayat at [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

PARTICIPATION:

Your participation in this study is voluntary; you may decline to participate at any time without penalty to you. If you decide to participate, you may withdraw from the study at any time without penalty and without loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. If you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed your data will be removed from the data set and destroyed.

Sign below if you agree to participate in this research study. You will be given a copy of this form to keep.

Subject's signature _____ Date _____

Investigator's signature _____ Date _____

Annexure-B

Anx- B: Ethical Leadership Scale

Ethical leadership scale by (Brown, Treviño & Harrison, OBHDP, 2005)

	Excellent	Good	Acceptable	fair	poor
1. Listens to what employees have to say	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
2. Disciplines employees who violate ethical standards	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
3. Conducts his/her personal life in an ethical manner	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
4. Has the best interests of employees in mind	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
5. Makes fair and balanced decisions	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
6. Can be trusted	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
7. Discusses business ethics or values with employees	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
8. Sets an example of how to do things the right way in terms of ethics	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
9. Defines success not just by results but also the way that they are obtained	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
10. When making decisions, asks "what is the right thing to do?"	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

Annexure-C

Anx- C :Organization Compassion Scale

ORGANIZATION COMPASSION SCALE

1. When I see that someone in my organization is hurting in some way, I feel comfortable offering assistance or help.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

2. In my organization, people are expected to leave their emotions at the door and not share their troubles.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

3. When someone is in need, my organization uses its communication channels, such as an internal newsletter or email update, to notify members of ways we can help and support that person.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

4. The leaders in my organization take time to talk and listen to people who are having a hard time.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

5. People in my organization feel comfortable revealing that they're stressed out, suffering, feeling burdened, or experiencing hardships.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

6. When I feel distressed, I have the sense that others at my organization feel concerned for me.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

7. I hear stories in my organization about colleagues receiving support from one another during difficult times, such as through meals, cards, flowers, or other expressions of care.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

8. In my organization, everyone is too busy to pay attention to whether someone is suffering or not.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

9. When my organization is looking for new members, we talk about care and compassion as part of what makes someone fit.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

10. My organization sponsors ways for us to help others in need, such as donation programs, fundraisers, or financial support or vacation donation funds for colleagues.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

11. When someone at my organization talks about his or her troubles, it makes other people feel anxious and want to avoid that person.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

12. I feel that the leaders in my organization support efforts to respond to someone who needs help or care.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

13. When I am in my organization, I feel valued as a whole person.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

14. In my organization, it is seen as a sign of weakness to ask for help, flexibility, or accommodations if someone is facing painful circumstances.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

15. When someone in my organization expresses that they are having a hard time, most people believe they deserve a caring response.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

16. When people in my organization help someone in need, they consider that individual's unique preferences and needs rather than responding in a more generic way.

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Often

Always

17. I have been a recipient of compassion in my organization.

Yes

No

18. My organization is primarily a/an:

Business

Charitable Organization

Community Service Organization

Educational Institution

Governmental Agency

Health Care Provider

Legal/Criminal Justice Organization

Media Organization

Place of Worship

19. For how long have you been a member of this organization?

Less than 6 months

6 months to 2 years

2 to 5 years

5 to 10 years

More than 10 years

20. Approximately how many people belong to your organization?

Fewer than 10

11-50

51-100

101-1,000

1,001-5,000

More than 5,000

21. What is your gender?

Female

Male

22. What is your age?

Under 18

18 - 29

30 - 39

40 - 49

50 - 59

60 - 69

70 or Over

Annexure-D

Anx- D :Job Strain Questionnaire

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. Feeling you have too much responsibility for the work of others.	1	2	3	4	5
2. having to do or decide things where mistakes could be quite costly	1	2	3	4	5
3. Not having enough help or equipment to get the job done well.	1	2	3	4	5
4 thinking that the amount of work you have to do may interfere with how well it gets done.	1	2	3	4	5
5. feeling that you have to do things that are against your better judgement.	1	2	3	4	5
6. feeling unable to influence your immediate supervisor decisions and actions that affect you.	1	2	3	4	5
7. thinking that you'll not be able to meet the conflicting demands of various people you work with.		2	3	4	5
8. not knowing what the people you work with expect of you.	1	2	3	4	5
9. having to deal with or satisfy too many people.	1	2	3	4	5
10 feeling that your job tends to interfere with your family life.	1	2	3	4	5
11. being asked for work overtime when you don't want to.					
12. feeling trapped in a job you don't like but can't get out of.					
13. how often does your job require you to work very fast?					

Annexure-E

Anx- E :Employee Job outcome Scale

Employee Job Performance Scale

<p>INSTRUCTIONS</p> <p>Please respond to each of the items below by circling the one number that most closely describes the extent to which you agree or disagree with the statement.</p>	1 = Unsatisfactory	2	3 = Satisfactory	4	5 = Excellent
<p>TIMELINES:</p> <p>Consider the degree to which an activity is completed, or a result produced, at the earliest time desirable from the standpoints of coordinating with the outputs of others, maximizing the time available for other activities.</p>	1	2	3	4	5
<p>QUALITY OF WORK:</p> <p>Consider neatness, accuracy, and dependability of results regardless of volume.</p>	1	2	3	4	5
<p>QUANTITY OF WORK:</p> <p>Consider the volume of work produced under normal conditions. Disregard errors.</p>	1	2	3	4	5
<p>NEED FOR SUPERVISION:</p> <p>Consider the degree to which you carry out a job function without either having to request supervisory assistance or requiring supervisory intervention.</p>	1	2	3	4	5
<p>INTERPERSONAL IMPACT:</p> <p>Consider the degree to which you promote feelings of self-esteem, goodwill, and cooperativeness among co-workers and leaders.</p>	1	2	3	4	5

Note: Employee Performance Scale is adapted from Wiedower, K. A. (2001). A shared vision: The relationship of management communication and contingent reinforcement of the corporate vision with job performance, organizational commitment, and intent to leave [Doctoral dissertation]. UMI: 3030139